

Austria

Trends and Sources of Zoonoses and Zoonotic Agents in Humans, Foodstuffs, Animals and Feedingstuffs

including information on food-borne outbreaks,
antimicrobial resistance in zoonotic and indicator bacteria
and some pathogenic microbiological agents

in 2016

Preface

This report is submitted to the European Commission in accordance with Article 9 of Council Directive 2003/99/EC¹. The information has also been forwarded to the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA).

The report contains information on trends and sources of zoonoses and zoonotic agents in Austria during the year 2016.

The information covers the occurrence of these diseases and agents in humans, animals, foodstuffs and in some cases also in feedingstuffs. In addition the report includes data on antimicrobial resistance in some zoonotic agents and indicator bacteria as well as information on epidemiological investigations of food-borne outbreaks. Complementary data on susceptible animal populations in the country is also given. The information given covers both zoonoses that are important for the public health in the whole European Union as well as zoonoses, which are relevant on the basis of the national epidemiological situation.

The report describes the monitoring systems in place and the prevention and control strategies applied in the country. For some zoonoses this monitoring is based on legal requirements laid down by the European Union legislation, while for the other zoonoses national approaches are applied.

The report presents the results of the examinations carried out in the reporting year. A national evaluation of the epidemiological situation, with special reference to trends and sources of zoonotic infections, is given. Whenever possible, the relevance of findings in foodstuffs and animals to zoonoses cases in humans is evaluated.

The information covered by this report is used in the annual European Union Summary Reports on zoonoses and antimicrobial resistance in 2016 that are published each year by EFSA.

As of July 5th, 2017

¹Directive 2003/99/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 December 2003 on the monitoring of zoonoses and zoonotic agents, amending Decision 90/ 424/ EEC and repealing Council Directive 92/117/EEC, OJ L 325, 17.11.2003, p. 31

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2. Information on the Reporting and Monitoring System

Country: Austria

Reporting Year: 2016

This report was prepared by the Departments for Statistics (STA) and Data Management (DAM) of the Business Area Data, Statistics and Risk Assessment (DSR) of the AGES. Following Institutions and Laboratories were involved:

Institutions and laboratories involved

Authorities		
Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
Central Veterinary Services	Federal Ministry of Health and Womens's Affairs (BMGF)	Data concerning notifiable zoonoses in animals; Revision of the draft of the Trend Report; Approval of the Trend Report for Submission
Food Office	Federal Ministry of Health and Womens's Affairs (BMGF)	Revision of the draft of the Trend Report
DG Public Health	Federal Ministry of Health and Womens's Affairs (BMGF)	Validation of data concerning notifiable zoonoses in humans and food borne outbreaks; revision of the draft of the Trend Report
Feed Office	Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry, the Environment and Water management	Revision of the draft of the Trend Report
Provincial Veterinary Services	Nine provinces, one Veterinary Service per province	Data concerning notifiable zoonoses in animals
Local/District health authorities	Part of each local administration authority ("Bezirksverwaltungsbehörde"); one physician per district	Collection and entry of the data concerning notifiable zoonoses in humans and food borne outbreaks

Institutes		
Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
Department for Statistics and the Department for Data Management of the Business Area Data, Statistics and Risk Assessment (DSR)	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Compilation, validation, preparation, data entry and submission of the Zoonoses Trend Report (Reporting officer, national reporters); analysis of laboratory results for antimicrobial resistance of <i>Salmonella</i> spp., <i>Campylobacter</i> spp., and <i>E. coli</i> ; mapping of food and feed data; creation of xml-files, upload of data to DCF
Statistics Austria	The independent and non-profit-making federal institution, Statistics Austria, provides data on the economy, demography, environment and social and cultural situation in Austria to federal bodies. Federal agencies can then implement controlling measures in the scientific community, business and public institutions.	Demographic and livestock census data

Human Medicine		
Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
Department for Infectious Epidemiology Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Vienna	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning notifiable zoonotic diseases in humans and food borne outbreaks
National Reference Centre for <i>Salmonella</i> Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning salmonellosis in feedingstuff, animals, foodstuff and humans, and antimicrobial susceptibility testing
National Reference Centre for <i>Campylobacter</i> , Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning <i>Campylobacteriosis</i> in humans, speciation of <i>Campylobacter</i> from food and animals, and antimicrobial susceptibility testing
National Reference Laboratory for antimicrobial resistance, Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning antimicrobial susceptibility testing

Human Medicine		
Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
National Reference Centre for Tuberculosis, Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Vienna	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning tuberculosis in humans
National Reference Centre for <i>E. coli</i> including VTEC Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Typing of VTEC from humans, food and animals
National Reference Centre for <i>Listeria</i> Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Vienna	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning listeriosis in humans
National Reference Centre for <i>Yersinia</i> , Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning yersiniosis in humans
National Reference Laboratory for Brucellosis, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control (IVET), Moedling	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning brucellosis in humans and animals
National Reference Laboratory for Rabies, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control (IVET), Moedling	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning rabies in humans and animals
Toxoplasmoselabor und Nachsorgeambulanz Toxoplasmose, Diagnostik in der Schwangerschaft und kindliches Follow-up, The Austrian Toxoplasmosis Register, Klinische Abteilung für Neonatologie, pädiatrische Intensivmedizin und Neuropädiatrie, Department of Pediatrics and Adolescent Medicine	Medical University of Vienna	Data concerning toxoplasmosis in humans

Food Control Institutes		
Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
Official Food Control Laboratories (ILMU)	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES; Laboratories in Graz, Innsbruck, Linz, Salzburg and Vienna	Data concerning investigations in foodstuffs
Food Safety Department of the City of Vienna	Regional Food Laboratory	Data concerning investigations in foodstuffs
Institute for Environment and Food Safety of the State of Vorarlberg	Regional Food Laboratory	Data concerning investigations in foodstuffs
Carinthian Institute for Food Analysis and Quality Control	Regional Food Laboratory	Data concerning investigations in foodstuffs
National Reference Centre for <i>Salmonella</i> Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning salmonellosis in feedingstuff, animals, foodstuff and humans, and antimicrobial resistance testing
National Reference Laboratory for <i>Campylobacter</i> , Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning <i>Campylobacteriosis</i> in humans, speciation of <i>Campylobacter</i> from food and animals, and antimicrobial resistance testing
National Reference Centre for <i>E. coli</i> including VTEC Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Typing of VTEC from humans, food and animals
National Reference Laboratory for <i>Listeria</i> Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning listeriosis in food
National Reference Centre for <i>Yersinia</i> , Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning yersiniosis in food

Veterinary Medicine		
Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
Department for Veterinary Microbiology (VEMI) Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning monitoring programmes in animals
National Reference Laboratory for Tuberculosis in animals, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control (IVET), Moedling	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning tuberculosis in animals
National Reference Centre for <i>Salmonella</i> Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning salmonellosis in feedingstuff, animals, foodstuff and humans and antimicrobial resistance testing
National Reference Laboratory for <i>Campylobacter</i> , Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning <i>Campylobacteriosis</i> in humans, speciation of <i>Campylobacter</i> from food and animals, antimicrobial resistance testing
National Reference Laboratory for Antimicrobial resistance, Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Testing for antimicrobial resistance of <i>E. coli</i> from animals
National Reference Centre for <i>E. coli</i> including VTEC Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Typing of VTEC from humans, food and animals
National Reference Laboratory for Brucellosis, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control (IVET), Moedling	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning brucellosis in humans and animals
National Reference Laboratory for Trichinellosis in Animals, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control (IVET), Innsbruck	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning trichinellosis in animals
Institutes for Veterinary Disease Control (IVET)	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES; Laboratories in Innsbruck, Linz and Moedling	Data concerning investigations in animals; bacteriological investigation in slaughtered animals

Veterinary Medicine		
Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
National Reference Laboratory for Rabies, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control (IVET), Moedling	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning rabies in humans and animals
Austrian Poultry Health Data (PHD)	Association installed by law, running different programs e.g. <i>Salmonella</i> control and hygiene programs, Control of veterinarians and poultry farmers	Data concerning the Austrian poultry industry

Feed Control Institute		
Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
Institute for Animal Nutrition and Feed, Linz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning feeding stuff
National Reference Centre for <i>Salmonella</i> Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning salmonellosis in feedingstuff, animals, foodstuff and humans, and antimicrobial resistance testing

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AGES	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety
EHEC	Enterohemorrhagic <i>E. coli</i>
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
EMS	Epidemiological Notification System for human notifiable diseases ("epidemiologisches Meldesystem")
BMGF	Federal Ministry of Health and Women's Affairs
ILMU	Official Food Control Laboratories, AGES
IMED	Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, AGES
IVET	Institute for Veterinary Disease Control, AGES
NRC	National Reference Centre
NRL	National Reference Laboratory
OIE	World Organisation for Animal Health
PHD	Poultry Health Data
RDNC	reaction pattern does not conform to the phage scheme
TESSy	the European Surveillance System
VIS	Veterinary Information System
VTEC	Verocytotoxin producing <i>E. coli</i>

3. Animal Populations

3.1. Information on susceptible animal population

Sources of information

The independent and non-profit-making federal institution, Statistics Austria, provides data on the economy, demography, environment and social and cultural situation in Austria to federal bodies. Federal agencies can then implement controlling measures in the scientific community, business and public institutions. The data for this report are available from an online database established by Statistics Austria. Herds, flocks, holdings and stocks: The number of holdings and animals is based on the yearly full survey for pig, sheep and goats of the Veterinary Information System (VIS).

Poultry: The numbers of holdings, flocks and animals presented here are part of the *Salmonella* control program and are based on the Poultry Health Data. In Austria there are also holdings with a small number of animals that are not covered by the *Salmonella* control program and these numbers of holdings, flocks and animals are not presented in the following table.

Cattle, Equids: The number of slaughters is based on a monthly/yearly statistic of all examined slaughters (reported by veterinarians), performed by Statistics Austria.

Pigs: The number of slaughters is based on a monthly/yearly statistic of all examined slaughters (reported by veterinarians), combined with not-examined slaughters (out of pig-random-sample-surveys) performed by Statistics Austria.

Sheep & Goats: The number of slaughters is based on an expert-model carried out by Statistics Austria.

Dates the figures relate to and the content of the figures

Data are received from Statistics Austria, only poultry data from Poultry Health Data.

Definitions used for different types of animals, herds, flocks and holdings as well as the types covered by the information

Cattle: BGBl. II Nr. 163/2012 (Statistiken über den Viehbestand)

Swine, Sheep and Goats: BGBl. II Nr. 291/2009 (Tierkennzeichnungs- und Registrierungsverordnung 2009)

National evaluation of the numbers of susceptible population and trends in these figures

Nil

Geographical distribution and size distribution of the herds, flocks and holdings

Pigs: 97.25 % of all pigs are kept in 82.53 % of the holdings that are located in the 4 provinces Carinthia, Lower Austria, Upper Austria and Styria;

Sheep: 74.78 % of the sheep holdings are located in the 4 provinces Lower Austria, Upper Austria, Styria and the Tyrol; 72.81 % of the sheep are kept there.

Goats: 69.55 % of the goat holdings are located in the 4 provinces Lower Austria, Upper Austria, Styria and the Tyrol; 77.86 % of the goats are kept there.

Solipeds: 67.81 % of the soliped holdings are located in the 4 provinces Lower Austria, Upper Austria, Styria and the Tyrol; 70.92% of the solipeds are kept there.

Deer: 89.30% of the deer holdings are located in the 4 provinces Carinthia, Lower Austria, Upper Austria and Styria; 90.14% of the deer are kept there.

Cattle: 71.64% of the cattle holdings are located in the 4 provinces Lower Austria, Upper Austria, Styria and Carinthia; 77.75% of the cattle are kept there.

Additional information

Not available

Table 1 Susceptible animal populations: number of animals, herds, holdings and slaughtered animals, 2016

Animals species	Unit	Number	comments
Cattle (bovine animals)	holding	61919	Veterinary Information System
Cattle (bovine animals)	animal	1954008	Veterinary Information System
Cattle (bovine animals)	slaughter animal (heads)	626533	incl. young cattle (9-12m) but without calves; Data established by Statistics Austria
Cattle (bovine animals) - calves (under 1 year)	holding	56723	Veterinary Information System (Calves with age under 1 year at 1.04.2016)
Cattle (bovine animals) - calves (under 1 year)	animal	616183	Veterinary Information System (Calves with age under 1 year at 1.04.2016)
Cattle (bovine animals) - calves (under 1 year)	slaughter animal (heads)	59992	calves only; Data established by Statistics Austria
Pigs	holding	32725	Veterinary Information System
Pigs	animal	2950354	Veterinary Information System
Pigs	slaughter animal (heads)	5227573	Data established by Statistics Austria
Pigs - breeding animals - unspecified - sows	holding	5786	Veterinary Information System
Pigs - breeding animals - unspecified - sows	animal	244267	Veterinary Information System
Pigs - breeding animals - unspecified - sows	slaughter animal (heads)	87350	Data established by Statistics Austria
Pigs - fattening pigs	holding	24798	Veterinary Information System
Pigs - fattening pigs	animal	1134999	Veterinary Information System
Pigs - fattening pigs	slaughter animal (heads)	5140223	Data established by Statistics Austria
Sheep	holding	18136	Veterinary Information System
Sheep	animal	485044	Veterinary Information System
Sheep	slaughter animal (heads)	269290	Data established by Statistics Austria
Sheep - animals over 1 year	holding	16937	Veterinary Information System
Sheep - animals over 1 year	animal	292658	Veterinary Information System (livestock at 1.04.2016 or average livestock)
Sheep - animals over 1 year	slaughter animal (heads)	63924	Data established by Statistics Austria
Sheep - animals under 1 year (lambs)	holding	14060	Veterinary Information System
Sheep - animals under 1 year (lambs)	animal	192386	Veterinary Information System (livestock at 1.04.2016 or average livestock)
Sheep - animals under 1 year (lambs)	slaughter animal (heads)	205366	Data established by Statistics Austria
Goats	holding	11009	Veterinary Information System
Goats	animal	106479	Veterinary Information System
Goats	slaughter animal (heads)	56832	Data established by Statistics Austria
Goats - animals over 1 year	holding	10697	Veterinary Information System
Goats - animals over 1 year	animal	73260	Veterinary Information System (livestock at 1.04.2016 or average livestock)
Goats - animals over 1 year	slaughter animal (heads)	13184	Data established by Statistics Austria
Goats - animals under 1 year	holding	4632	Veterinary Information System
Goats - animals under 1 year	animal	33219	Veterinary Information System (livestock at 1.04.2016 or average livestock)
Goats - animals under 1 year	slaughter animal (heads)	43648	Data established by Statistics Austria
Solipeds, domestic	holding	17947	Veterinary Information System
Solipeds, domestic	animal	89103	Veterinary Information System
Solipeds, domestic	slaughter animal (heads)	602	Data established by Statistics Austria

Animal Populations

Animals species	Unit	Number	comments
Deer - farmed	holding	1935	Veterinary Information System
Deer - farmed	animal	44117	Veterinary Information System
Deer - farmed	slaughter animal (heads)	unknown	Data established by Statistics Austria
Wild boars - farmed	holding	22	Veterinary Information System
Wild boars - farmed	animal	359	Veterinary Information System
Wild boars - farmed	slaughter animal (heads)	unknown	Data established by Statistics Austria
Gallus gallus (fowl)	slaughter animal (heads)	83439000	hens for roasting, baking and for soup; data established by Statistics Austria
Gallus gallus (fowl) - breeding flocks for broiler production line	holding	62	adults
Gallus gallus (fowl) - breeding flocks for broiler production line	animal	929686	adults
Gallus gallus (fowl) - breeding flocks for broiler production line	herd/flock	116	adults
Gallus gallus (fowl) - breeding flocks for egg production line	holding	16	adults
Gallus gallus (fowl) - breeding flocks for egg production line	animal	234491	adults
Gallus gallus (fowl) - breeding flocks for egg production line	herd/flock	30	adults
Gallus gallus (fowl) - broilers	holding	536	
Gallus gallus (fowl) - broilers	animal	66388197	
Gallus gallus (fowl) - broilers	herd/flock	4666	
Gallus gallus (fowl) - laying hens	holding	1118	
Gallus gallus (fowl) - laying hens	animal	9842717	
Gallus gallus (fowl) - laying hens	herd/flock	2876	
Gallus gallus (fowl) - parent breeding flocks for broiler production line	holding	62	adults
Gallus gallus (fowl) - parent breeding flocks for broiler production line	animal	929686	adults
Gallus gallus (fowl) - parent breeding flocks for broiler production line	herd/flock	116	adults
Gallus gallus (fowl) - parent breeding flocks for egg production line	holding	16	adults
Gallus gallus (fowl) - parent breeding flocks for egg production line	animal	234491	adults
Gallus gallus (fowl) - parent breeding flocks for egg production line	herd/flock	30	adults
Turkeys	holding	136	
Turkeys	animal	2007838	
Turkeys	herd/flock	406	
Turkeys - meat production flocks	holding	136	
Turkeys - meat production flocks	animal	2007838	
Turkeys - meat production flocks	herd/flock	406	

4. Information on Specific Zoonoses and Zoonotic Agents

The World Health Organization defines zoonoses as “those diseases and infections which are naturally transmitted between vertebrate animals and man.” Foodstuffs often serve as vehicles of zoonotic infections. Zoonotic agents include viruses, bacteria, fungi, parasites or other biological entities that are likely to cause zoonoses.

Collection of human cases

Starting with January 1st 2009 a new reporting system, the **epidemiological reporting system** (Epidemiologisches Meldesystem, EMS) has been put in operation at the BMGF. The physicians report all notifiable diseases (case based) to the local health authorities which are part of the local administration authorities (“Bezirksverwaltungsbehörde”). The physicians working at the local health authorities (public health officers) have to enter the data of the human cases of all notifiable diseases in the data base EMS including all relevant variables and laboratory results (case based). Also the laboratories enter the results of their laboratory work in EMS via a gateway to streamline the process.

EMS is the one and only database for notifiable diseases in the human sector in Austria. This system is also the standard gateway for reporting to ECDC (TESSy). A short report is also extracted and compiled using EMS which is published nationwide monthly and once a year by the Federal Ministry of Health online on the BMGF-homepage:

http://www.bmgf.gv.at/home/Gesundheit/Krankheiten/Uebertragbare_Krankheiten/Statistiken_und_Fallzahlen/Jahresstatistiken_meldepflichtiger_Infektionskrankheiten_seit_dem_Jahr_2000).

Additionally data of primary isolates from patients typed in the national reference centres are available. The responsible reference centres for zoonotic diseases published the numbers of microbiologically typed primary isolates from humans; due to the fact that more than one bacterial strain could be isolated from single patients these figures may differ from the case numbers notified to the Federal Ministry.

In this report it is indicated which data source has been used for the reporting of human cases for each respective zoonosis.

General Information about the Food Sampling Strategy

In 2016, foodstuffs were sampled all over Austria according to the national control plan given in the ordinance „Nationaler Kontrollplan für das Jahr 2016 gem. § 31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2016“ (BMG-75500/0168-II/B/13/2015) from the Federal Ministry of Health and Women’s Affairs. This “Nationaler Kontrollplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2016-2018) according to the Art. 41ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004 and consists of several separated parts:

The inspection part (“Inspektionsteil”) determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be visited and inspected. Every food business has to be inspected regularly. The inspection comprises sampling, hygienic investigations of the establishment and the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc.

The part for sampling is comprised of scheduled (“Planproben”) and suspect samples (“Verdachtsproben”). In 2016, the part for sampling intended approximately 20,000 scheduled samples and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). This yearly part for sampling determines the number of samples for each stage (retail, processing plants, primary production) and for each food category that has to be investigated randomly.

If specific suspicions (e.g. colour deviation, temperature, etc.) initiate the sampling by officials, these samples are categorised as suspect samples. Moreover any follow up sampling (e.g. due to RASFF, monitoring, positive samples, further information, etc.) is defined as suspect sample as well as food samples from private persons or sampling due to outbreak situations.

In addition there are monitoring plans, so called campaigns, for specific food items (about 55-60 individual campaigns per year). In the course of those campaigns food items of special interest are investigated for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents. In order to gain in-depth information the sampling takes place during a specified time frame. In 2016, 4 different food campaigns were conducted throughout Austria dealing with zoonotic agents. Each campaign is described in detail and results are depicted in the respective chapters per pathogen.

Further activities at food production facilities are made pursuant to Regulation (EC) no 178/2002 (e. g. traceability of food, feed, food-producing animals and all substances incorporated into foodstuffs must be established at all stages of production, processing and distribution). To fulfil these obligations, food business operators are required to apply appropriate systems and procedures, e.g. HACCP-concept. One part is given by Commission Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005 on microbiological criteria for foodstuffs that indicates the minimal quantity of sampling (number of sample units and size of the analytical unit) regarding to specific microbiological hazards at the stage of products placed on the market within their shelflife and at a specific stage of production (e.g. before and/or after chilling).

4.1. Salmonellosis

4.1.1. General evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

The incidence of human salmonellosis has significantly declined since the peak in 1998/1999. In 2016, the number of laboratory confirmed notified salmonellosis cases (table 2, n = 1,415 cases) decreased compared to 2015 by 6.5% and reached the lowest level since notification has been made mandatory. Human campylobacteriosis is the most commonly reported food-borne zoonoses in Austria although salmonellosis remains relevant to human health.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The *Salmonella*-contamination of raw poultry meat has declined from 30 % in 1999 to less than 5.5 % in 2009, since 2012 it has increased from 9.3 % to 10 % in 2013, 11.5 % in 2014, 14% in 2015, and to 15% in 2016 due to the fact that *S. Infantis*-prevalence is still high in poultry meat (12%). The consumption of *Salmonella*-contaminated eggs and egg products is presumably the main cause for human infections with *S. Enteritidis* even though *S. Enteritidis* was detected only in 9 out of 2,876 flocks of laying hens (0.3%) within the National Control Program.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

The incidence of human salmonellosis has declined within the last years. Different foodstuffs (e.g. poultry meat, eggs, or mixed foodstuffs) may pose a certain risk, therefore kitchen hygiene is of utmost importance. The relatively high prevalence of *S. Infantis* in Austrian broiler flocks (2.2%) and in broiler meat (12%) and its increase within the last years was not reflected in an increase of human cases; in the last years, *S. Infantis* caused between 40 and 68 cases per year in Austria.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

There were EU programs implemented to control the contamination of *Salmonella* in poultry, most programs involved meat and egg production. The effort of the intervention is directed toward improving the sanitation of breeding flocks and laying flocks, broiler flocks and turkey flocks according to EU legislation.

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Continue the efforts already started, especially to improve harmonization of monitoring and control programs along the food chain and update the target serovars in the different poultry populations, e.g. *S. Infantis* in broiler flocks or *S. Stanley* in turkey flocks.

Additional information

If zoonotic agents that are listed in the national Zoonoses Act, are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the diagnosing laboratories are obligated to send these strains to the respective national reference laboratory for typing and comparative analysis.

4.1.2. Salmonellosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

The number of salmonellosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to the EMS.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

Any person with at least one of the following four symptoms:

- Diarrhoea

- Fever
- Abdominal pain
- Vomiting

Laboratory criteria

- Isolation of *Salmonella* (other than *S. Typhi* and *S. Paratyphi*) from stool or blood

Case classification

Possible case

- NA

Probable case

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria and with an epidemiological link

Confirmed case

- Any person meeting the clinical and the laboratory criteria

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Bacteriology: Sample material is processed as described in „Richtlinien für die Diagnostik von Salmonellen (Anonymus: Standardisierung und Qualitätssicherung in der mikrobiologischen Diagnostik. Richtlinien. Bundesministerium für Soziale Sicherheit und Generationen. ISBN 3-84123-126-0, Wien, 2001, pg. 11-12)“.

At the National Reference Centre for *Salmonella* (NRC-*Salmonella*) all isolates are serotyped according to the White-Kauffmann-Le Minor Scheme. And further all *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are lysotyped according to the methods used by PHE, Colindale, UK. Additionally the antimicrobial resistance testing by disk diffusion method is performed with each isolate.

Notification system in place

Notification of salmonellosis according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In 1989 and 1990, human infections with *Salmonella* increased markedly in Austria. After a peak in 1992, the incidence of *Salmonella* illness decreased, but the number of infections has remained at a high level until 2002. Since that year the number of laboratory confirmed cases of human *Salmonella* cases has decreased by 83 % (2002: 8,405 primary isolates, 2016: 1,415 notified cases).

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2016, the number of cases of salmonellosis notified to EMS decreased and reached the lowest level since notification has been made mandatory (1,415 cases). In 2012, for the first time the proportion of *S. Enteritidis* was lower than that of all other serovars. The proportion of *S. Enteritidis* isolates out of all *Salmonella* cases increased in 2016 to 47 % (2015: 43%). The most frequently identified *Enteritidis* phage types in 2016 were: PT 8 (260 cases), PT 4 (81 cases), and PT 21 (77 cases). The proportion of *S. Typhimurium* isolates reported decreased slightly to 12.3 % (2015: 12.7%, 2014: 12.3%, 2013: 7.2 %; 2012: 13.9 %). Most frequent phage types were RDNC (29 cases) and DT 120 (28 cases). Sixty-four isolates were typed as *S. Infantis* followed by 55 isolates of *S. Typhimurium*, monophasic strain (1,4,[5],12:1:-) (2015: 42 cases, 2014: 63 cases, 2013: 68 cases).

Relevance as zoonotic disease

In 2016, the number of notified human laboratory confirmed cases of campylobacteriosis again exceeded the number of salmonellosis cases.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via reports published from the Federal Ministry for Health and Women's Affairs (BMGF) on monthly and yearly basis. The yearly report is published on the Website of the BMGF.

Table 2 Salmonellosis cases from humans - serotype distribution (EMS/NRC-S), 2016

Serotype	Cases				
	Incidence/100,000	Autochthonous	Imported	Unknown	status
	N	population	cases	cases	
	1.415	16,26	1.029	332	54
<i>S. Enteritidis</i>	671	7.71	465	168	38
<i>S. Typhimurium</i>	174	2.00	134	34	6
<i>S. Infantis</i>	64	0.74	59	5	
<i>S. Typhimurium</i> , monophasic (1.4.[5].12:l:-)	55	0.63	44	11	
serovar unknown	47	0.54	33	13	1
<i>S. Senftenberg</i>	37	0.43	36	1	
<i>S. Coeln</i>	22	0.25	17	4	1
<i>S. Newport</i>	19	0.22	14	5	
<i>S. Stanley</i>	19	0.22	11	8	
<i>S. Virchow</i>	18	0.21	14	4	
<i>S. group (B) O:4</i>	17	0.20	12	5	
<i>S. Thompson</i>	17	0.20	15	2	
<i>S. Agona</i>	15	0.17	10	4	1
<i>S. Braenderup</i>	15	0.17	10	5	
<i>S. Saintpaul</i>	15	0.17	10	4	1
<i>S. Bovismorbificans</i>	12	0.14	8	4	
<i>S. Kentucky</i>	11	0.13	7	4	
<i>S. Poona</i>	9	0.10	8	1	
<i>S. Paratyphi B</i> var. L(+) tartrate+ (variant Java)	8	0.09	6	2	
<i>S. Chester</i>	7	0.08	1	6	
<i>S. Corvallis</i>	7	0.08	4	3	
<i>S. Weltevreden</i>	6	0.07	4	2	
<i>S. Derby</i>	5	0.06	5		
<i>S. subspecies IIIb (diarizonae)</i>	5	0.06	5		
<i>S. Abony</i>	4	0.05	2	2	
<i>S. Brandenburg</i>	4	0.05	4		
<i>S. group (C1) O:7</i>	4	0.05	3	1	
<i>S. Hadar</i>	4	0.05	3		1
<i>S. Haifa</i>	4	0.05	1	3	
<i>S. Mbandaka</i>	4	0.05	3	1	
<i>S. Ohio</i>	4	0.05	3	1	
<i>S. subspecies I (enterica)</i>	4	0.05	4		
<i>S. Adjame</i>	3	0.03	3		
<i>S. Agama</i>	3	0.03	3		
<i>S. Eastbourne</i>	3	0.03	1	2	
<i>S. Javiana</i>	3	0.03	1	2	
<i>S. Kenya</i>	3	0.03	1	2	
<i>S. Liverpool</i>	3	0.03	1	2	
<i>S. Muenchen</i>	3	0.03	1	2	
<i>S. Oranienburg</i>	3	0.03	2	1	
<i>S. Ordonez</i>	3	0.03	3		
<i>S. Panama</i>	3	0.03	3		
<i>S. Stanleyville</i>	3	0.03	3		
<i>S. subspecies IV (houtenae)</i>	3	0.03	3		
<i>S. Bredeney</i>	2	0.02		2	
<i>S. Give</i>	2	0.02	1		1
<i>S. Goldcoast</i>	2	0.02	2		
<i>S. Kaapstad</i>	2	0.02	1	1	
<i>S. Kottbus</i>	2	0.02	2		
<i>S. Litchfield</i>	2	0.02	2		

Serotype	Cases				
	N	Incidence/100,000 population	Autochthonous cases	Imported cases	Unknown status
	1.415	16,26	1.029	332	54
<i>S. Livingstone</i>	2	0.02	2		
<i>S. London</i>	2	0.02	2		
<i>S. Mikawasima</i>	2	0.02	2		
<i>S. Montevideo</i>	2	0.02	1	1	
<i>S. Muenster</i>	2	0.02	1	1	
<i>S. Napoli</i>	2	0.02	2		
<i>S. Potsdam</i>	2	0.02	2		
<i>S. Rissen</i>	2	0.02		2	
<i>S. subspecies II (salamae)</i>	2	0.02	2		
<i>S. Telelkebir</i>	2	0.02	2		
<i>S. Tennessee</i>	2	0.02	2		
<i>S. Umbilo</i>	2	0.02		2	
<i>S. Urbana</i>	2	0.02		1	1
<i>S. Adelaide</i>	1	0.01	1		
<i>S. Alachua</i>	1	0.01	1		
<i>S. Albany</i>	1	0.01		1	
<i>S. Altona</i>	1	0.01	1		
<i>S. Arechavaleta</i>	1	0.01	1		
<i>S. Bareilly</i>	1	0.01			1
<i>S. Bonn</i>	1	0.01	1		
<i>S. Brunei</i>	1	0.01	1		
<i>S. Caracas</i>	1	0.01	1		
<i>S. Cerro</i>	1	0.01	1		
<i>S. Chicago</i>	1	0.01		1	
<i>S. Choleraesuis</i>	1	0.01			1
<i>S. Essen</i>	1	0.01		1	
<i>S. Gaminara</i>	1	0.01	1		
<i>S. group (D1) O:9</i>	1	0.01	1		
<i>S. Halle</i>	1	0.01	1		
<i>S. Havana</i>	1	0.01			1
<i>S. Hull</i>	1	0.01		1	
<i>S. Hvittingfoss</i>	1	0.01	1		
<i>S. Inganda</i>	1	0.01		1	
<i>S. Irumu</i>	1	0.01		1	
<i>S. Kasenyi</i>	1	0.01	1		
<i>S. Kimuenza</i>	1	0.01	1		
<i>S. Leeuwarden</i>	1	0.01		1	
<i>S. Monschau</i>	1	0.01	1		
<i>S. Orientalis</i>	1	0.01	1		
<i>S. Oxford</i>	1	0.01	1		
<i>S. Reading</i>	1	0.01	1		
<i>S. Ridge</i>	1	0.01	1		
<i>S. Schwarzengrund</i>	1	0.01	1		
<i>S. Stourbridge</i>	1	0.01	1		
<i>S. Strathcona</i>	1	0.01		1	
<i>S. Szentcs</i>	1	0.01	1		
<i>S. Uganda</i>	1	0.01	1		

Data source: EMS, NRC-S 27.01.2017

Table 3 Salmonellosis cases in humans - age distribution (EMS/NRC-S), 2016

age groups	Salmonellosis			S. Enteritidis		S. Typhimurium		S. Infantis		S. Typhimurium, monophasic		S. Senftenberg		other and unknown serotypes	
	all	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F
< 1 year	33	19	14	6	2	3	1	2	1	0	2	0	1	8	7
1 to 4 years	184	97	87	64	36	10	22	0	1	5	4	0	1	18	23
5 to 14 years	244	147	97	84	56	25	18	5	2	6	0	2	1	25	20
15 to 24 years	185	95	90	44	47	9	7	4	4	6	4	2	0	30	28
25 to 44 years	299	145	154	54	62	17	17	6	8	9	3	5	3	54	61
45 to 64 years	273	146	127	68	60	10	16	7	10	5	2	5	6	51	33
65 years and older	197	86	111	38	50	5	14	7	7	3	6	5	6	28	28
All age groups	1,415	735	680	358	313	79	95	31	33	34	21	19	18	214	200

Data source: EMS, NRC-S 27.01.2017

Table 4 Salmonellosis cases in humans – seasonal distribution (EMS/NRC-S), 2016

Month	Salmonellosis	S. Enteritidis	S. Typhimurium	S. Infantis	S. Typhimurium, monophasic	S. Senftenberg	other and unknown serotypes
January	75	31	11	2	3	1	27
February	59	13	10	3	0	2	31
March	68	19	9	7	1	8	24
April	79	26	6	4	4	12	27
May	114	51	16	5	2	5	35
June	134	66	11	10	2	5	40
July	122	61	15	5	9	1	31
August	228	136	23	10	5	0	54
September	225	124	27	4	19	1	50
October	149	79	20	7	4	1	38
November	102	46	23	2	2	0	29
December	60	19	3	5	4	1	28
Total	1,415	671	174	64	55	37	414

Data source: EMS, NRC-S 27.01.2017

4.1.3. *Salmonella* spp. in foodstuffs

Monitoring system - Sampling strategy

In 2016, foodstuffs were sampled all over Austria according to the national control plan given in the ordinance „Nationaler Kontrollplan für das Jahr 2016 gem. § 31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2016“ (BMG-75500/0168-II/B/13/2015) from the Federal Ministry of Health and Women’s Affairs. This “Nationaler Kontrollplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2016-2018) according to the Art. 41ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004 and consists of several separated parts:

The inspection part (“Inspektionsteil”) determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be visited and inspected. Every food business has to be inspected regularly. The inspection comprises sampling, hygienic investigations of the establishment and the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc.

The part for sampling is comprised of scheduled (“Planproben”) and suspect samples (“Verdachtsproben”). In 2016, the part for sampling intended approximately 20,000 scheduled samples and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). This yearly part for sampling determines the number of samples for each stage (retail, processing plants, primary production) and for each food category that has to be investigated randomly.

If specific suspicions (e.g. colour deviation, temperature, etc.) initiate the sampling by officials, these samples are categorised as suspect samples. Moreover any follow up sampling (e.g. due to RASFF, monitoring, positive samples, further information, etc.) is defined as suspect sample as well as food samples from private persons or sampling due to outbreak situations.

In addition there are monitoring plans, so called campaigns, for specific food items (about 55-60 individual campaigns per year). In the course of those campaigns food items of special interest are investigated for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents. In order to gain in-depth information the sampling takes place during a specified time frame. In 2016, 4 different food campaigns were conducted throughout Austria dealing with zoonotic agents. Each campaign is described in detail and results are depicted in the respective chapters per pathogen.

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling

Sampling distributed evenly throughout the year

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken

Fresh meat, meat preparations, minced meat, eggs, vegetables, etc.

Monitoring system - Definition of positive finding

Detection of *Salmonella* spp. in 25 g

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Bacteriological method ISO 6579:2002 + Cor.1:2004 + Amd.1:2007. The amount of tested food in general is 25 g. Some exceptions exist, according to the Commission Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005, as indicated in tables 5-8. All *Salmonella* isolates are sent to the National Reference Centre for *Salmonella* in Graz and serotyped according to the White-Kauffmann-Le Minor-Scheme. All *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are lyso-typed according to the methods used by PHE, Colindale, UK. Additionally all isolates are tested for their antibiotic susceptibility using the disk diffusion method applying EUCAST clinical breakpoints. In case of an outbreak situation the stored isolates may be further investigated with pulsed-field gel electrophoresis (PFGE) or multiple-locus variable-number of tandem-repeats analysis (MLVA).

Control program/mechanisms - Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

No actions (e.g. new regulations, new control programs, etc.) taken.

Control program/mechanisms - Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

All *Salmonella* serotypes should be covered by monitoring programs and/or microbiological criteria.

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Whenever *Salmonella* is detected the isolates are sent to the National Reference Centre for *Salmonella* in Graz, where the isolates are further analysed and stored. Investigation into the source of the contamination is initiated if indicated.

Results of the investigation

see tables

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Salmonella spp. was detected in fresh broiler meat samples in 20.3% (27 out of 133) and in 3.7% of fresh turkey meat samples (2 out of 54). In five of the remaining fresh meat samples (n = 23) from duck meat, geese meat and unspecified poultry meat *Salmonella* has been detected. Meat preparations, raw but intended to be eaten cooked contained *Salmonella* in 19% (CI: 11-31%) of broiler meat, whereas 25 of 159 poultry meat preparations (unspecified) were tested positive (15.7%; CI: 11-22%).

None of the poultry meat products, no matter if cooked or raw, contained any *Salmonella* (31 samples tested). Segregating the data for processing plants and slaughter houses (fresh broiler meat), 7 samples were tested positive for *Salmonella* (44 samples tested, 15.9%, CI: 8-29%). At processing plants the five *Salmonella* serovars found where four times *S. Infantis* and once *S. Typhimurium*. At the stage of slaughter, no *Salmonella* has been detected.

70 *Salmonella* serovars have been detected in poultry meat. The most prevalent serovar detected in poultry and products thereof is *S. Infantis* (81.4% of all serovars) followed by *S. Newport* (5.7%).

In total 999 samples of meat, minced meat, meat products and meat preparations (poultry not included) were tested, with 7 samples positive for *Salmonella*.

No *Salmonella* were found in 862 samples of milk, dairy products and cheeses, as in the years 2007-2015. 2,728 samples of different matrices were tested for *Salmonella*, resulting in five positive ones.

All egg products (liquid, dried), where negative for *Salmonella* (104 tested samples). Out of the 92 samples from packing centers, processing plants, retail, catering or wholesale no sample was tested positive for *Salmonella* in table eggs in 2016.

Relevance of the findings in foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of human infection)

The relevance of these findings is delineated in food-borne outbreaks. Since January 2012, the Outbreak Detection System (ODS) for the early detection of salmonellosis has been installed in Austria. Within this tool real-time data on *Salmonella* isolates are utilized to determine a threshold value. If the number of *Salmonella* cases of the current week exceeds this threshold, a signal indicates a possible outbreak. This signal enables an early start of outbreak investigations.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Campaign A-027-16: *Salmonella* spp. in food – fruits and vegetables - pre-cut – single (food/feed) – at retail – surveillance – official sampling – objective sampling

Monitoring system - Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health and Women's Affairs. Samples are taken at retail by competent authorities.

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: June to August

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken

Fresh fruits and vegetables, precut (like all kinds of melons, strawberries, kiwi, pineapple, salads, etc.), sold fresh

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Sample weight: 25 g

Monitoring system - Definition of positive finding

Detection of *Salmonella* spp. in 25 g

Results of the investigation

55 samples were tested for *Salmonella* spp.: none positive

Additional information

Samples were also tested for *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Campylobacter* and VTEC.

Campaign A-045-16: *Salmonella* spp. in food – foodstuffs intended for special nutritional uses – single (food/feed) – at retail – surveillance – official sampling – objective sampling

Monitoring system - Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health and Women's Affairs. Samples are taken at retail by competent authorities.

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: October to November

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken

Foodstuffs, intended for special nutritional uses on the basis of plants (non-animal origin). Mainly in form of powder and capsules.

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Sample weight: 25 g

Monitoring system - Definition of positive finding

Detection of *Salmonella* spp. in 25 g

Results of the investigation

49 samples were tested for *Salmonella* spp.

In one sample (powder of *Moringa olifeira* leaves) *Salmonella* Mgulani was detected.

Campaign A-004-16: *Salmonella* spp. in food – Foodstuffs intended for special nutritional uses - processed cereal-based food for infants and young children – single (food/feed) – at wholesale outlets – surveillance – official sampling – objective sampling

Monitoring system - Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health and Women's Affairs. Samples are taken at wholesale outlets by competent authorities.

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: January to March

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken

Foodstuffs intended for special nutritional uses - processed cereal-based food for infants and young children (*Salmonella*) and foodstuffs intended for special nutritional uses - other food for infants and children (*Listeria*)

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Sample weight: 25 g

Monitoring system - Definition of positive finding

Detection of *Salmonella* spp. in 25 g

Results of the investigation

15 samples were tested for *Salmonella* spp.: none positive

Additional information

19 samples from foodstuffs intended for special nutritional uses - other food for infants and children (baby milk) were tested for *L. monocytogenes*: none positive

Campaign A-041-16: *Salmonella* spp. in food – egg products (liquid and dried) – at retail and processing plants – surveillance – official sampling – objective sampling

Monitoring system - Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health and Women's Affairs. Samples are taken at retail outlets and processing plants by competent authorities.

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: October to November

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken

Liquid egg products (yolk, white, and whole) and dried egg products (yolk, white, and whole)

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Sample weight: 25 g

Monitoring system - Definition of positive finding

Detection of *Salmonella* spp. in 25 g

Results of the investigation

39 samples were tested for *Salmonella* spp.: none positive

Additional information

None

Table 5 *Salmonella* spp. in poultry meat and meat products, 2016

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> sp.	<i>S.</i> Agona	<i>S.</i> Coeln	<i>S.</i> Enteritidis PT1	<i>S.</i> Enteritidis RDNC	<i>S.</i> group C1	<i>S.</i> Infantis	<i>S.</i> Montevideo	<i>S.</i> Newport	<i>S.</i> Senftenberg	<i>S.</i> Thompson	<i>S.</i> Typhimurium DT1	<i>S.</i> Typhimurium DT12	<i>S.</i> Typhimurium DT46a	<i>S.</i> Typhimurium DT120	
Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>), fresh	Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	22	5	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
		XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	67	16	0	1	0	0	0	15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	13	2	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Slaughterhouse	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	17	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wholesale		EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>), fresh, HACCP and own checks	Slaughterhouse	AT	slaughter batch	25	Gram	115	34*	2	7	0	0	1	17	7	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	
Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>), meat preparation, intended to be eaten cooked	Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	40	10	0	0	0	0	0	9	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
Meat from duck, fresh	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	
Meat from geese, fresh	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from poultry, unspecified, fresh	Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	10	2	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat from poultry, unspecified, meat preparation	Retail		EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from poultry, unspecified, meat preparation, intended to	Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	2	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	

Salmonellosis

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> sp.	<i>S. Agona</i>	<i>S. Coeln</i>	<i>S. Enteritidis</i> PT1	<i>S. Enteritidis</i> RDNC	<i>S. group</i> C1	<i>S. Infantis</i>	<i>S. Montevideo</i>	<i>S. Newport</i>	<i>S. Senftenberg</i>	<i>S. Thompson</i>	<i>S. Typhimurium</i> DT1	<i>S. Typhimurium</i> DT12	<i>S. Typhimurium</i> DT46a	<i>S. Typhimurium</i> DT120	
be eaten cooked	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	31	7	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	
		XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	103	15	1	0	0	0	0	12	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Slaughterhouse	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat from poultry, unspecified, meat products	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from poultry, unspecified, meat products, cooked, ready-to-eat	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Slaughterhouse	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from poultry, unspecified, meat products, unspecified, ready-to-eat	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from turkey, fresh	Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	31	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	13	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Slaughterhouse	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Meat from turkey, fresh, HACCP and own check	Slaughterhouse	AT	slaughter batch	25	Gram	103	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from turkey, meat preparation, intended to be eaten cooked	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from turkey, meat products, cooked, ready-to-eat	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	

*2 different isolates in 2 samples of broiler slaughter batches

Table 6 *Salmonella* spp. in red meat and products thereof, 2016

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> sp.	<i>S. enterica</i> subsp. enterica, rough	<i>S. Enteritidis</i> PT13a	<i>S. group B</i>	<i>S. Infantis</i>	<i>S. Rissen</i>	<i>S. Saintpaul</i>	<i>S. Typhimurium</i> DT120	<i>Salmonella</i> spp., unspec	
Meat from bovine animals - fresh	Game handling establishment	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
				25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
				25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
					25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat from bovine animals - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
				XX	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
				25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		EU	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
				25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from bovine animals - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
				25	Gram	25	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
				25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Slaughterhouse	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	298	4	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	
				25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
			25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Meat from bovine animals and pig - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
				Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat from bovine animals and pig - meat products	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
				Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat from bovine animals and pig - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
				25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from other animal species or not specified	Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
				Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	14	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
				25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		EU	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
				25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from other animal species or not specified - fresh	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0		
Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		

Salmonellosis

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> sp.	<i>S. enterica</i> subsp. <i>enterica</i> , rough	<i>S. Enteritidis</i> PT13a	<i>S. group B</i>	<i>S. Infantis</i>	<i>S. Rissen</i>	<i>S. Saintpaul</i>	<i>S. Typhimurium</i> DT120	<i>Salmonella</i> spp., unspec
preparation - intended to be eaten cooked		EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
				25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat preparation - intended to be eaten raw	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	21	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products - fermented sausages	Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Game handling establishment	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat from other animal species or not specified - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		EU	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Pigs – carcase swabs - HACCP and own check	slaughterhouse	AT	slaughter animal batch	100	Square centimetre	4,581	36	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	36
Meat from pig - fresh	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
				25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
				25	Gram	15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat from pig - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
				25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	13	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
				25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	97	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
				25	Gram	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		EU	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
				XX	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat from pig - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Salmonellosis

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> sp.	<i>S. enterica</i> subsp. <i>enterica</i> , rough	<i>S. Enteritidis</i> PT13a	<i>S. group B</i>	<i>S. Infantis</i>	<i>S. Rissen</i>	<i>S. Saintpaul</i>	<i>S. Typhimurium</i> DT120	<i>Salmonella</i> spp., unspec
	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
				25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat from pig - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat from pig - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat from pig - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked - chilled	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat from pig - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat from sheep - fresh	Border inspection activities	XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat from sheep - meat preparation	Retail	XE	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat from wild boar - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat from wild game - birds - fresh	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat, mixed meat - minced meat	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat, mixed meat - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		XX	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	72	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Slaughterhouse	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products	Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	24	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			25	Gram	38	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	

Salmonellosis

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> sp.	<i>S. enterica</i> subsp. <i>enterica</i> , rough	<i>S. Enteritidis</i> PT13a	<i>S. group B</i>	<i>S. Infantis</i>	<i>S. Rissen</i>	<i>S. Saintpaul</i>	<i>S. Typhimurium</i> DT120	<i>Salmonella</i> spp., unspec
	Processing plant	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
				25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	19	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	41	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	22	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Slaughterhouse	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked	Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		EU	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Retail				10	Gram	32	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
					25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		EU	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 7 *Salmonella* spp. in milk and dairy products, 2016

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> sp.
Cheeses made from cows' milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk	Border inspection activities	XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	14	0
	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	19	0
	Retail	XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	46	0
	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0
		EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - unspecified	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - unspecified - made from pasteurised milk	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0
		XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	18	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	9	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	12	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0
	Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk	Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	14	0
Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0

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Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> sp.
Dairy products (excluding cheeses)	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - butter	Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0
	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	25	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy products, not specified	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0
	Border inspection activities	XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - fermented dairy products	Catering	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - ice-cream	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0
	Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	142	0
		EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0
	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	281	0
	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	144	0
EU		single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - ice-cream - made from pasteurised milk	Catering	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0
		AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0
	Conservation Facilities	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0
	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0
	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
Milk, cows' - raw milk	Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0
	Farm	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0
	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0
Milk, cows' - raw milk - intended for direct human consumption	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	19	0
Milk, cows' - raw milk for manufacture - intended for manufacture of raw or low heat-treated products	Retail	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	20	0
Milk, goats' - raw milk	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0
Milk, goats' - raw milk - intended for direct human consumption	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
Milk, sheep's - raw milk	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0
	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0

Table 8 *Salmonella* spp. in other food, 2016

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> sp.	<i>S.</i> Enteritidis PT5	<i>S.</i> Enteritidis PT62	<i>S.</i> Infantis	<i>S.</i> Isangi	<i>S.</i> Mgulani	
Bakery products		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	25	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bakery products - cakes		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	15	0	0	0	0	0	0
			Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	30	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bakery products - pastry		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	17	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	13	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	68	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Beverages, alcoholic		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Beverages, non-alcoholic		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cereals and meals		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	36	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Chocolate		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0		
Cocoa and cocoa preparations, coffee and tea		Catering	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			Packing centre	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	11	0	0	0	0	0	
		Processing plant	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0		
			AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	36	0	0	0	0	0		

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Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> sp.	<i>S.</i> Enteritidis PT5	<i>S.</i> Enteritidis PT62	<i>S.</i> Infantis	<i>S.</i> Isangi	<i>S.</i> Mgulani
Food			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	36	0	0	0	0	0	0
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0	0	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	11	0	0	0	0	0	0
			AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Coconut - coconut products		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Crustaceans		Border inspection activities	XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	14	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Wholesale	XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Crustaceans - unspecified - cooked		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Egg products	Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0
			Packing centre	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0
Egg products		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	23	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	
Egg products - dried		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	
		A-041-16	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0		
Egg products - liquid		Catering	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	
		Packing centre	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	13	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	10	0	0	0	0	0	

Salmonellosis

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> sp.	<i>S.</i> Enteritidis PT5	<i>S.</i> Enteritidis PT62	<i>S.</i> Infantis	<i>S.</i> Isangi	<i>S.</i> Mgulani	
Food	A-041-16	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	17	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Eggs - table eggs		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	300	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	300	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Farm	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
					300	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Packing centre	AT	single (food/feed)	240	Gram	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
					300	Gram	39	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
					180	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
					240	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
					300	Gram	16	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
					EU	single (food/feed)	300	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0
		Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
300	Gram				1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Fish - gravad /slightly salted		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Fish - raw		Catering	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Fish - smoked		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Fish - smoked - cold-smoked		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Fishery products, unspecified		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	

Salmonellosis

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> sp.	<i>S. Enteritidis</i> PT5	<i>S. Enteritidis</i> PT62	<i>S. Infantis</i>	<i>S. Isangi</i>	<i>S. Mgulani</i>	
Food	Retail		AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Fishery products, unspecified - ready-to-eat	Processing plant		EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Fishery products, unspecified - ready-to-eat - chilled	Processing plant		AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Retail		AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Fishery products, unspecified - seafood pâté	Processing plant		AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Foodstuffs intended for special nutritional uses	Processing plant		AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0
				EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Wholesale		XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	A-045-16	Retail		XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
				AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	14	1	0	0	0	0	1
				EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	22	0	0	0	0	0	0
				XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Foodstuffs intended for special nutritional uses - processed cereal-based food for infants and young children	A-004-16	Wholesale	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0
AT				single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Foodstuffs intended for special nutritional uses - ready-to-eat	Retail		EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Fruits	Farm		AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Retail		EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Wholesale		AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	
XE			single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Fruits - non-pre-cut - frozen	Retail		XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Fruits - pre-cut	A-027-16	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	19	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	

Salmonellosis

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> sp.	<i>S.</i> Enteritidis PT5	<i>S.</i> Enteritidis PT62	<i>S.</i> Infantis	<i>S.</i> Isangi	<i>S.</i> Mgulani	
Food		Catering	XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Fruits - products		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Wholesale	XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	23	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Fruits - products - dried		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Fruits and vegetables - pre-cut	A-027-16	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Infant formula		Packing centre	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0				
Infant formula - dried		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Juice - fruit juice		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Juice - fruit juice - unpasteurised		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Juice - mixed juice		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	

Salmonellosis

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> sp.	<i>S. Enteritidis</i> PT5	<i>S. Enteritidis</i> PT62	<i>S. Infantis</i>	<i>S. Isangi</i>	<i>S. Mgulani</i>
Molluscan shellfish - raw - chilled		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mushrooms		Catering	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Nuts and nut products		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	37	0	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	44	0	0	0	0	0	0
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	37	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Wholesale	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	12	0	0	0	0	0	0
			AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0
	EU		single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Nuts and nut products - roasted		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Other food		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Other food of non-animal origin		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	11	0	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Other processed food products and prepared dishes		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	185	0	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	51	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
					25	Gram	186	0	0	0	0	0	0

Salmonellosis

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> sp.	<i>S.</i> Enteritidis PT5	<i>S.</i> Enteritidis PT62	<i>S.</i> Infantis	<i>S.</i> Isangi	<i>S.</i> Mgulani	
Food			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	640	3	1	1	1	0	0	
			AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - noodles		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - pasta		Catering	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Packing centre	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	57	1	0	0	0	1	0	
		Processing plant	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	33	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	22	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0			
	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0			
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - sandwiches		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0		
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0		
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - sushi		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0		
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0		
			AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0	0	0	0	0		
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0		
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0		
Ready-to-eat salads		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0		
			AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	17	0	0	0	0	0		
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	37	0	0	0	0	0		
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0		
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0		
		Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0		
Sauce and dressings		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0		
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0		

Salmonellosis

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> sp.	<i>S. Enteritidis</i> PT5	<i>S. Enteritidis</i> PT62	<i>S. Infantis</i>	<i>S. Isangi</i>	<i>S. Mgulani</i>
Food	Retail		AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sauce and dressings - mayonnaise	Processing plant		AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	9	0	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Retail		EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Seeds, dried	Processing plant		AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0	0	0	0	0
EU				single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
XE				single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0
Retail			AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	22	0	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0	0	0	0	0	0
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wholesale			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0
			AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Seeds, sprouted - ready-to-eat	Farm		XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
			AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Soups - dehydrated	Retail		EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Spices and herbs	Catering		AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Packing centre		AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	21	0	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Processing plant		AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	21	0	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	24	0	0	0	0	0	0
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	14	0	0	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	11	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Retail		AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	10	0	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wholesale		AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Spices and herbs - dried	Retail		AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0

Salmonellosis

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> sp.	<i>S. Enteritidis</i> PT5	<i>S. Enteritidis</i> PT62	<i>S. Infantis</i>	<i>S. Isangi</i>	<i>S. Mgulani</i>
Food			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sweets		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Vegetables		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	12	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	9	0	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0
Vegetables - pre-cut		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	23	0	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Vegetables - products		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0
EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0			
Vegetables - products - dried		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0

4.1.4. *Salmonella* spp. in animals

A. *Salmonella* in *Gallus gallus* - breeding flocks for meat production and broiler flocks

Monitoring system - Sampling strategy - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

There are only parent flocks in Austria, no elite and no grandparent flocks. The permanent monitoring plan performed by a national program takes place at hatcheries and on farm level; each flock is tested regularly as well by the farmer as by the Veterinary Authorities. If *S. Enteritidis*, *S. Typhimurium*, *S. Infantis*, *S. Hadar* and *S. Virchow* or *S. Pullorum Gallinarum* is isolated from breeding flocks at the hatchery the flock is banned and sampled for confirmation on the farm: 300 faeces samples and inner organs of 5 chickens or intestinal content of 5 chickens are pooled. If a parent flock tests positive for other *Salmonella* serotypes, official veterinarians are required to investigate the source of infection to optimise biosecurity.

Monitoring system - Sampling strategy - Broiler flocks

Within 3 weeks prior to slaughter boot swabs have to be taken. Other programs are not intended; only voluntary sampling by the farmer or sampling according to private cooperatives is performed.

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Day-old chicks

Every flock is tested at day one

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Rearing period

1. Routine testing: Every flock is tested at the age of 4 and 12 weeks and two weeks before moving to laying phase or laying unit. 2. Confirmation: If routine testing reveals positive *Salmonella* test results a follow-up test must be performed from the identical flock.

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Production period

Monitoring is performed according the national program and takes place at the hatchery and on the farm: at the hatchery: each flock is tested every two weeks by the industry, and every 16 weeks by the Veterinary Authorities; on the farm: each flock is tested every two weeks by the farmer and 3 times by the Veterinary Authorities (at beginning of production, in the middle of the production period and within the last 8 weeks before slaughter).

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling - Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks

No legal requirements

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling - Broiler flocks: Rearing period

No legal requirements

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling - Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Within 3 weeks before the birds are moved to the slaughterhouse 2 pairs of boot swabs have to be taken at the farm. 10 % of all flocks produced per year have to be tested by the competent authority. Commission Regulation (EC) No 200/2012 is in force since 01.01.2009.

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling - Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flock based approach)

According to Commission regulation 2073/2005

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Day-old chicks

Visibly soiled hatcher basket liners, dead chicks if available

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Rearing period

Routine testing: drag swabs, pooled faeces. For confirmation: 300 faeces samples and inner organs of 5 chickens or intestinal content of 5 chickens were pooled.

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Production period

Routine testing: Boot swabs, pooled faeces; in the hatchery: dust, meconium, broken eggshells and hatched eggs. For confirmation: 300 faeces samples and inner organs of 5 chickens or intestinal content of 5 chickens were pooled.

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken - Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks

no legal requirements, e.g. visibly soiled hatcher basket liners

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken - Broiler flocks: Rearing period

No sampling

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken - Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

two pairs of boot swabs per flock

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken - Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flock based approach)

According to Commission regulation 2073/2005

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Day-old chicks

Visibly soiled hatcher basket liners, dead chicks if available

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Rearing period

Routine testing: 5 pairs of boot swabs or 200 to 300 pooled droppings of 1 gram per flock, collection of dust. For confirmation: 300 feces samples and inner organs of 5 chickens or intestinal content of 5 chickens were pooled.

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) - Breeding flocks: Production period

Routine testing: 5 pairs of boot swabs, pooled feces, collection of dust. For confirmation: 300 feces samples and inner organs of 5 chickens or intestinal content of 5 chickens were pooled.

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) - Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks

No legal requirements

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) - Broiler flocks: Rearing period

No legal requirements

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) - Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Sampling was in accordance with the Annex of Commission Regulation (EU) No 200/2012.

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) - Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flock based approach)

According to Commission regulation 2073/2005

Monitoring system - Case definition - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Day-old chicks

Routine testing: *Salmonella* spp. isolated from samples taken

Monitoring system - Case definition - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Rearing period

Salmonella spp. isolated from samples taken.

Monitoring system - Case definition - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Production period

Salmonella spp. isolated from samples taken.

Monitoring system - Case definition - Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks

A flock from which *Salmonella* spp. was isolated

Monitoring system - Case definition - Broiler flocks: Rearing period

A flock from which *Salmonella* spp. was isolated

Monitoring system - Case definition - Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

A flock from which *Salmonella* spp. was isolated

Monitoring system - Case definition - Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flock based approach)

A flock from which *Salmonella* spp. was isolated

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Day-old chicks

According to ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007 (Annex D of ISO 6579). All isolates obtained in the primary laboratory are sent to the NRC *Salmonella* and serotyped according to the White-Kauffmann-Le-Minor-Scheme. All *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are lyso-typed according to the methods used by PHE, Colindale, UK.

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Rearing period

See day-old chicks

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Production period

See day-old chicks

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used - Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks

See below

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used - Broiler flocks: Rearing period

See below

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used - Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

According to ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007 (Annex D of ISO 6579). All isolates obtained in the primary laboratory are sent to the NRC *Salmonella* and serotyped according to the White-Kauffmann-Le-Minor-Scheme. All *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are lyso-typed according to the methods used by PHE, Colindale, UK.

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used - Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flock based approach)

See above

Vaccination policy - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

The national program for parent flocks made vaccination against *Salmonella* Enteritidis mandatory for all flocks.

Vaccination policy - Broiler flocks

Neither legal requirements nor recommendations

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place - Broiler flocks

In the last years, a multi-resistant clone of *S. Infantis* was isolated from broiler flocks, in 2016 this serotype was identified in 65 % of all *Salmonella* positive broiler flocks. To control *S. Infantis* but also *Campylobacter* in broiler flock, the application of a competitive exclusion product for poultry (broilact®) was started in 2015. Each positive flock was treated once. The treatment was co-financed by the Poultry Health Service.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Level of biosecurity was increased.

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

The Austrian control program is conducted according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation (BGBl. II 2007/100, Geflügelhygieneverordnung 2007 as amended). This Regulation is in line with Commission Regulation (EU) No 200/2010.

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place - Broiler flocks

The Austrian control program is conducted according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation (BGBl. II 2007/100, Geflügelhygieneverordnung 2007 as amended). This Regulation is in line with Commission Regulation (EU) No 200/2012.

Control program/mechanisms - Recent actions taken to control the zoonosis

See chapter "other preventive measures than vaccination"

Control program/mechanisms - Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Review the target serovars in the different poultry populations

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Day-old chicks

Measures according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation: Banning of the incriminated sector of the holding; culling of the infected flock; disposal of the hatched eggs; abolishing of the restriction after cleaning and disinfection; if necessary prescriptions of GMP to prevent re-infection

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Rearing period

See day-old chicks

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Production period

See day-old chicks

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases - Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks

Competitive exclusion strategies take place.

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases - Broiler flocks: Rearing period

Competitive exclusion strategies take place.

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases - Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Competitive exclusion strategies take place. Logistic Slaughtering is permitted for *Salmonella* spp. positive flocks (flocks positive for *S. Enteritidis* or *S. Typhimurium* are not slaughtered).

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases - Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flock based approach)

According to Commission regulation 2073/2005

Notification system in place

All positive findings in broiler flocks had to be notified to the local authority and via the Poultry health data (PHD) to the Federal Ministry of Health.

Results of the investigation

Breeding flocks: In 2016, 122 breeding flocks for meat production were kept in 57 holdings in Austria (one holding with both flocks for meat and egg production). *Salmonella* sp. has been detected in 2 flocks, the target serovars were not identified in any flock. Austria met the EU-target that has to be calculated for all breeding flocks (meat and egg production line, n = 149 flocks) of max 1% set for 2016 (0.0%).

Broiler flocks: In 2016, 4.666 broiler flocks were grown up in 536 holdings in Austria. In 177 flocks (3.8%) *Salmonella* sp. has been detected but the target serovars were only identified in seven flocks (0.2%).

Austria met the EU-target of max 1% set for 2016. *S. Infantis* was the most common serovar in 104 flocks (58%), followed by *S. Thompson* in 31 flocks (17%), and *S. Montevideo* (10 flocks, 6%). In two flocks two different serovars could be isolated (*S. Infantis* and *S. Thompson*).

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Breeding flocks: The number of breeding flocks has increased in Austria since 2005 from 60 flocks to 149 flocks (meat production and egg production lines). Based on that numbers, the EU-target can only be met, if maximum one flock is positive for the target serovars. Since the control program in breeding flocks has been running, the annual target of max. 1% was met with exception of 2005 and 2012.

Broiler flocks: In 2009, the first year of the existence of the *Salmonella* control program in broiler the EU-target of max. 1% could not be achieved, but since then the program was successful and the EU-target was met each year. In the last years the prevalence of *Salmonella* spp. increased from 2.4% to 3.8%; the lowest prevalence of *Salmonella* spp. positive flocks was observed in 2011 (2.4%).

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonosis brochure.

B. *Salmonella* in *Gallus gallus* - breeding flocks for egg production and flocks of laying hens

Monitoring system - Sampling strategy - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

There are only parent flocks in Austria, no elite and no grandparent flocks. The permanent monitoring plan performed by a national program takes place at hatcheries and on farm level; each flock is tested regularly as well by the farmer as by the Veterinary Authorities. If *S. Enteritidis*, *S. Typhimurium*, *S. Infantis*, *S. Hadar* and *S. Virchow* or *S. Pullorum Gallinarum* is isolated from breeding flocks at the hatchery the flock is banned and sampled for confirmation on the farm: 300 faeces samples and inner organs of 5 chickens or intestinal content of 5 chickens are pooled. If a parent flock tests positive for other *Salmonella* serotypes, official veterinarians are required to investigate the source of infection to optimize biosecurity.

Monitoring system - Sampling strategy - Laying hens flocks

Each flock is tested every 15 weeks sampling two pairs of boot swabs, at least one testing per year is done by an official veterinarian (boot swabs, dust samples and faeces for residue testing are taken) according to Commission Regulation (EU) No 517/2011. At the earliest 3 weeks prior to slaughter, two pairs of boot swabs must be taken from each flock. Since May 2007, every flock has been tested in accordance to Commission Regulation (EU) No 517/2011.

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Day-old chicks

Every flock is tested at day one

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Rearing period

1. Routine testing: Every flock is tested at the age of 4 and 12 weeks and two weeks before moving to laying phase or laying unit. 2. Confirmation: If routine testing reveals positive *Salmonella* test results, a follow-up test must be performed from the identical flock.

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Production period

Monitoring is performed according the national program and takes place at the hatchery and on the farm; at the hatchery: each flock is tested every two weeks by the industry, and every 16 weeks by the Veterinary Authorities; on the farm: each flock is tested every two weeks by the farmer and 3 times by the Veterinary Authorities (at beginning of production, in the middle of the production period and within the last 8 weeks before slaughter).

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling - Laying hens: Day-old chicks

Chickens are tested at day one.

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling - Laying hens: Rearing period

3 times (at day one, week 8 to 12) and two weeks before moving to laying phase or laying unit

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling - Laying hens: Production period

Each flock is tested every 15 weeks with two pairs of boot swabs; an official veterinarian samples every flock at least once a year according to Commission Regulation (EU) No 517/2011.

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling - Laying hens: Before slaughter at farm

Within 3 weeks before slaughter with two pairs of boot swabs at farm

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling - Laying hens: At slaughter

According to Commission regulation 2073/2005

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling - Eggs at packing centre (flock based approach)

According to the program of the cooperatives voluntary surface swabs (e.g. every eight weeks)

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Day-old chicks

Visibly soiled hatcher basket liners, dead chicks if available

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Rearing period

Routine testing: drag swabs, pooled faeces. For confirmation: 300 faeces samples and inner organs of 5 chickens or intestinal content of 5 chickens were pooled.

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Production period

Routine testing: Boot swabs, pooled faeces; in the hatchery: dust, meconium, broken eggshells and hatched eggs. For confirmation: 300 faeces samples and inner organs of 5 chickens or intestinal content of 5 chickens were pooled.

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken - Laying hens: Day-old chicks

Visibly soiled hatcher basket liners, dead chicks if available

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken - Laying hens: Rearing period

Boot swabs, pooled faeces

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken - Laying hens: Production period

Boot swabs, pooled faeces in holdings with enriched cages; official controls: additional dust samples and pooled faeces for antimicrobial testing

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken - Laying hens: Before slaughter at farm

Two pairs of boot swabs per flock

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken - Laying hens: At slaughter

According to Commission regulation 2073/2005

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken - Eggs at packing centre (flock based approach)

Voluntary e.g. surface swabs

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Day-old chicks

Visibly soiled hatcher basket liners, dead chicks if available

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Rearing period

Routine testing: 5 pairs of boot swabs or 200 to 300 pooled droppings of 1 gram per flock, collection of dust. For confirmation: 300 feces samples and inner organs of 5 chickens or intestinal content of 5 chickens were pooled.

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) - Breeding flocks: Production period

Routine testing: 5 pairs of boot swabs, pooled feces, collection of dust. For confirmation: 300 feces samples and inner organs of 5 chickens or intestinal content of 5 chickens were pooled.

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) - Laying hens: Day-old chicks

Visibly soiled hatcher basket liners, dead chicks if available

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) - Laying hens: Rearing period

2 pairs of boot swabs per flock

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) - Laying hens: Production period

Industry sampling: 2 pairs of boot swabs per flock.

Official sampling: 2 pairs of boot swabs per flock, 25 g of dust and 60 pooled feces samples.

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) - Laying hens: Before slaughter at farm

Two pairs of boot swabs per flock

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) - Laying hens: At slaughter

According to Commission regulation 2073/2005

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) - Eggs at packing centre (flock based approach)

No legal requirements, e.g. surface swabs

Monitoring system - Case definition - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Day-old chicks

Routine testing: *Salmonella* spp. isolated from samples taken

Monitoring system - Case definition - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Rearing period

Salmonella spp. isolated from samples taken.

Monitoring system - Case definition - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Production period

Salmonella spp. isolated from samples taken.

Monitoring system - Case definition - Laying hens: Day-old chicks

Salmonella spp. isolated from samples taken

Monitoring system - Case definition - Laying hens: Rearing period

Salmonella spp. isolated from samples taken

Monitoring system - Case definition - Laying hens: Production period

Salmonella spp. isolated from boot swabs or dust or detection of antimicrobials or bacterial growth inhibitory effect in feces samples

Monitoring system - Case definition - Laying hens: Before slaughter at farm

Salmonella spp. isolated from boot swabs

Monitoring system - Case definition - Laying hens: At slaughter

According to Commission regulation 2073/2005

Monitoring system - Case definition - Eggs at packing centre (flock based approach)

Salmonella spp. isolated from surface swabs

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Day-old chicks

According to ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007 (Annex D of ISO 6579). All isolates obtained in the primary laboratory are sent to the NRC *Salmonella* and serotyped according to the White-Kauffmann-Le-Minor-Scheme. All *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are lyso-typed according to the methods used by PHE, Colindale, UK.

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Rearing period

See day-old chicks

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Production period

See day-old chicks

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used - Laying hens: Day-old chicks

According to ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007 (Annex D of ISO 6579). All isolates obtained in the primary laboratory are sent to the NRC *Salmonella* and serotyped according to the White-Kauffmann-Le-Minor-Scheme. All *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are lyso-typed according to the methods used by PHE, Colindale, UK.

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used - Laying hens: Rearing period

See day-old chicks

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used - Laying hens: Production period

See day-old chicks

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used - Laying hens: Before slaughter at farm

See day-old chicks

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used - Laying hens: At slaughter

See day-old chicks

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used - Eggs at packing centre (flock based approach)

See day-old chicks

Vaccination policy - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

The national program for parent flocks made vaccination against *Salmonella* Enteritidis mandatory for all flocks.

Vaccination policy - Laying hens flocks

The national program made vaccination against *Salmonella* Enteritidis mandatory for all flocks.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Stringent biosecurity

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place - Laying hens flocks

No.

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

The Austrian control program is conducted according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation (BGBl. II 2007/100, Geflügelhygieneverordnung 2007 as amended). This Regulation is in line with Commission Regulation (EU) No 200/2010.

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place - Laying hens flocks

The Austrian control program is conducted according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation (BGBl. II 2007/100, Geflügelhygieneverordnung 2007 as amended). This Regulation is in line with Commission Regulation (EU) No 517/2011.

Control program/mechanisms - Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

All actions according to EU- and national legislation

Control program/mechanisms - Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Review of the target serovars.

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Measures according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation: Banning of the incriminated sector of the holding; culling of the infected flock; disposal of the hatched eggs; abolishing of the restriction after cleaning and disinfection; if necessary prescriptions of GMP to prevent re-infection

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases - Laying hens flocks

No class A eggs or culling in case of association with a food borne outbreak; EU regulation No 1237/2007 is in force.

Notification system in place

All positive results from laying flocks must be reported to the local authorities and via the Poultry Health Data to the Federal Ministry of Health (FMH).

Results of the investigation

Breeding flocks: In 2016, 30 breeding flocks for egg production were kept in 16 holdings in Austria (one holding with both flocks for meat and egg production). *Salmonella* spp. have been detected in one flocks, none of the target serovars was identified in the flocks. Austria met the EU-target that has to be calculated for all breeding flocks (meat and egg production line, n = 149 flocks) of max 1% set for 2015 (0.0%).

Laying flocks: In 2016, 2,876 flocks were in production in 1,118 holdings in Austria. In 44 flocks (1.5%) *Salmonella* spp. have been detected, the target serovars in 13 flocks (0.5%), 9-times *S. Enteritidis* and 4-times *S. Typhimurium*. Austria met the EU-target of max 1% set for 2016.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Breeding flocks: The number of breeding flocks has increased in Austria since 2005 from 60 flocks to 149 flocks. Based on that numbers, the EU-target can only be met, if maximum one flock is positive for the target serovars. Since the control program in breeding flocks has been running, the annual target of max. 1% was met with exception of 2005 and 2012.

Laying flocks: Since 2008 an EU-target has been implemented for laying hens. In 2008, the target set for Austria based on the EU-baseline survey was max 8.6%, since then max 2 %. Austria met the EU-target each year with the exception of 2009. The prevalence of *Salmonella* spp. positive flocks has been successfully reduced from 4.3% in 2007 to 0.9% in 2015, but increased in 2016 to 1.5%.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Laying hens and eggs still play an important role as reservoir and vehicle for human infections.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the zoonosis brochure 2016.

C. *Salmonella* in other poultry, turkey flocks

Monitoring system - Sampling strategy - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

no breeding flocks in Austria

Monitoring system - Sampling strategy - Meat production flocks

Within 3 weeks prior to slaughter boot swabs have to be taken. Other programs are not established, only voluntary sampling by the farmer or sampling according to private cooperatives is performed.

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Day-old chicks

no breeding flocks in Austria

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Rearing period

no breeding flocks in Austria

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Production period

no breeding flocks in Austria

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling - Meat production flocks: Day-old chicks

no legal requirements, e.g. at day one each flock

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling - Meat production flocks: Rearing period

no legal requirements

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling - Meat production flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Two pairs of boot swabs per flock; 10 % of the flocks sampled by competent authority, Regulation EU 584/2008, followed by Commission Regulation (EU) No 1190/2012, is in force since 01.01.2010

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling - Meat production flocks: At slaughter (flock based approach)

According to Commission regulation 2073/2005

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Day-old chicks

no breeding flocks in Austria

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Rearing period

no breeding flocks in Austria

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Production period

no breeding flocks in Austria

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken - Meat production flocks: Day-old chicks

no legal requirements, e.g. visibly soiled hatcher basket liners

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken - Meat production flocks: Rearing period

no legal requirements, e.g. pooled feces

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken - Meat production flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Industry sampling: 2 pairs of boot swabs per flock Official sampling: 2 pairs of boot swabs per flock, 60 pooled faeces samples (150g)

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken - Meat production flocks: At slaughter (flock based approach)

According to Commission regulation 2073/2005

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Day-old chicks

no breeding flocks in Austria

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Rearing period

no breeding flocks in Austria

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Production period

no breeding flocks in Austria

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) - Meat production flocks: Day-old chicks

No sampling

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) - Meat production flocks: Rearing period

No legal requirements

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) - Meat production flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Two pairs of boot swabs per flock; 10 % of the flocks sampled by competent authority, Regulation EU 584/2008, followed by Commission Regulation (EU) No 1190/2012, is in force since 01.01.2010

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) - Meat production flocks: At slaughter (flock based approach)

According to Commission regulation 2073/2005

Monitoring system - Case definition - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Day-old chicks

no breeding flocks in Austria

Monitoring system - Case definition - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Rearing period

no breeding flocks in Austria

Monitoring system - Case definition - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Production period

no breeding flocks in Austria

Monitoring system - Case definition - Meat production flocks: Day-old chicks

No legal requirements

Monitoring system - Case definition - Meat production flocks: Rearing period

No legal requirements

Monitoring system - Case definition - Meat production flocks: Before slaughter at farm
Salmonella spp. isolated from sample material

Monitoring system - Case definition - Meat production flocks: At slaughter (flock based approach)

According to Commission regulation 2073/2005

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Day-old chicks

no breeding flocks in Austria

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Rearing period
no breeding flocks in Austria

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary): Production period
no breeding flocks in Austria

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used - Meat production flocks: Day-old chicks

According to ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007 (Annex D of ISO 6579). All isolates obtained in the primary laboratory are sent to the NRC-*Salmonella* and serotyped according to the White-Kauffmann-Le-Minor-Scheme. All *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are lyso-typed according to the methods used by PHE, Colindale, UK.

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used - Meat production flocks: Rearing period
see day-old chicks

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used - Meat production flocks: Before slaughter at farm
see day-old chicks

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used - Meat production flocks: At slaughter (flock based approach)
see day-old chicks

Vaccination policy - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)
no breeding flocks in Austria

Vaccination policy - Meat production flocks
Neither legal requirements nor recommendations

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)
no breeding flocks in Austria

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place - Meat production flocks
Nil

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place - Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)
no breeding flocks in Austria

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place - Meat production flocks

The Austrian control program is conducted according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation (BGBl. II 2007/100, Geflügelhygieneverordnung 2007 as amended). This Regulation is in line with Commission Regulation (EU) No 1190/2013.

Control program/mechanisms - Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses
Nil

Control program/mechanisms - Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Review of the target serovars

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases - Breeding flocks

no breeding flocks in Austria

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases - Meat Production flocks

According to Commission Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005

Notification system in place

All positive findings in turkey broiler flocks have to be notified to the local authority and via the Poultry health data (PHD) to the Federal Ministry of Health and Women's Affairs (BMGF).

Results of the investigation

In 2016, 406 flocks have been fattened in 136 holdings in Austria. *Salmonella* spp. have been detected in 10 flocks (2.5%), the target serovars were identified in 2 flocks (0.5%) (2-times *S. Enteritidis*). Austria met the EU-target of max 1% set for 2016.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2016, Austria again met the EU-target in turkeys. Since 2010 the prevalence of *Salmonella* spp. has shown a decreasing trend. In 2013 the highest prevalence of *Salmonella* spp. was detected (36 flocks, 10.1%), in 2016 the lowest so far (10 flocks, 2.5%).

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

D. *Salmonella* in carcasses of both broilers and fattening turkeys sampled for testing and verification of compliance, in accordance with point 2.1.5 of Chapter 2 of Annex I to Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005

See chapter "Antimicrobial resistance of *Salmonella* spp. isolates from animals and food"

Table 9 *Salmonella* spp. in poultry breeding flocks (*Gallus gallus*), 2016

Animal species	No of flocks under control programme	Source of information	Sampling strategy	Sampler	Sampling stage	Analytical method	Target verification	Sampling unit	Comment	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<i>S. Enteritidis</i>	<i>S. Typhimurium</i>	<i>S. Agona</i>	<i>S. Rissen</i>
<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl), parent breeding flocks for egg production line, during rearing period, control and eradication programmes	11	PHD	Census sampling	Official and industry sampling	farm	ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	No	herd/flock	-	11	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl), parent breeding flocks for egg production line, adult, control and eradication programmes	30	PHD	Census sampling	Official and industry sampling	farm	ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	Yes	herd/flock	-	30	1	0	0	1	0
<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl), parent breeding flocks for broiler production line, during rearing period, control and eradication programmes	65	PHD	Census sampling	Official and industry sampling	farm	ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	No	herd/flock	-	65	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl), parent breeding flocks for broiler production line, adult, control and eradication programmes	116	PHD	Census sampling	Official and industry sampling	farm	ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	Yes	herd/flock	-	116	1	0	0	0	1

PHD: Poultry Health Data

Table 10 *Salmonella* spp. in other commercial poultry, 2016

Animal species	No of flocks under control programme	Source of information	Sampling strategy	Sampler	Sample type	Analytical method	Target verification	Sampling unit	Comment	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	Total units positive for <i>S. Enteritidis</i> and <i>S. Typhimurium</i>	Total units positive for <i>S. Enteritidis</i>	Total units positive for <i>S. Typhimurium</i>	<i>S. Agona</i>	<i>S. Coelin</i>	<i>S. Dublin</i>	<i>S. Enteritidis</i> PT11	<i>S. Enteritidis</i> PT12	<i>S. Enteritidis</i> PT21	<i>S. Enteritidis</i> PT4	<i>S. Enteritidis</i> PT62	<i>S. Enteritidis</i> PT6c	<i>S. Enteritidis</i> PT7	<i>S. Enteritidis</i> PT8	<i>S. Geminata</i>	<i>S. Havana</i>	<i>Salmonella enterica</i> , subspecies <i>salamae</i>	<i>Salmonella enterica</i> , subspecies <i>diarizonae</i>	<i>S. Indiana</i>	<i>S. Infantis</i>	<i>S. Kottbus</i>	<i>S. Livingstone</i>	<i>S. Liandoff</i>	<i>S. Mbandaka</i>	<i>S. Monophasischer Stamm d. C1-Gruppe</i>	<i>S. Montevideo</i>	<i>S. Muenchen</i>	<i>S. Paratyphi B var. Java</i>	<i>S. Saintpaul</i>	<i>S. Sentenberg</i>	<i>S. Stanley</i>	<i>S. Tennessee</i>	<i>S. Thompson</i>	<i>S. Typhimurium</i> DT 1	<i>S. Typhimurium</i> RDNC	<i>S. Umbilo</i>				
Gallus gallus (fowl), Laying hens																																																			
During rearing period, control and eradication programmes	408	PHD	Census sampling	Official and industry sampling	environmental sample	ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	No	flock/herd		408	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0							
Adult: at farm, control and eradication programmes	2,876	PHD	Census sampling	Official and industry sampling	environmental sample	ISO6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	Yes	flock/herd	1)	2,876	44	13	9	4	3	1	1	4	1	1					3	1	1	1	4	3	1					6	2	1	2	1	3	3	4								
Adult: at farm, control and eradication programmes	2,876	PHD	Census sampling	Industry sampling	environmental sample	ISO6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	No	flock/herd		2,647	20	5	3	2	1	1		1	1						1											6	2			1		1	2								
Adult: at farm, control and eradication programmes	2,876	PHD	Objective sampling	Official sampling	environmental sample	ISO6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	No	flock/herd	2)	1,698	26	9	7	2	2			1	3	1					3		1	1	4									1	1	1		3	2	2							
Adult: at farm, control and eradication programmes	2,876	PHD	Suspect sampling	Official sampling	environmental sample	ISO6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	No	flock/herd		7	2	1	1	0											1															1											
Gallus gallus (fowl); Broilers																																																			
Before slaughter, at farm, control and eradication programmes	4,666	PHD	Census sampling	Official and industry sampling	environmental sample	ISO6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	Yes	flock/herd	3)	4,666	177	7	2	5	5	5	1							1		1								1	104	1	2	3	1	10		6	1	31	1	4	1				
Before slaughter, at farm, control and eradication programmes	4,666	PHD	Census sampling	Industry sampling	environmental sample	ISO6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	No	flock/herd	3)	4,608	173	7	2	5	4	5	1							1		1								1	101	1	2	3	1	10		6	1	31	1	4	1				
Before slaughter, at farm, control and eradication programmes	4,666	PHD	Objective sampling	Official sampling	environmental sample	ISO6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	No	flock/herd		61	4	0	0	0	1																																				
Turkeys; Breeding flocks																																																			
Adult, at farm, control and eradication programmes	0	PHD																																																	
Turkeys; Fattening flocks																																																			
Before slaughter, at farm, control and eradication programmes	406	PHD	Census sampling	Official and industry sampling	environmental sample	ISO6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	Yes	flock/herd	4)	406	10	2	2	0	1																																				
Before slaughter, at farm, control and eradication programmes	406	PHD	Census sampling	Industry sampling	environmental sample	ISO6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	No	flock/herd		399	9	2	2	0	1																																				
Before slaughter, at farm, control and eradication programmes	406	PHD	Objective sampling	Official sampling	environmental sample	ISO6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	No	flock/herd		20	2	2	2	0										1	1																										

PHD: Poultry Health Data

- 1) one flock harbouring two different *S. Enteritidis* phage types (PT4 and PT12) and one flock two different *Salmonella* serovars (*S. Typhimurium* RDNC and *S. Java*)
- 2) one flock harbouring two different *S. Enteritidis* phage types (PT4 and PT12)
- 3) two flocks harbouring two different *Salmonella* serovars (*S. Infantis* and *S. Thompson*)
- 4) one flock harbouring two different *S. Enteritidis* phage types (PT6c and PT7)

4.1.5. *Salmonella* spp. in feeding stuff

Monitoring system – Sampling strategy

Official monitoring based on risk assessment, own check programme by the industry based on HACCP.

Monitoring system – Frequency of the sampling – Domestic feed material of plant origin

Assigned sampling plan, random samples are collected based on an official surveillance programme.

Monitoring system – Frequency of the sampling – Domestic feed material of animal origin

Assigned sampling plan, random samples are collected based on an official surveillance programme.

Monitoring system – Frequency of the sampling – Imported feed material of plant origin

Assigned sampling plan, random samples are collected based on an official surveillance programme.

Monitoring system – Frequency of the sampling – Imported feed material of animal origin

Assigned sampling plan, random samples are collected based on an official surveillance programme.

Monitoring system – Frequency of the sampling – Process control in feed mills

Assigned sampling plan, random samples are collected based on an official surveillance programme.

Monitoring system – Frequency of the sampling – Compound feedingstuffs

Assigned sampling plan, random samples are collected based on an official surveillance programme.

Monitoring system – Type of specimen taken – Domestic feed material of plant origin

Feed material of cereal grain and oil seed or fruit origin

Monitoring system – Type of specimen taken – Domestic feed material of animal origin

Fish meal, dried animal by-products for pets

Monitoring system – Type of specimen taken – Imported feed material of plant origin

Oil seed meals and cakes

Monitoring system – Type of specimen taken – Imported feed material of animal origin

Fish meal, dried animal by-products for pets

Monitoring system – Type of specimen taken – Process control in feed mills

Not applicable (n. a.)

Monitoring system – Type of specimen taken – Compound feedingstuffs

Feed for farm animals (mainly poultry) and pets

Monitoring system – Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) – Domestic feed material of plant origin

Sampling is performed according to EC-Directive 152/2009/EEC applying special hygiene requirements or sampling of original packaged products.

Monitoring system – Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) – Domestic feed material of animal origin

Sampling is performed according to EC-Directive 152/2009/EEC applying special hygiene requirements or sampling of original packaged products.

Monitoring system – Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) – Imported feed material of plant origin

Sampling is performed according to EC-Directive 152/2009/EEC applying special hygiene requirements or sampling of original packaged products.

Monitoring system – Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) – Imported feed material of animal origin

Sampling is performed according to EC-Directive 152/2009/EEC applying special hygiene requirements or sampling of original packaged products.

Monitoring system – Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) – Process control in feed mills

Sampling is performed according to EC-Directive 152/2009/EEC applying special hygiene requirements or sampling of original packaged products.

Monitoring system – Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) – Compound feedingstuffs

Sampling is performed according to EC-Directive 152/2009/EEC applying special hygiene requirements or sampling of original packaged products.

Monitoring system – Definition of positive finding – Domestic feed material of plant origin

Salmonella spp. Isolated from the sample

Monitoring system – Definition of positive finding – Domestic feed material of animal origin

Salmonella spp. Isolated from the sample

Monitoring system – Definition of positive finding – Imported feed material of plant origin

Salmonella spp. Isolated from the sample

Monitoring system – Definition of positive finding – Imported feed material of animal origin

Salmonella spp. Isolated from the sample

Monitoring system – Definition of positive finding – Process control in feed mills

Salmonella spp. Isolated from the sample

Monitoring system – Definition of positive finding – Compound feedingstuffs

Salmonella spp. Isolated from the sample

Monitoring system – Diagnostic/analytical methods used – Domestic feed material of plant origin

Bacteriological method: ISO 6579:2002; sample weight: 25 g (samples related to suspected lots or cases are analysed by testing several subsamples in parallel); all isolates are sent to the NRC *Salmonella* are serotyped according to the White-Kauffmann-Le-Minor-Scheme. All *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are lysotyped according to the methods used by PHE, Colindale, UK.

Monitoring system – Diagnostic/analytical methods used – Domestic feed material of animal origin

as above

Monitoring system – Diagnostic/analytical methods used – Imported feed material of plant origin

as above

Monitoring system – Diagnostic/analytical methods used – Imported feed material of animal origin

as above

Monitoring system – Diagnostic/analytical methods used – Process control in feed mills

as above

Monitoring system – Diagnostic/analytical methods used – Compound feedingstuffs
as above

Control program/mechanisms – The control program/strategies in place

National legislation: BGBl. Nr. 139/1999, as last amended by BGBl. Nr. 87/2005 (Futtermittelgesetz 1999) and BGBl. Nr. 316/2010 (Futtermittelverordnung 2010) containing general requirements for feedingstuffs and BGBl. II Nr. 100/2007 (Geflügelhygieneverordnung 2007). EC: Reg. (EG) 183/2005 (Futtermittelhygieneverordnung) and Reg. (EG) 882/2004 (Kontrollverordnung) with regard to *Salmonella* monitoring, general requirements for feed material and compound feed, coordinated annual control program.

Control program/mechanisms – Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Control program/mechanisms – Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings – Domestic feed material of plant origin

In the event of a positive result, the notification results in the confiscation of the infected feedingstuffs according to official measures. This includes the withdrawal of the feedingstuffs from the market, the recall of feed, decontamination of the feed, disposal or other use of the feed, exploration and elimination of the sources of contamination and operational measures to prevent future contaminations.

Measures in case of the positive findings – Domestic feed material of animal origin

In the event of a positive result, the notification results in the confiscation of the infected feedingstuffs according to official measures. This includes the withdrawal of the feedingstuffs from the market, the recall of feed, decontamination of the feed, disposal or other use of the feed, exploration and elimination of the sources of contamination and operational measures to prevent future contaminations.

Measures in case of the positive findings – Imported feed material of plant origin

In the event of a positive result, the notification results in the confiscation of the infected feedingstuffs according to official measures. This includes the withdrawal of the feedingstuffs from the market, the recall of feed, decontamination of the feed, disposal or other use of the feed, exploration and elimination of the sources of contamination and operational measures to prevent future contaminations.

Measures in case of the positive findings – Imported feed material of animal origin

In the event of a positive result, the notification results in the confiscation of the infected feedingstuffs according to official measures. This includes the withdrawal of the feedingstuffs from the market, the recall of feed, decontamination of the feed, disposal or other use of the feed, exploration and elimination of the sources of contamination and operational measures to prevent future contaminations.

Measures in case of the positive findings – Process control in feed mills

In the event of a positive result, the notification results in the confiscation of the infected feedingstuffs according to official measures. This includes the withdrawal of the feedingstuffs from the market, the recall of feed, decontamination of the feed, disposal or other use of the feed, exploration and elimination of the sources of contamination and operational measures to prevent future contaminations.

Measures in case of the positive findings – Compound feedingstuffs

In the event of a positive result, the notification results in the confiscation of the infected feedingstuffs according to official measures. This includes the withdrawal of the feedingstuffs from the market, the recall of feed, decontamination of the feed, disposal or other use of the feed, exploration and elimination of the sources of contamination and operational measures to prevent future contaminations.

Notification system in place

The Rapid Alert System for Food and Feed (RASFF) notifies the local authorities and the system has been in place since 1979. The legal basis of the RASFF is Regulation EC/178/2002.

Results of the investigation

see tables

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In the last 20 years, the quality of feed has improved due to the increase of numbers of farms, processing plants and retailer using HACCP concepts. Further thoroughly investigations on feed related contaminations in connection with traceability of contaminated feed/components of feed as well as more frequently processing and pelletizing feed/contaminated feed have contributed to a better feed quality. So during this period a considerable increase of feed hygiene and feed safety could be reached. Additionally a long-term improvement of the *Salmonella*-status of feed, however, can be achieved only by a proactive approach of this issue involving all parties concerned, such as crushing plants, wholesalers and retailers, trader, but also by cooperation and rapid notification of positive findings from poultry farms, food and feed business operators to the competent authority for feed control.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Table 11 *Salmonella* spp. in feed material of animal origin, 2016

matrixTerm	sampStageTerm	sampUnitTerm	sampOrig	sampWeight	sampWeightUnitTerm	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> spp.
Feed material of land animal origin	Processing plant	batch (food/feed)	XX	25	Gram	1	0
Feed material of marine animal origin - fish meal	Processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0
			EU	25	Gram	1	0
	Retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	2	0
			EU	25	Gram	2	0

Sampling context: Surveillance - official control - objective sampling

Table 12 *Salmonella* spp. in compound feeding stuff, 2016

matrixTerm	sampStageTerm	sampUnitTerm	sampOrig	sampWeight	sampWeightUnitTerm	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<i>S.</i> Derby	<i>S.</i> Infantis	<i>S.</i> Livingstone	<i>S.</i> Typhimurium DT1	<i>S.</i> Typhimurium, monophasic DT193	<i>S.</i> Uganda
Compound feedingstuffs for cattle - final product - non-pelleted/meal	Farm	batch (food/feed)	XX	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			XX	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Compound feedingstuffs for fish - final product	Retail	batch (food/feed)	XX	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Feed mill	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Compound feedingstuffs for fish - final product - non-pelleted/meal	Retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Compound feedingstuffs for horses - final product - non-pelleted/meal	Feed mill	batch (food/feed)	XX	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			XX	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	25	Gram	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
XX	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Compound feedingstuffs for horses - final product - pelleted	Processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
XX			25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Compound feedingstuffs for pigs - final product	Retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Compound feedingstuffs for pigs - final product - non-pelleted/meal	Farm	batch (food/feed)	XX	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Feed mill	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			XX	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			XX	25	Gram	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	31	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
EU			25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
XX	25	Gram	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Compound feedingstuffs for pigs - final product - pelleted	Processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
XX			25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry (non specified) - final product - non-pelleted/meal	Farm	batch (food/feed)	XX	25	Gram	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Feed mill	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		XX	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry (non specified) - final product - pelleted	Farm	batch (food/feed)	XX	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry, breeders - final product - non-pelleted/meal	Processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry,	Farm	batch	XX	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

matrixTerm	sampStageTerm	sampUnitTerm	sampOrig	sampWeight	sampWeightUnitTerm	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	S. Derby	S. Infantis	S. Livingstone	S. Typhimurium DT1	S. Typhimurium, monophasic DT193	S. Uganda	
broilers - final product - non-pelleted/meal		(food/feed)												
	Feed mill	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
XX			25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry, broilers - final product - pelleted	Farm	batch (food/feed)	XX	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry, laying hens - final product - non-pelleted/meal	Farm	batch (food/feed)	XX	25	Gram	21	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Feed mill	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			XX	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry, laying hens - final product - pelleted	Retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			XX	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Compound feedingstuffs for rabbits - final product	Retail	batch (food/feed)	XX	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Compound feedingstuffs for rabbits - final product - non-pelleted/meal	Feed mill	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Compound feedingstuffs for rabbits - final product - pelleted	Retail	batch (food/feed)	XX	25	Gram	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XX	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Compound feedingstuffs for reindeers - final product - non-pelleted/meal	Processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
XX			25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Compound feedingstuffs for turkeys - final product - non-pelleted/meal	Farm	batch (food/feed)	XX	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Compound feedingstuffs for turkeys - final product - pelleted	Farm	batch (food/feed)	XX	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Pet food	Processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XX	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		single (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	25	Gram	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Retail	single (food/feed)	XX	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			AT	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Pet food - dog snacks (pig ears, chewing bones)	Processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	9	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	
			XX	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		single (food/feed)	XX	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	13	3	1	0	1	0	0	1	
			EU	25	Gram	4	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	
			XE	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
XX			25	Gram	3	1	0	1	0	0	0	0		
single	AT	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			

matrixTerm	sampStageTerm	sampUnitTerm	sampOrig	sampWeight	sampWeightUnitTerm	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<i>S.</i> Derby	<i>S.</i> Infantis	<i>S.</i> Livingstone	<i>S.</i> Typhimurium DT1	<i>S.</i> Typhimurium, monophasic DT193	<i>S.</i> Uganda
		(food/feed)	EU	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			XX	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sampling context: Surveillance - official control - objective sampling

Table 13 *Salmonella* spp. in other feed matter, 2016

matrixTerm	sampStageTerm	sampUnitTerm	sampOrig	sampWeight	sampWeightUnitTerm	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> spp.
Feed material of cereal grain origin - other cereal grain derived - by-products of brewing and distilling	Processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	2	0
	Retail	batch (food/feed)	XX	25	Gram	1	0
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin	Retail	batch (food/feed)	XX	25	Gram	4	0
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - other oil seeds derived	Farm	batch (food/feed)	XX	25	Gram	1	0
	Feed mill	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0
	Processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	3	0
	Retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - rape seed derived	Farm	batch (food/feed)	XX	25	Gram	1	0
	Feed mill	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0
	Processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	5	0
			XX	25	Gram	1	0
	Retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	2	0
			EU	25	Gram	1	0
XX			25	Gram	2	0	
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - soya (bean) derived	Farm	batch (food/feed)	XX	25	Gram	2	0
	Feed mill	batch (food/feed)	XX	25	Gram	1	0
	Processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	10	0
			XX	25	Gram	3	0
	Retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	7	0
			XX	25	Gram	2	0
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - sunflower seed derived	Processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0
			XX	25	Gram	1	0
	Retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	3	0
			XX	25	Gram	1	0

Sampling context: Surveillance - official control - objective sampling

4.1.6. *Salmonella* serovars and phage type distribution

The methods of collecting, isolating and testing of *Salmonella* isolates are described in the chapters above respectively for each animal species, foodstuffs and in humans. The serotype and phage type distributions can be used to investigate the sources of the *Salmonella* infections in humans. Findings of same serovars and phagetypes in human cases and in foodstuffs or animals may indicate that the food category or animal species in question serves as a source of human infections. However, as information of the potential source of infection is not available, conclusions have to be made with caution.

Results presented here show the number of isolates from human cases notified to the EMS and typed by the NRC-S, food isolates obtained from sampling plan (exclusion of suspected samples), poultry isolates from the National Control Plan (NCP). Therefore the number of isolates in the tables of this chapter can differ from the number of isolates antimicrobial susceptibility tested (all isolates typed in the NRC-S are subjected to AST using the disk diffusion test).

Table 14 *Salmonella* serovars in humans, food, animals and feed (EMS/NRC-S), 2016

Serovars	Human	Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus)	Meat from bovine animals	Meat from duck	Meat from other animal species or not specified	Meat from poultry, unspecified	Meat from turkey	Meat from pig	Other processed food products and prepared dishes	Broiler flock, NCP	Layer flock, NCP	Broiler flock, slaughterhouse PHC	Turkey flock, NCP	Pet food
Number of isolates	1,415	38	4	2	1	28	2	2	4	179	46	36	11	7
<i>S. Enteritidis</i>	671			1	1	1			2	2	10		3	
<i>S. Typhimurium</i>	174	1	1	1		1				5	4	1		1
<i>S. Infantis</i>	64	35	1			22			1	106	3	17	3	1
<i>S. Typhimurium</i> , monophasic (1.4.[5].12:l:-)	55													1
serovar unknown	47													
<i>S. Senftenberg</i>	37									6	1	1		
<i>S. Coeln</i>	22	1				1				5		7	1	
<i>S. Newport</i>	19					2	2							
<i>S. Stanley</i>	19													2
<i>S. Virchow</i>	18													
<i>S. group B</i>	17		1											
<i>S. Thompson</i>	17	1								29	3		1	
<i>S. Agona</i>	15					1				5	3	2		
<i>S. Braenderup</i>	15													
<i>S. Saintpaul</i>	15		1										1	
<i>S. Bovismorbificans</i>	12													
<i>S. Kentucky</i>	11													
<i>S. Poona</i>	9													
<i>S. Java</i>	8										2			
<i>S. Chester</i>	7													
<i>S. Corvallis</i>	7													
<i>S. Weltevreden</i>	6													
<i>S. Derby</i>	5													2
<i>S. enterica</i> , subsp. <i>diarizonae</i>	5										4			
<i>S. Abony</i>	4													
<i>S. Brandenburg</i>	4													
<i>S. enterica</i> , subsp. <i>enterica</i>	4													
<i>S. group C1</i>	4									1		1		
<i>S. Hadar</i>	4													
<i>S. Haifa</i>	4													
<i>S. Mbandaka</i>	4									3	6			
<i>S. Ohio</i>	4													
<i>S. Adjame</i>	3													

Serovars	Human	Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus)	Meat from bovine animals	Meat from duck	Meat from other animal species or not specified	Meat from poultry, unspecified	Meat from turkey	Meat from pig	Other processed food products and prepared dishes	Broiler flock, NCP	Layer flock, NCP	Broiler flock, slaughterhouse PHC	Turkey flock, NCP	Pet food
Number of isolates	1,415	38	4	2	1	28	2	2	4	179	46	36	11	7
<i>S. Agama</i>	3													
<i>S. Eastbourne</i>	3													
<i>S. enterica, subsp. houtenae</i>	3													
<i>S. Javiana</i>	3													
<i>S. Kenya</i>	3													
<i>S. Liverpool</i>	3													
<i>S. Muenchen</i>	3										1			
<i>S. Oranienburg</i>	3													
<i>S. Ordonez</i>	3													
<i>S. Panama</i>	3													
<i>S. Stanleyville</i>	3													
<i>S. Bredeney</i>	2													
<i>S. enterica, subsp. salamae</i>	2										1			
<i>S. Give</i>	2													
<i>S. Goldcoast</i>	2													
<i>S. Kaapstad</i>	2													
<i>S. Kottbus</i>	2										1			
<i>S. Litchfield</i>	2													
<i>S. Livingstone</i>	2									1				1
<i>S. London</i>	2													
<i>S. Mikawasima</i>	2													
<i>S. Montevideo</i>	2									10	2	7		
<i>S. Muenster</i>	2													
<i>S. Napoli</i>	2													
<i>S. Potsdam</i>	2													
<i>S. Rissen</i>	2							1						
<i>S. Telelkebir</i>	2													
<i>S. Tennessee</i>	2									1	3			
<i>S. Umbilo</i>	2									1				
<i>S. Urbana</i>	2													
<i>S. Adelaide</i>	1													
<i>S. Alachua</i>	1													
<i>S. Albany</i>	1													
<i>S. Altona</i>	1													
<i>S. Archavaleta</i>	1													
<i>S. Bareilly</i>	1													
<i>S. Bonn</i>	1													
<i>S. Brunei</i>	1													
<i>S. Caracas</i>	1													
<i>S. Cerro</i>	1													
<i>S. Chicago</i>	1													
<i>S. Choleraesuis</i>	1													
<i>S. Essen</i>	1													
<i>S. Gaminara</i>	1									1				
<i>S. group D1</i>	1													
<i>S. Halle</i>	1													
<i>S. Havana</i>	1										1			
<i>S. Hull</i>	1													
<i>S. Hvittingfoss</i>	1													
<i>S. Inganda</i>	1													
<i>S. Irumu</i>	1													

Serovars	Human	Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus)	Meat from bovine animals	Meat from duck	Meat from other animal species or not specified	Meat from poultry, unspecified	Meat from turkey	Meat from pig	Other processed food products and prepared dishes	Broiler flock, NCP	Layer flock, NCP	Broiler flock, slaughterhouse PHC	Turkey flock, NCP	Pet food
Number of isolates	1,415	38	4	2	1	28	2	2	4	179	46	36	11	7
<i>S. Kasenyi</i>	1													
<i>S. Kimuenza</i>	1													
<i>S. Leeuwarden</i>	1													
<i>S. Monschaui</i>	1													
<i>S. Orientalis</i>	1													
<i>S. Oxford</i>	1													
<i>S. Reading</i>	1													
<i>S. Ridge</i>	1													
<i>S. Schwarzengrund</i>	1													
<i>S. Stourbridge</i>	1													
<i>S. Strathcona</i>	1													
<i>S. Szentes</i>	1													
<i>S. Uganda</i>	1													
<i>S. Dublin</i>											1			
<i>S. enterica, subsp. enterica rough</i>								1						
<i>S. Indiana</i>										1				
<i>S. Isangi</i>									1					
<i>S. Llandoff</i>										2				
<i>S. Uganda</i>														1

NCP – National Control Program

PHC – Process Hygiene Criteria

Data source: EMS/NRC-S as of 27.01.2017

Table 15 S. Enteritidis phage types in humans, food, animals and feed (EMS/NRC-S), 2016

S. Enteritidis phage types	Human	Meat from duck	Meat from other animal species or not specified	Meat from poultry, unspecified	Other processed food products and prepared dishes	Broiler flock, NCP	Layer flock, NCP	Turkey flock, NCP
Number of isolates	671	1	1	1	2	2	10	3
PT 8	260						3	
PT 4	81						1	
PT 21	77						4	
PT 6c	39					1		2
PT 13a	23		1					
PT 5	21				1			
PT 1	20	1						
PT 3	17							
PT 2	15							
PT 29	14							
RDNC	13			1				
PT 14b	12							
PT U	9							
PT 4b	8							
PT 11	7					1		
PT 6a	7							
PT 12	6						1	
PT 6	6							
PT 20a	5							
PT 60	3							
PT 65	3							
PT 15a	2							
PT 1d	2							
PT 23	2							
PT 53	2							
PT 9c	2							
PT not typed	2							
PT 11b	1							
PT 13	1							
PT 1b	1							
PT 20	1							
PT 21b	1							
PT 21c	1							
PT 31	1							
PT 35	1							
PT 42	1							
PT 58a	1							
PT 59	1							
PT 61	1							
PT 7	1							1
PT 62					1		1	

NCP – National Control Program

PHC – Process Hygiene Criteria

Data source: EMS/NRC-S as of 27.01.2017

Table 16 S. Typhimurium definitive types in humans, food, animals and feed (EMS/NRC-S), 2016

S. Typhimurium definitive type	Human	Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus)	Meat from bovine animals	Meat from duck	Meat from poultry, unspecified	Broiler flock, NCP	Layer flock, NCP	Broiler flock, slaughterhouse PHC	Pet food
Number of isolates	145	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1
DT 120	28		1	1					
DT 193	22								
DT 1	21				1	1			1
DT 46a	13	1							
DT U277	12								
DT 104	6								
DT U311	5								
DT U323	4								
DT 12	3								
DT 3	3								
DT 85	3								
DT U302	3								
DT 2	2								
DT 8	2								
DT not typed	2								
DT U318	2								
DT 107	1								
DT 12a	1								
DT 17	1								
DT 4	1								
DT 40	1								
DT 41	1								
DT 59	1								
DT 69	1								
DT 74	1								
DT 93	1								
DT 95	1								
DT 99	1								
DT U	1								
DT U291	1								
DT12								1	

NCP – National Control Program; PHC – Process Hygiene Criteria

Data source: EMS/NRC-S as of 27.01.2017

Table 17 S. Typhimurium, monophasic, definitive types in humans, food, animals and feed (EMS/NRC-S), 2016

definitive type	Human	Pet food
S. Typhimurium, monophasic	55	1
DT 120	1	
DT 193	47	1
DT U311	6	
RDNC	1	

Data source: EMS/NRC-S as of 27.01.2017

4.2. Campylobacteriosis

4.2.1. General evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In 2006, the number of notified human campylobacteriosis cases exceeded for the first time the number of notified salmonellosis cases in Austria. Since then, the gap between the number of cases of human campylobacteriosis and salmonellosis has been widening.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In recent years, the number of notified cases of campylobacteriosis steadily increased, reaching a new peak of 7,084 cases in 2016. The number of *Campylobacter* cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to EMS by January 26, 2017. The sources of infection are still unclear. The few published outbreaks in Austria were due to contaminated cows raw milk or chicken meat. Pets may be considered another possible source.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Feedings stuff has no obvious relevance. Animals show different colonization rates: broiler and turkey flocks approx. 50% (as of 2016), pigs approx. 50% (last monitoring in 2008), and cattle approx. 30% (last monitoring in 2011). The actual source of infection in human cases is unknown, chicken meat may account for approx. 40% of human infections.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

On January 1st, 2006, the Federal Zoonoses Act (128. Bundesgesetz: Zoonosengesetz, published on 18th November 2005) was implemented. The subject of this Act is to ensure that zoonoses, zoonotic agents and related antimicrobial resistance are properly monitored, that food-borne outbreaks receive proper epidemiological investigation to enable the collection of the information necessary in the EU. According to this Zoonoses Act, to survey and combat the zoonoses in Austria, a Federal Commission for Zoonoses (Zoonoses Commission) has been founded to advise the Federal Minister. The first meeting took place on May 3rd, 2006. The tasks of this Zoonoses Commission are - securing of effective and continuous teamwork of special fields concerned, cooperation based on free exchange of general information and where necessary, of specific data- determination of measures in case of Austrian-wide food borne outbreaks (concerning several provinces by one outbreak), to issue the annually report on trends and sources of zoonoses in Austria, and preparation of risk based, integrated monitoring and surveillance programmes. In 2016, the Austria-wide monitoring program on the trends of *Campylobacter*-prevalence and antimicrobial resistance of *Campylobacter* in broilers and turkey was performed according to Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU of the European Parliament and the Council and the Federal Zoonoses Act.

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Continue to work for harmonization of monitoring programs

Additional information

If zoonotic agents that are listed in the national Zoonoses Act are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference laboratory for typing and comparative analysis.

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

4.2.2. Campylobacteriosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

The number of *Campylobacter*-cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to the EMS as of January 26, 2017.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

Any person with at least one of the following three symptoms:

- Diarrhoea
- Abdominal pain
- Fever

Laboratory criteria

- Isolation of *Campylobacter* spp. from stool or blood
- Differentiation of *Campylobacter* spp. should be performed if possible

Case classification

Possible case

- NA

Probable case

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria and with an epidemiological link

Confirmed case

- Any person meeting the clinical and the laboratory criteria

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Stool samples are plated on selective media and incubated in microaerobic atmosphere at 37–42 °C for a minimum of 36 hours (Anonymus: Standardisierung und Qualitätssicherung in der mikrobiologischen Diagnostik. Richtlinien. Bundesministerium für Soziale Sicherheit und Generationen. ISBN 3-84123-126-0, Wien, 2001, pg. 13). *Campylobacter* is confirmed by observing the typical colony morphology and characteristic motility and morphology under the microscope. For typing and differentiation of isolates to species level biochemical and/or molecular methods as well as matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization time-of-flight mass spectrometry (MALDI-TOF) were applied. The differentiation to species level is not performed in each laboratory.

Notification system in place

Notification of campylobacteriosis according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In 2006, the number of notified human campylobacteriosis cases in Austria for the first time exceeded the number of notified salmonellosis cases. Since that year campylobacteriosis has remained the most frequently reported bacterial enteritis in humans in Austria.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2016, campylobacteriosis (n = 7,084) was the most frequently notified food borne enteric disease. It seems that the main sources of infection are chicken meat and raw milk (Feierl G. 2007. Jahresbericht 2006 der Nationalen Referenzzentrale für *Campylobacter*. Mitteilungen der Sanitätsverwaltung 4/2007).

Relevance as zoonotic disease

In 2016, campylobacteriosis remained the most frequently notified food borne disease in Austria.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via reports published by the Federal Ministry of Health and Women's Affairs (BMGF) on a monthly and yearly basis and the annual report of the National Reference Centre. The yearly report is published on the Website of the BMGF.

Table 18 Campylobacteriosis in humans - species distribution (EMS/NRL-C), 2016

Campylobacteriosis	N	Cases			
		Incidence/100,000 population	Autochtone cases	Imported cases	Unknown status

Cases	7,084	81.42	6234	609	241
<i>C. jejuni</i>	5,866	67.42	5171	494	201
<i>C. coli</i>	614	7.06	530	60	24
<i>Campylobacter</i> not specified	604	6.94	533	55	16

Data source: EMS/NRL as of January 26, 2017

Table 19 Campylobacteriosis in humans - age and gender distribution (EMS/NRL-C), 2016

age groups	<i>Campylobacter</i> spp.			<i>C. jejuni</i>			<i>C. coli</i>			<i>Campylobacter</i> not specified		
	All *	M	F	All **	M	F	All**	M	F	All	M	F
< 1 year	99	59	40	84	50	34	0	0	0	15	9	6
1 to 4 years	489	274	215	412	237	175	40	17	23	37	20	17
5 to 14 years	609	370	238	529	320	209	41	25	15	39	25	14
15 to 24 years	1,321	751	570	1,100	623	477	104	62	42	117	66	51
25 to 44 years	2,047	1,097	949	1,694	912	781	197	95	102	156	90	66
45 to 64 years	1,447	811	636	1,190	678	512	143	69	74	114	64	50
65 years and older	1,072	577	495	857	470	387	89	40	49	126	67	59
All age groups	7,084	3,939	3,143	5,866	3,290	2,575	614	308	305	604	341	263

* in 2 cases sex unknown

** in 1 case sex unknown

Table 20 Campylobacteriosis in humans - seasonal distribution (EMS/NRL-C), 2016

Month	<i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	<i>C. jejuni</i>	<i>C. coli</i>	<i>Campylobacter</i> not specified
	cases	cases	cases	cases
January	460	410	29	21
February	338	281	28	29
March	373	318	27	28
April	405	347	35	23
May	552	477	43	32
June	891	750	77	64
July	846	715	66	65
August	936	765	98	73
September	718	609	65	44
October	602	488	67	47
November	543	359	44	140
December	420	347	35	38
Total	7,084	5,866	614	604

4.2.3. *Campylobacter* spp. in foodstuffs

Monitoring system - Sampling strategy

In 2016, foodstuffs were sampled all over Austria according to the national control plan given in the ordinance „Nationaler Kontrollplan für das Jahr 2016 gem. § 31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2016“ (BMG-75500/0168-II/B/13/2015) from the Federal Ministry of Health and Women’s Affairs. This “Nationaler Kontrollplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2016-2018) according to the Art. 41ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004 and consists of several separated parts:

The inspection part (“Inspektionsteil”) determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be visited and inspected. Every food business has to be inspected regularly. The inspection comprises sampling, hygienic investigations of the establishment and the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc.

The part for sampling is comprised of scheduled (“Planproben”) and suspect samples (“Verdachtsproben”). In 2016, the part for sampling intended approximately 20,000 scheduled samples and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). This yearly part for sampling determines the number of samples for each stage (retail, processing plants, primary production) and for each food category that has to be investigated randomly. If specific suspicions (e.g. colour deviation, temperature, etc.) initiate the sampling by officials, these samples are categorised as suspect samples. Moreover any follow up sampling (e.g. due to RASFF, monitoring, positive samples, further information, etc.) is defined as suspect sample as well as food samples from private persons or sampling due to outbreak situations.

In addition there are monitoring plans, so called campaigns, for specific food items (about 55-60 individual campaigns per year). In the course of those campaigns food items of special interest are investigated for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents. In order to gain in-depth information the sampling takes place during a specified time frame. In 2016, 4 different food campaigns were conducted throughout Austria dealing with zoonotic agents. Each campaign is described in detail and results are depicted in the respective chapters per pathogen.

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling

Sampling distributed evenly throughout the year

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken

Fresh meat and meat preparations from poultry and other foodstuffs.

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Monitoring system - Definition of positive finding

Isolation of thermotolerant *Campylobacter* from the sample independent of the microbiological method (quantitative or qualitative) used.

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Bacteriological method: ISO 10272-1:2006 and 10272-2:2006. Isolates were sent to the National Reference Centre. *Campylobacter*-like colonies were differentiated into *Campylobacter jejuni* or *Campylobacter coli* with matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization time-of-flight mass spectrometry (MALDI-TOF). All other species were identified by additional biochemical and molecular methods including 16S rDNA sequencing. Pulsed field gel electrophoresis (PFGE) and whole genome sequencing (WGS) is available for outbreak detection and all isolates are stored for epidemiological investigations.

Preventive measures in place

No preventive measures in place

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place

No control program in place

Control program/mechanisms - Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Campylobacter should be added to microbiological criteria.

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

No measures foreseen.

Notification system in place

No notification system in place.

Results of the investigation

see tables

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Fresh meat from broilers has been tested at different sampling stages. At processing plants and slaughterhouses 28 samples have been tested for *Campylobacter*, with 23 positive results (18 *C. jejuni*, 5 *C. coli*). At the sampling stage retail 49 (33 *C. jejuni*, 18 *C. coli*, 1 *Campylobacter* unspecified; 3 samples with two different species) out of 85 samples have been positive for *Campylobacter* (57.6%, CI: 47-68%) in fresh broiler meat. Due to the existing dataset a slight decrease of positive fresh broiler samples (2014: 68.9%, 2015: 59.8%) is observed.

Fresh meat from turkey (at retail and catering) had a positivity rate of 28% (CI: 14-48%; 7 positive samples out of 25). In 2015, the positivity rate for fresh meat from turkey at retail and wholesale was 32%.

In total, 115 meat preparations from unspecified poultry meat (intended to be eaten cooked) have been tested with a prevalence of 47.8% (CI: 39-57%).

In one sample of "minced meat, intended to be eaten cooked" *C. jejuni* was detected at catering whereas in 56 raw milk samples from cow, sheep and goat. In 402 processed food products and prepared dishes 15 *C. jejuni* have been detected (3.8%, CI: 2-6%). Whereas in 166 other food samples of diverse food categories (meat, meat products, salad, fruits) no *Campylobacter* was found.

Additionally, 110 samples from fresh broiler meat samples from all sampling stages have been tested quantitatively (70 positive samples). In 4 samples > 1,000 CFU/g *Campylobacter* could be detected, 4 samples between 500-1,000 CFU/g, 9 between 100-500 CFU/g, 11 between 10-100 CFU/g and 42 samples counted positive but <10 CFU/g. Comparing the rate of *Campylobacter* positive samples in broiler meat >500 CFU/g and >1.000 CFU/g with the year 2015, no trend can be detected.

The 26 fresh turkey meat samples have been tested quantitatively and revealed no sample with more than 10 CFU/g, but seven positive samples were below 10 CFU/g.

Relevance of the findings in foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of human infection)

The relevance of these findings is delineated in the respective chapter for food-borne outbreaks.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Campaign A-027-16: *Campylobacter* in food – fruits and vegetables - pre-cut – single (food/feed) – at retail – surveillance – official sampling – objective sampling

Monitoring system - Sampling strategy

Random sampling was done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health and Women's Affairs. Samples are taken at retail by competent authorities.

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: June to August

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken

Fresh fruits and vegetables, precut (like all kinds of melons, strawberries, kiwi, pineapple, salads, etc.), sold fresh

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Sample weight: 25 g

Monitoring system - Definition of positive finding

Detection of *Campylobacter* in 25 g

Results of the investigation

55 samples were tested for *Campylobacter*: none positive

Additional information

Samples were also tested for *Listeria monocytogenes*, VTEC and *Salmonella*.

Table 21 Thermotolerant *Campylobacter* spp. in poultry meat, 2016

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Campylobacter</i> sp.	zoonosisTerm	<i>C. coli</i>	<i>C. jejuni</i>	<i>Campylobacter</i> sp., unspecified
Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - fresh	Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	1		0	1	0
		EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	1		0	1	0
		XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0		0	0	0
	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	22	18		2	16	0
		EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	1		1	0	0
		XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	3		1	2	0
	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	70	44		16	30	0
		EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	14	4		2	2	1
		XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	1		0	1	0
	Slaughterhouse	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	1		1	0	0
	Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	2		0	2	0
	Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0		0	0
Retail		AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	1		1	0	0
		XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	99	30		0	27	3
Meat from poultry, unspecified - fresh	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	2		0	2	0
	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	2		2	0	0
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat preparation	Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0		0	0	0
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	11	3		1	2	0
		EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0		0	0	0
	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	23	15		5	10	0
		XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	1		0	1	0
	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	74	36		15	20	1
EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0		0	0	0		
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0		0	0	0
Meat from turkey - fresh	Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	1		1	0	0

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Campylobacter</i> sp.	zoonosisTerm	<i>C. coli</i>	<i>C. jejuni</i>	<i>Campylobacter</i> sp., unspecified
Food	Processing plant	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0		0	0	0
	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	18	5		3	2	0
		EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	1		1	0	0
	Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	1		0	1	0
Meat from turkey - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	Retail	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	13	3		0	3	0

Table 22 Thermotolerant *Campylobacter* spp. in food, 2016

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Campylobacter</i> sp.	<i>C. coli</i>	<i>C. jejuni</i>	<i>Campylobacter</i> sp., unspecified
Bakery products		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0
Crustaceans		Border inspection activities	XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy products, not specified		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - fermented dairy products		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
Fishery products, unspecified - ready-to-eat		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Fruits		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0
Fruits - pre-cut	A-027-16	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	19	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
Fruits and vegetables - pre-cut	A-027-16	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0	0	0	0
Meat from bovine animals - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Meat from other animal species or not specified		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0	0	0	0
Meat from other animal species or not specified - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	1	1	0	0
Meat from pig - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat		Retail	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
Milk, cows' - raw milk		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
		Farm	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	19	0	0	0	0
Milk, cows' - raw milk - intended for direct human consumption		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	20	0	0	0	0

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Campylobacter</i> sp.	<i>C. coli</i>	<i>C. jejuni</i>	<i>Campylobacter</i> sp., unspecified
Milk, cows' - raw milk for manufacture - intended for manufacture of raw or low heat-treated products		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Milk, goats' - raw milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Milk, goats' - raw milk - intended for direct human consumption		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
Milk, sheep's - raw milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	393	15	0	15	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - sushi		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Ready-to-eat salads		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	9	0	0	0	0
Vegetables		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
Vegetables - pre-cut	A-027-16	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	23	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Vegetables - products		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0

4.2.4. *Campylobacter* spp. in animals

C. jejuni isolates from caecal samples gathered at slaughter from broilers

Monitoring system - Sampling strategy

In 2016, the monitoring for *Campylobacter* (*C.*) *jejuni* was performed according to CID 2013/652/EU. This program focused on antimicrobial resistance and not on prevalence of *C. jejuni*. A sampling plan was calculated to obtain a representative sample of 170 *C. jejuni* isolates from broiler flocks all over Austria during the whole year. Based on the average prevalence of *C. jejuni* in the previous three years (42%), 433 flocks had to be sampled to be 90% sure to obtain 170 isolates.

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling

Sampling was performed in the 4 broiler abattoirs, where >80% of all Austrian broiler flocks are slaughtered. For stratification procedures the number of slaughtered batches per abattoir 2013 and 2014 were collected (data source: Poultry Health Data, PHD). The samples were stratified proportionally by slaughterhouses in accordance with their annual throughputs. The number of samples per slaughterhouse was evenly distributed throughout the year, given as number of samples per month. According to their throughput of slaughtered flocks, 182 (abattoir A), 125 (B), 13 (C), and 113 (D) samples had to be taken in the abattoirs. The sampling plan also determined the number of slaughter batches that had to be sampled every month.

At the end of the 3rd quarter of the year the number of isolates *C. jejuni* was lower than expected. Therefore the sampling plan had to be adjusted so that during the last quarter per abattoir the double number of samples had to be taken.

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken

Intestines of 10 animals per slaughter batch.

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

The sampling was performed by officially and designated veterinarians carrying out the post-mortem inspection. At time of evisceration the whole intestines of 10 animals per slaughter batch were taken, wrapped in a sterile plastic bag and cooled down to 4°C. Using a polystyrene box with freezer bags the samples were sent to the AGES Institute of Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, Department for Veterinary Microbiology (VEMI) in Graz. In the laboratory the temperature of the content was measured, caeca of each intestinal convolute were identified and some content of each caecum pooled and cultured by direct plating onto selective medium and incubated.

Monitoring system - Case definition

A slaughter batch is considered to be infected with thermotolerant *Campylobacter* following isolation of *C. jejuni* or *C. coli* from the pooled caecal content.

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used

For the isolation of thermotolerant *Campylobacter* the ISO 10272-1:2006 was used. *Campylobacter*-like colonies were identified by observing their characteristic motility and morphology under the microscope and the production of catalase and oxidase and gram staining. Species identification was done using matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization time-of-flight mass spectrometry (MALDI-TOF). All *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* isolates were stored at -80 °C. For quality control *Campylobacter jejuni* ATCC 33560, *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922 and internal control isolates *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* were used. Data analysis was performed using Microsoft Excel 2010.

Vaccination policy

Vaccination is not performed in Austria.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Different strategies are in discussion, e.g. a quick test for identification of *Campylobacter* infected flocks at farm.

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place

None

Control program/mechanisms - Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

A *Campylobacter* platform called “*Campylobacter*—a concern to everyone” was launched in June 2012. Experts in the fields of human and veterinary medicine, food as well as representatives from industry, several authorities, poultry health service, trade organizations, etc. are assembled to ventilate on possible and plausible strategies against *Campylobacter* in the Austrian broiler production chain, including the impact of *Campylobacter* on human health in Austria.

Control program/mechanisms - Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Emphasis should be placed on education of the people for a better care in kitchen hygiene.

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

The food business operator is referred to his responsibilities according to Reg. 178/2002, Art. 19.

Notification system in place

Isolates are sent to NRL-C. Findings of *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* in animals do not need to be reported to authorities in Austria.

Results of the investigation including the origin of the positive animals

In 2016, 491 samples out of 504 that reached the lab complied with CID’s specification and were analysed for the presence of thermotolerant *Campylobacter*. In 231 samples (47%) *Campylobacter* were detected; specification of the isolates revealed 175 broiler flocks positive for *C. jejuni* (35.6%) and 56 positive for *C. coli* (11.4%).

The prevalence of thermotolerant *Campylobacter* in flocks differed in the slaughterhouses sampled: In broiler flocks sampled at two slaughterhouses (A and B) the prevalence of *Campylobacter* was between 52% and 53%, in the two other slaughterhouses (C and D) at 33%. The prevalence of *C. jejuni* varied from 44.4% of broiler flocks slaughtered in abattoir A, to 33.3% to 34.7 in abattoir B and C and 22.9% in abattoir D. Prevalence of *C. coli* also varied widely from 18.7% in flocks slaughtered at abattoir B, 7.7% to 9.9% in abattoirs A and D and 0% in abattoir C (only 9 flocks sampled).

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

About 50 % of broiler flocks in Austria are colonized with thermotolerant *Campylobacter*. Therefore kitchen hygiene at each household is of utmost importance when handling raw chicken meat and their products.

Results of the investigation - Investigations of the human contacts with positive cases

See chapter food-borne outbreaks.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

The findings of *Campylobacter* in broiler flocks is crucial for findings of the pathogens on chicken meat; especially when the first slaughter batch on a day is colonized (probability 50%) the contamination of the following batches can occur easily despite high hygiene standards in abattoirs.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the zoonosis brochure 2016.

***C. jejuni* isolates from caecal samples gathered at slaughter from fattening turkeys**

Monitoring system - Sampling strategy

In 2016, the monitoring for *Campylobacter* (*C.*) *jejuni* was performed according to CID 2013/652/EU. This program focused on antimicrobial resistance and not on prevalence of *C. jejuni*. In two national

slaughter houses > 80% of all Austrian turkey flocks are slaughtered. According to EUROSTAT, 109,000 tons (t) of turkeys were slaughtered in Austria in 2008 (no newer data available). So Austria is only a few tons above the given level in the CID that 170 isolates of *C. jejuni* have to be obtained from turkey fattening flocks for AMR-testing; it would not be realistic to obtain *C. jejuni*-isolates from 170 turkey flocks, therefore it was decided to calculate a sampling plan to obtain 85 *C. jejuni* isolates. During the DG (Sante)-audit 2016-8918 – MR in April 2016 the audit team did not approve Austria's decision. Therefore the sampling plan was adjusted and all Austrian turkey flocks slaughtered in Austria should be sampled.

Additionally a specificity of one fattening-turkeys integration was taken into account: in larger turkey holdings when male and female turkey chicks are housed in the stables at the same time they are locally separated. Therefore the male and female herds can be counted at two different epidemiological units. The slaughtering dates of female (earlier) and male (later) turkeys are one to 1.5 months apart. After learning this specificity of that integration it was decided that during the second half of the year each female and each male flock were sampled separately.

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling

Initially, 221 samples were foreseen to obtain 85 *C. jejuni*-isolates. Later the year it was decided that each flock had to be sampled.

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken

Caeca of 10 animals per slaughter batch.

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

The sampling was performed by officially and designated veterinarians carrying out the post-mortem inspection. At time of evisceration caeca of 10 animals per slaughter batch were taken, wrapped in a sterile plastic bag and cooled down to 4°C. Using a polystyrene box with freezer bags the samples were sent to the AGES Institute of Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, Department for Veterinary Microbiology (VEMI) in Graz. In the laboratory the temperature of the content was measured, caeca were identified and some content of each caecum pooled and cultured by direct plating onto selective medium and incubated.

Monitoring system - Case definition

A slaughter batch is considered to be infected with thermotolerant *Campylobacter* following isolation of *Campylobacter jejuni* or *C. coli* from the pooled caecal content.

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used

For the isolation of thermotolerant *Campylobacter* the ISO 10272-1:2006 was used. *Campylobacter*-like colonies were identified by observing their characteristic motility and morphology under the microscope and the production of catalase and oxidase and gram staining. Species identification was done using matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization time-of-flight mass spectrometry (MALDI-TOF). All *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* isolates were stored at -80 °C. For quality control *Campylobacter jejuni* ATCC 33560, *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922 and internal control isolates *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* were used. Data analysis was performed using Microsoft Excel 2010.

Vaccination policy

Vaccination is not performed in Austria.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Different strategies are in discussion, e.g. a quick test for identification of *Campylobacter* infected flocks at farm.

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place

None

Control program/mechanisms - Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

A *Campylobacter* platform called "*Campylobacter*—a concern to everyone" was launched in June 2012. Experts in the fields of human and veterinary medicine, food as well as representatives from

industry, several authorities, poultry health service, trade organizations, etc. are assembled to ventilate on possible and plausible strategies against *Campylobacter* in the Austrian broiler production chain, including the impact of *Campylobacter* on human health in Austria.

Control program/mechanisms - Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Emphasis should be placed on education of the people for a better care in kitchen hygiene.

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

The food business operator is referred to his responsibilities according to Reg. 178/2002, Art. 19.

Notification system in place

Isolates are sent to NRL-C. Findings of *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* in animals do not need to be reported to authorities in Austria.

Results of the investigation including the origin of the positive animals

In 2016, 199 samples out of 205 that reached the lab complied with CID's specification and were analysed for the presence of thermotolerant *Campylobacter*. In 102 samples (51.3%) *Campylobacter* were detected; specification of the isolates revealed 56 broiler flocks positive for *C. jejuni* (28.1%) and 46 positive for *C. coli* (23.1%).

The prevalence of thermotolerant *Campylobacter* in flocks differed in the slaughterhouses sampled: In turkey flocks sampled at slaughterhouse E the prevalence of *Campylobacter* was 65.2% and in slaughterhouse F 43.8%. The prevalence of *C. jejuni* varied widely from 39.1% of turkey flocks slaughtered in abattoir E to 22.3% in abattoir F. Prevalence of *C. coli* varied from 26.1% in flocks slaughtered at abattoir E to 21.5% in abattoir F.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

About 50 % of turkey flocks in Austria are colonized with thermotolerant *Campylobacter*. Therefore kitchen hygiene at each household is of utmost importance when handling raw turkey meat and their products.

Results of the investigation - Investigations of the human contacts with positive cases

See chapter food-borne outbreaks.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

The findings of *Campylobacter* in turkey flocks is crucial for findings of the pathogens on turkey meat; especially when the first slaughter batch on a day is colonized (probability 50%) the contamination of the following batches can occur easily despite high hygiene standards in abattoirs.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the zoonosis brochure 2016.

Table 23 Thermotolerant *Campylobacter* spp. in animals, 2016

Animal species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling Details	Source of information	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive	<i>C. jejuni</i>	<i>C. coli</i>
Broiler flocks	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - caecum - monitoring	official sampling - objective sampling	10 intestines per slaughter batch	VEMI Graz	slaughter batch	491	231	175	56
Turkeys - fattening flocks	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - caecum - monitoring	official sampling - objective sampling	10 intestines per slaughter batch	VEMI Graz	slaughter batch	199	102	56	46

4.3. Listeriosis

4.3.1. General evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Listeriosis can be regarded as a relatively rare infectious disease in Austria with an annual incidence between 0.1 and 0.25 cases per 100,000 inhabitants in the years 1996 to 2007. In 2008 a total of 31 culturally verified human cases of listeriosis were recorded for Austria (incidence 0.38 per 100,000 inhabitants), four of them were associated with pregnancy. In 2009 a further increase had to be assessed, 46 cases what corresponds to an incidence of 0.6. Two cases were associated with pregnancy. In 2010, a reduction to 34 cases could be observed and also in 2011, n = 24 (incidence of 0.29). In 2013, 36 cases in 2014, 49 cases were notified in the EMS, 47 in the NRC-L. In 2015, a slight decrease of cases was observed, 38 cases (EMS) or 37 cases (NRLC). In 2016, 46 cases were notified to the EMS. The incidences are similar to those of most other western European countries (0.2 to 0.9). In 2016, lethality was reported in 7 out of 46 cases in EMS (15 % of cases). Due to the fact that an isolate is not sent to the NRC-L for each notified case, the case numbers reported from the NRC-L may differ. EMS data correlate with the notification data of the medicating physician and the diagnosing laboratory. According to the NRC-L, isolates from 44 cases were typed (2 cases were confirmed by PCR, the 28-day lethality was 17 % (8 cases), none of the cases was pregnancy related. The high fatality rate and the sometimes severe permanent disabilities demand every effort to ascertain potential food-associated outbreaks as early as possible.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

See History of the disease.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Listeriosis is a rare disease, but not a rare bacterium, which means that a systemic disease develops only under certain particular predispositions, including pregnancy and immunosuppression. Although raw milk, soft and semi-soft cheeses, ready-to-eat meat products, and smoked salmons are likely candidates as vehicles for infections. The source of an infection often remains unclear.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

A monthly report is sent to the Ministry of Health by the National Reference Center, whereas outbreaks are reported immediately. Restrictions were tightened to sell unpasteurised milk in remote areas (Alps).

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

More widespread information for pregnant and immunocompromised persons should be provided.

Additional information

If zoonotic agents that are listed in the national Zoonoses Act are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send those strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

4.3.2. Listeriosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

The number of Listeriosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases as well notified to the EMS as typed in the NRC-L.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

Any person with at least one of the following three symptoms:

- Listeriosis of newborns defined as stillbirth or at least one of the following five in the first month of life:
 - Granulomatosis infantiseptica
 - Meningitis or meningoen­cephalitis
 - Septicaemia
 - Dyspnoea
 - Lesions on skin, mucosal membranes or conjunctivae
- Listeriosis in pregnancy defined as at least one of the following three:
 - Abortion, miscarriage, stillbirth or premature birth
 - Fever
 - Influenza-like symptoms
- Other form of listeriosis defined as at least one of the following four:
 - Fever
 - Meningitis or meningoen­cephalitis
 - Septicaemia
 - Localised infections such as arthritis, endocarditis, and abscesses

Laboratory criteria

At least one of the following two:

- Isolation of *Listeria monocytogenes* from a normally sterile site
- Isolation of *Listeria monocytogenes* from a normally non-sterile site in a foetus, stillborn, newborn or the mother at or within 24 hours of birth

Case classification

Possible case

- NA

Probable case

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria and with an epidemiological link

Confirmed case

- Any person meeting the laboratory criteria

or

- Any mother with a laboratory confirmed listeriosis infection in her foetus, stillborn or newborn

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Bacteriology: Smears of the samples are Gram stained. Specimen from normally sterile sites are inoculated in blood culture broth or thioglycollate broth and Columbia blood agar plates, vaginal swabs are plated only directly on Columbia blood and colistin-nalidixic acid (CNA) agar. *L. monocytogenes* is identified by catalase and Api *Listeria* test.

Stool samples were examined after cold enrichment in Fraser enrichment broth and streaked onto selective chromogenic agar plate and Columbia blood-agar. All isolates obtained in Austria are sent to the NRC-*Listeria* for confirmation, subtyping by PCR and PFGE and comparison.

Notification system in place

Notification of listeriosis according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

History of the disease in chapter general evaluation.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In the EMS, 46 cases of listeriosis were notified (as of Feb. 13, 2017); due to the fact that an isolate is not sent to the NRC-L for each notified case, the case numbers reported from the NRC-L may differ. EMS data correlate with the notification data of the medicating physician and the diagnosing laboratory. In the NRC-L, isolates from 44 cases were typed, although 46 cases reported (in two cases detection of *L. monocytogenes* DNA in liquor samples; as of Jan. 26, 2017).

Relevance as zoonotic disease

Listeriosis is a rare disease, but not a rare bacterium, which means that a systemic disease develops only under certain particular predispositions, including pregnancy and immunosuppression. Although dairy products and ready-to-eat meat and fish products are likely candidates as vehicles for the bacterium, the source of an infection often remains unclear.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via the monthly and yearly reports published from the BMGF. The yearly report is published on the Website of the BMGF.

Table 24 Listeriosis in humans - species/serotype distribution (EMS), 2016

Listeriosis	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population
Cases	46	0,53
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 1/2a	21	0,24
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 1/2b	2	0,02
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 1/2c	1	0,01
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 4b	19	0,22
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> not specified	3	0,03
Deaths	7	0,08
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 1/2a	2	0,02
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 4b	4	0,05
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> not specified	1	0,01
Congenital cases	0	

Data source: EMS as of Feb. 13, 2017

Table 25 Listeriosis in humans - species/serotype distribution (NRC-L), 2016

Listeriosis	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population
Cases	46	0,53
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 1/2a	22	0,25
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 1/2b	2	0,02
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 1/2c	1	0,01
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 4b	19	0,22
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> not specified	2	0,02
Deaths	8	0,09
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 1/2a	3	0,03
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 4b	4	0,05
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> not specified	1	0,01
Congenital cases	0	

Data source: NRC-L as of Jan. 26, 2017

Table 26 Listeriosis in humans - age distribution (EMS), 2016

Listeriosis	L.	L.	L.	L.	<i>L. monocytogenes</i>
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				<i>monocytogenes</i> 1,2a			<i>monocytogenes</i> 1,2b			<i>monocytogenes</i> 1/2c			<i>monocytogenes</i> 4b			not typeable/not specified		
	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F
< 1 year	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1 to 4 years	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5 to 14 years	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
15 to 24 years	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
25 to 44 years	2	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1
45 to 64 years	12	8	4	4	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	7	5	2	1	1	0
65 years and older	30	20	10	16	10	6	2	2	0	0	0	0	11	7	4	1	1	0
	46	30	16	21	12	9	2	2	0	1	1	0	19	13	6	3	2	1

Data source: EMS as of Feb. 13, 2017

4.3.3. *Listeria* spp. in foodstuffs

Monitoring system - Sampling strategy

In 2016, foodstuffs were sampled all over Austria according to the national control plan given in the ordinance „Nationaler Kontrollplan für das Jahr 2016 gem. § 31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2016“ (BMG-75500/0168-II/B/13/2015) from the Federal Ministry of Health and Women’s Affairs. This “Nationaler Kontrollplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2016-2018) according to the Art. 41ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004 and consists of several separated parts:

The inspection part (“Inspektionsteil”) determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be visited and inspected. Every food business has to be inspected regularly. The inspection comprises sampling, hygienic investigations of the establishment and the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc.

The part for sampling is comprised of scheduled (“Planproben”) and suspect samples (“Verdachtsproben”). In 2016, the part for sampling intended approximately 20,000 scheduled samples and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). This yearly part for sampling determines the number of samples for each stage (retail, processing plants, primary production) and for each food category that has to be investigated randomly. If specific suspicions (e.g. colour deviation, temperature, etc.) initiate the sampling by officials, these samples are categorised as suspect samples. Moreover any follow up sampling (e.g. due to RASFF, monitoring, positive samples, further information, etc.) is defined as suspect sample as well as food samples from private persons or sampling due to outbreak situations.

In addition there are monitoring plans, so called campaigns, for specific food items (about 55-60 individual campaigns per year). In the course of those campaigns food items of special interest are investigated for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents. In order to gain in-depth information the sampling takes place during a specified time frame. In 2016, 4 different food campaigns were conducted throughout Austria dealing with zoonotic agents. Each campaign is described in detail and results are depicted in the respective chapters per pathogen.

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling

Sampling distributed evenly throughout the year.

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken

Pasteurized and raw cows’ milk, pig meat products, bovine meat products, fishery products, smoked fish, fruits and vegetables, etc.

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Monitoring system - Definition of positive finding

Detection of *Listeria* spp. in 25 g

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Bacteriological method ISO 11290-1:2004 and ISO 11290-2:2005. For further investigations all isolates from foodstuffs are sent to the National Reference Laboratory for *Listeria* in Graz. This includes the isolates from process hygiene controls at the production plant, self-monitoring as well as all isolates from regularly testing at retail.

Preventive measures in place

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place

Control program/mechanisms - Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

All isolates from foodstuffs and process hygiene controls from any laboratories within Austria are gathered and typed at the National Reference Laboratory for *Listeria*. In a first step the species *Listeria monocytogenes* is confirmed by different selective media (e. g. Palcam agar, Ottoviani Agosti agar, Rapid L. mono agar) and/or API, matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization time of flight (MALDI TOF) is available. A serogroup-specific PCR according to Doumith et al. is performed routinely (Doumith et.al. Differentiation of the major *Listeria monocytogenes* serovars by multiplex PCR. J Clin Microbiol (2004); 51, 3819-22). Finally, typing is realized with PFGE to answer type specific questions. In the case of an outbreak the data of the outbreak strain are compared with the existing data base.

Control program/mechanisms - Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Follow-up surveillance programs; a folder was created by the AGES in cooperation with the Austrian Medical Chamber: Infections during pregnancy transmitted via food. This folder is available in German, Turkish and Serbo-Croatian (<http://www.ages.at/themen/krankheitserreger/listerien/>) and was distributed to all gynecologists. The folder contains advices to prevent food-borne infections during pregnancy, including listeriosis, toxoplasmosis, campylobacteriosis and salmonellosis as well as mycotoxicosis. Folders of hygiene guidelines on the webpage of the Federal Ministry of Health and Women's Affairs (<https://www.verbrauchergesundheit.gv.at/lebensmittel/buch/hygieneleitlinien/hytienell.html>).

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Increased awareness and information should be made available for parents, gynecologists and general practitioners in regard to food safety and the prevention of infection.

Notification system in place

Results of the investigation

See tables

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Listeria monocytogenes was not detected in samples of pasteurised cows' milk (0/10) like in the last 7 years (2010 – 2016). One out of 57 samples of raw cows' milk was found positive. In total 532 cheeses were tested and *L. monocytogenes* could be detected in 9 samples (2–times >100 cfu/g, the others below detection limit). In 5 of 17 samples from pig meat products – raw and intended to be eaten raw (1–time >100 cfu/g) and in 2 out of 37 samples (5.4 %) in fermented sausages from other animal meat products *L. monocytogenes* was qualitatively found. 4 out of 211 samples (1.9 %) of red meat products were found positive in 25 g (quantitatively 1–time <100 cfu/g, rest below detection limit). And in fermented sausages from red meat 8 out of 118 (6.8 %) were found positive, 1–time <100 cfu/g; the others below detection limit. 2.8 % of all samples from fishery products (3/106) revealed a contamination with *L. monocytogenes* (1-times <100 cfu/g), 2 out of 29 raw fish samples (6.9 %) and 1 out of 16 smoked fish samples (6.3 %) was found positive for *L. monocytogenes* below detection limit. Other processed food products and prepared dishes added

up to 855 samples of which 19 samples were found positive (2.2 %), 1-time >100 cfu/g, 2-times <100 cfu/g, the others below detection limit.

Relevance of the findings in foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of human infection)

The relevance of these findings is delineated in the chapter food-borne outbreaks.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Campaign A-027-16: *L. monocytogenes* in food – fruits and vegetables - pre-cut – single (food/feed) – at retail – surveillance – official sampling – objective sampling

Monitoring system - Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health and Women's Affairs. Samples are taken at retail by competent authorities.

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: June to August

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken

Fresh fruits and vegetables, pre-cut (like all kinds of melons, strawberries, kiwi, ananas, salads, etc), sold fresh

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Sample weight: 25 g

Monitoring system - Definition of positive finding

Detection of *Listeria* spp. in 25 g

Results of the investigation

55 samples were tested for *Listeria* spp. One sample of sugar leaf (*Cichorium intybus*) and one sample curled salad were tested positive for *L. monocytogenes*, but no sample exceeded 10 CFU/g.

Additional information

Samples were also tested for *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter* and VTEC.

Campaign A-004-16: *L. monocytogenes* in food – Foodstuffs intended for special nutritional uses - other food for infants and children – single (food/feed) – at wholesale outlets – surveillance – official sampling – objective sampling

Monitoring system - Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health and Women's Affairs. Samples are taken at wholesale outlets by competent authorities.

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: January to March

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken

Foodstuffs intended for special nutritional uses - processed cereal-based food for infants and young children (*Salmonella*) and foodstuffs intended for special nutritional uses - other food for infants and children (*Listeria*)

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Sample weight: 25 g

Monitoring system - Definition of positive finding

Detection of *L. monocytogenes* in 25 g

Results of the investigation

19 samples were tested for *L. monocytogenes*: none positive

Additional information

15 samples from foodstuffs intended for special nutritional uses - processed cereal-based food for infants and young children were tested for *Salmonella* spp.: none

Table 27 *Listeria monocytogenes* in milk and milky products, 2016

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Details	Total units tested	Total units positive for <i>L. monocytogenes</i>	Units tested with detection method	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> presence in x g	Units tested with enumeration method	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> > detection limit but < = 100 cfu/g	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> > 100 cfu/g
Cheeses made from cows' milk - fresh	Retail	AT		15	0	15	0	15	0	0
		EU		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk	Border inspection activities	XE		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Farm	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		37	0	37	0	33	0	0
	Retail	AT		5	0	5	0	4	0	0
		EU		4	0	4	0	4	0	0
		XE		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Processing plant	AT		14	0	14	0	12	0	0
	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard	Retail	AT		94	2	94	2	82	0	0
		EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard - made from pasteurised milk	Processing plant	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	Retail	AT		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
		EU		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Processing plant	AT		20	0	20	0	20	0	0
	Retail	AT		11	0	11	0	11	0	0
		EU		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
		XE		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft	Catering	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		XX		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Retail	AT		30	0	30	0	30	0	0
		EU		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk	Catering	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		31	2	31	2	30	0	0
	Retail	AT		25	0	25	0	21	0	0
		EU		31	0	31	0	31	0	0
		XE		1	0	1	0	1	0	0

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Details	Total units tested	Total units positive for <i>L. monocytogenes</i>	Units tested with detection method	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> presence in x g	Units tested with enumeration method	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> > detection limit but < = 100 cfu/g	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> >100 cfu/g
		XX		5	0	5	0	5	0	0
	Wholesale	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		EU		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Processing plant	AT		47	5	47	5	47	0	2
	Retail	AT		12	0	12	0	12	0	0
		EU		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - unspecified	Processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Wholesale	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - unspecified - made from pasteurised milk	Catering	XX		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk	Retail	AT		5	0	5	0	5	0	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk	Processing plant	AT		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Processing plant	AT		9	0	9	0	9	0	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk	Processing plant	AT		4	0	4	0	3	0	0
	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		EU		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Processing plant	AT		6	0	6	0	6	0	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk	Processing plant	AT		8	0	8	0	8	0	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Processing plant	AT		12	0	12	0	10	0	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - hard - made from pasteurised milk	Processing plant	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	Retail	EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - soft and semi-soft	Catering	EU		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk	Catering	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		4	0	4	0	4	0	0
	Retail	AT		6	0	6	0	6	0	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Processing plant	AT		6	0	6	0	6	0	0
	Retail	EU		2	0	2	0	2	0	0

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Details	Total units tested	Total units positive for <i>L. monocytogenes</i>	Units tested with detection method	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> presence in x g	Units tested with enumeration method	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> > detection limit but < = 100 cfu/g	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> > 100 cfu/g
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - fresh - made from pasteurised milk	Processing plant	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	Retail	EU		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Processing plant	AT		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		EU		4	0	4	0	4	0	0
	Wholesale	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk	Processing plant	AT		20	0	20	0	20	0	0
	Retail	AT		4	0	4	0	4	0	0
		XE		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk	Processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Retail	EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk	Retail	EU		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses)	Catering	AT		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		12	0	12	0	12	0	0
	Retail	AT		9	0	9	0	9	0	0
		EU		9	0	9	0	9	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - butter	Catering	AT		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		30	0	30	0	30	0	0
	Retail	AT		4	0	4	0	4	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - butter - made from pasteurised milk	Retail	AT		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - buttermilk	Processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
	Retail	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - cream	Retail	AT		4	0	4	0	4	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - cream - made from pasteurised	Processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Details	Total units tested	Total units positive for <i>L. monocytogenes</i>	Units tested with detection method	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> presence in x g	Units tested with enumeration method	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> > detection limit but < = 100 cfu/g	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> >100 cfu/g
milk										
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy desserts - chilled	Processing plant	AT		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy products, not specified	Border inspection activities	XE		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Catering	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
		EU		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		46	0	46	0	46	0	0
	Retail	AT		20	0	20	0	20	0	0
		EU		4	0	4	0	4	0	0
	XX		1	0	1	0	1	0	0	
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy products, not specified - ready-to-eat - made from pasteurised milk	Retail	EU		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - fermented dairy products	Catering	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		58	0	58	0	56	0	0
	Retail	AT		22	0	22	0	22	0	0
		EU		4	0	4	0	4	0	0
	Wholesale	EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - ice-cream	Catering	AT		40	0	40	0	3	0	0
		EU		4	0	4	0	1	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		47	0	47	0	17	0	0
	Retail	AT		51	0	51	0	38	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - ice-cream - made from pasteurised milk	Catering	AT		3	0	3	0	0	0	0
		EU		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
	Conservation Facilities	XX		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		4	0	4	0	0	0	0
	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - yoghurt	Processing plant	AT		7	0	7	0	0	0	0
	Retail	AT		21	0	21	0	19	0	0
		EU		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Milk, cows' - pasteurised milk	Processing plant	AT		9	0	9	0	6	0	0
	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Details	Total units tested	Total units positive for <i>L. monocytogenes</i>	Units tested with detection method	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> presence in x g	Units tested with enumeration method	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> > detection limit but < = 100 cfu/g	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> >100 cfu/g
Milk, cows' - raw milk	Catering	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	Farm	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		8	0	8	0	6	0	0
	Retail	AT		19	1	19	1	12	0	0
Milk, cows' - raw milk - intended for direct human consumption	Retail	XX		22	0	22	0	22	0	0
Milk, cows' - raw milk for manufacture - intended for manufacture of raw or low heat-treated products	Processing plant	AT		3	0	3	0	2	0	0
	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Milk, goats' - raw milk	Processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Milk, goats' - raw milk - intended for direct human consumption	Retail	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Milk, sheep's - raw milk	Processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0

Table 28 *Listeria monocytogenes* in other foods, 2016

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Details	Total units tested	Total units positive for <i>L.monocytogenes</i>	Units tested with detection method	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> presence in x g	Units tested with enumeration method	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> > detection limit but < = 100 cfu/g	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> >100 cfu/g
Bakery products	Catering	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		25	0	25	0	25	0	0
	Retail	AT		5	0	5	0	5	0	0
EU			3	0	3	0	3	0	0	
Bakery products - bread	Retail	AT		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
Bakery products - cakes	Catering	AT		5	0	5	0	5	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		15	0	15	0	12	0	0
	Retail	AT		30	0	30	0	30	0	0
Bakery products - desserts - containing raw cream	Processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Bakery products - pastry	Catering	AT		17	0	17	0	17	0	0
		EU		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		13	1	13	1	12	0	0
		AT		72	0	72	0	71	0	0
	Retail	EU		8	0	8	0	8	0	0
		Wholesale	XX		1	0	1	0	1	0
Cocoa and cocoa preparations, coffee and tea	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Coconut - coconut products	Processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Crustaceans	Border inspection activities	XE		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Egg products - dried	Processing plant	AT		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
Egg products - liquid	Processing plant	AT		13	0	13	0	13	0	0
		EU		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	Wholesale	EU		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Fish - Fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine - not enzyme matured	Catering	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Fish - gravad /slightly salted	Retail	EU		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Fish - raw	Catering	AT		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
		XX		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Retail	AT		14	1	14	1	13	0	0
		EU		5	0	5	0	5	0	0
		XE		1	0	1	0	1	0	0

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Details	Total units tested	Total units positive for <i>L. monocytogenes</i>	Units tested with detection method	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> presence in x g	Units tested with enumeration method	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> > detection limit but < = 100 cfu/g	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> >100 cfu/g
Food	Wholesale	XX		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		XE		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		XX		3	1	3	1	2	0	0
Fish - smoked	Retail	EU		3	1	3	1	3	0	0
		XE		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Wholesale	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Fish - smoked - cold-smoked	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		EU		7	0	7	0	7	0	0
	Wholesale	EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
XE			2	0	2	0	2	0	0	
Fishery products, unspecified	Catering	AT		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		19	1	19	1	19	0	0
		AT		48	1	48	1	47	1	0
	Retail	EU		25	1	25	1	25	0	0
		XE		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
		XX		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	Wholesale	AT		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
		EU		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
		XE		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Fishery products, unspecified - ready-to-eat	Catering	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
		AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
	Processing plant	EU		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
		XE		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
		EU		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
Fishery products, unspecified - seafood pâté	Processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
		AT		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
	Retail	EU		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Foodstuffs intended for special nutritional uses - other food for infants and children	Wholesale	AT	A-004-16	7	0	7	0	7	0	0
		EU	A-004-16	11	0	11	0	11	0	0
		XX	A-004-16	1	0	1	0	1	0	0

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Details	Total units tested	Total units positive for <i>L. monocytogenes</i>	Units tested with detection method	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> presence in x g	Units tested with enumeration method	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> > detection limit but < = 100 cfu/g	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> >100 cfu/g
Foodstuffs intended for special nutritional uses - ready-to-eat	Retail	EU		3	0	3	0	0	0	0
Fruits	Farm	AT		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
	Retail	AT		9	0	9	0	9	0	0
		EU		8	0	8	0	8	0	0
		XE		11	0	11	0	11	0	0
		XX		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	Wholesale	AT		4	0	4	0	4	0	0
		EU		4	0	4	0	4	0	0
XE			1	0	1	0	1	0	0	
Fruits - non-pre-cut - frozen	Retail	XE		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Fruits - pre-cut	Retail	AT	A-027-16	19	0	19	0	19	0	0
		EU	A-027-16	1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		XX	A-027-16	2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Fruits - products	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		XE		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Fruits and vegetables - pre-cut	Retail	AT	A-027-16	7	0	7	0	3	0	0
Infant formula - dried	Retail	EU		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Meat from bovine animals - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	Catering	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products - fermented sausages	Processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Catering	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Game handling establishment	AT		4	1	4	1	4	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		5	0	5	0	5	0	0
	Retail	AT		12	0	12	0	12	0	0
		EU		8	1	8	1	8	0	0
Wholesale	AT		7	0	7	0	7	0	0	
Meat from pig - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	Processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Meat from pig - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	Catering	AT		3	1	3	1	2	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		6	0	6	0	1	0	0
	Retail	AT		5	0	5	0	1	0	0
Meat from pig - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	Processing plant	AT		14	5	14	5	5	0	1
	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
		EU		2	0	2	0	0	0	0

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Details	Total units tested	Total units positive for <i>L. monocytogenes</i>	Units tested with detection method	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> presence in x g	Units tested with enumeration method	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> > detection limit but < = 100 cfu/g	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> >100 cfu/g
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		4	0	4	0	4	0	0
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	Retail	AT		16	0	16	0	16	0	0
		EU		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - unspecified, ready-to-eat	Processing plant	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	Retail	AT		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
Meat from turkey - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	Catering	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Meat from turkey - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Meat from wild boar - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	Wholesale	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Meat, mixed meat - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - sliced	Catering	AT		2	1	2	1	1	0	0
Meat, mixed meat - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked	Processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Catering	AT		7	0	7	0	7	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		30	0	30	0	30	0	0
	Retail	AT		47	1	47	1	47	1	0
		EU		5	0	5	0	5	0	0
		XX		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	Wholesale	AT		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
EU			1	0	1	0	1	0	0	
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	Catering	AT		13	0	13	0	13	0	0
	Game handling establishment	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		35	1	35	1	35	0	0
	Retail	AT		60	2	60	2	59	0	0
		EU		5	0	5	0	5	0	0
Wholesale	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0	
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages	Processing plant	AT		19	3	19	3	19	0	0
		EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		XX		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Retail	AT		71	5	71	5	71	1	0
		EU		22	0	22	0	22	0	0
	Slaughterhouse	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	Wholesale	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Details	Total units tested	Total units positive for <i>L. monocytogenes</i>	Units tested with detection method	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> presence in x g	Units tested with enumeration method	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> > detection limit but < = 100 cfu/g	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> >100 cfu/g
		EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - pâté	Processing plant	AT		4	0	4	0	4	0	0
	Retail	AT		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
		EU		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Molluscan shellfish - raw - chilled	Catering	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Mushrooms	Catering	XX		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Other food of non-animal origin	Processing plant	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes	Catering	AT		41	0	27	0	25	0	0
		EU		2	0	0	0	2	0	0
		XX		2	0	2	0	1	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		56	0	56	0	13	0	0
	Retail	AT		150	1	126	1	73	0	0
		EU		36	1	36	1	6	0	0
		XE		5	0	5	0	0	0	0
		XX		551	16	551	13	132	2	1
	Wholesale	AT		9	0	9	0	1	0	0
		EU		3	1	3	1	1	0	0
	Other processed food products and prepared dishes - noodles	Processing plant	AT		4	0	4	0	0	0
Retail		EU		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - pasta	Retail	XE		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - sandwiches	Retail	AT		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - sushi	Catering	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
	Catering	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
		Processing plant	AT		8	0	8	0	2	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		EU		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
	Retail	EU		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - vegetarian pâté	Retail	EU		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
	Catering	AT		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		17	0	17	0	0	0	0
Ready-to-eat salads	Retail	AT		31	2	31	2	14	0	0
		EU		3	0	3	0	2	0	0
	Retail	AT		3	0	3	0	0	0	0
Ready-to-eat salads - containing mayonnaise	Retail	AT		3	0	3	0	0	0	0

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Details	Total units tested	Total units positive for <i>L. monocytogenes</i>	Units tested with detection method	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> presence in x g	Units tested with enumeration method	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> > detection limit but < = 100 cfu/g	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> >100 cfu/g
Sauce and dressings	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
		EU		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
Sauce and dressings - mayonnaise	Processing plant	AT		9	0	9	0	3	0	0
	Retail	EU		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
		XX		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Seeds, sprouted - ready-to-eat	Farm	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Spices and herbs	Processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Sweets	Catering	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
	Retail	EU		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
Vegetables	Catering	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		12	0	12	0	12	0	0
	Retail	AT		9	0	9	0	9	0	0
		EU		4	0	4	0	4	0	0
Wholesale	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0	
Vegetables - pre-cut	Processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
	Retail	AT	A-027-16	23	2	23	2	23	2	0
		EU	A-027-16	2	0	2	0	2	0	0
		XX	A-027-16	1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Vegetables - products	Catering	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
		EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
	Retail	AT		5	0	5	0	5	0	0
		EU		3	0	3	0	3	0	0

4.4. Verotoxic *Escherichia coli*

4.4.1. General evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In 2016, the number of human VTEC cases notified to EMS reached a new maximum of 177 cases (2.03 cases per 100,000 population) (EMS/NRL-VTEC as of January 19, 2017). That increase of cases is not due to an outbreak but due to the effect that the reimbursement for laboratory analysis of VTEC of suspected human samples has been modified; so more samples were analysed and also found positive for VTEC. The average incidence during the last five years (2011-2015) has been lower at 1.55 cases per 100,000 population.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

See History of the disease. The number of VTEC cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to the EMS and typed in the NRL-VTEC.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

In 2016, the monitoring of VTEC in animals has been ceased due to the high costs of the monitoring and lack of EU-co-financing.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

The Austrian wide monitoring program on the trends of VTEC prevalence in bovine animals and sheep was stopped after 11 years in 2015.

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Increased awareness and information should be made available for parents, pediatricians and general practitioners in regard to food safety and the prevention of infection.

Additional information

If zoonotic agents that are listed in the national Zoonoses Act, are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

4.4.2. Verocytotoxic *Escherichia coli* in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

The number of VTEC cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to the EMS and typed in the NRL-VTEC (the isolate of one case was not typed and confirmed in the NRL-VTEC).

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

STEC/VTEC diarrhoea

Any person with at least one of the following two symptoms:

- Diarrhoea
- Abdominal pain

HUS

Any person with acute renal failure and at least one of the following two:

- Microangiopathic haemolytic anaemia
- Thrombocytopenia

Laboratory criteria

At least one of the following three:

- Isolation of Shigatoxin/Verotoxin (STEC/VTEC) producing *E. coli*

- Detection of *vtx1* or *vtx2* gene(s) nucleic acid
- Detection of free shigatoxins.

Only for HUS the following can be used as laboratory criterion to confirm STEC/VTEC:

- *E. coli* serogroups specific antibody response

Isolation and additional characterisation by serotype, *eae* genes, and subtypes of *stx1/stx2* should be performed if possible

Case classification

Possible case of STEC-associated HUS

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria for HUS

Probable case of STEC/VTEC

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria and with an epidemiological link or a laboratory confirmed case without clinical criteria

Confirmed case of STEC/VTEC

- Any person meeting the clinical and the laboratory criteria

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

1. Detection of *E. coli* O157 (most prominent serotype in HUS cases):

- Bacteriology: Isolation of O157 colonies on Sorbitol-MacConkey agar (or CT-Sorbitol-MacConkey agar) after incubation for 24 hours at 37 °C (or 41°C). O157 is confirmed via the *E. coli* O157 Latex Test.

- Serology: This method is constantly used at the German HUS-"Konsiliarlabor"; anti-O157 antibodies of IgG and IgM types can be distinguished.

2. Detection of Verotoxin (VTEC)-producing strains (used at the National Reference Laboratory/Center for EHEC/VTEC/STEC): Stools are enriched overnight in a medium containing mitomycin C (EHEC Direct Medium, Heipha, Heidelberg, Germany). Enriched cultures are plated on selective agar (CT-Sorbitol-MacConkey, Enterohemolysin, and Sorbitol-MacConkey). After incubation for 18-24 hours at 37°C a representative mixture of the viable cells were subjected to PCR reactions analyzing *stx1*, *stx2*, *eae* and *Ehly* (Reischl et al. (2002), Journal of Clinical Microbiology, p. 2555-2565). Isolates are gained via colony picking and pathotyped with the same PCR scheme. Isolate identification is further confirmed by conventional biochemical tests (VITEK or Api 20E, bioMerieux, Marcy-l'Étoile, France).

All EHEC/STEC/VTEC isolates obtained in Austria are to be sent to the National Reference Laboratory for confirmation, subtyping and comparison. All Shiga toxin producing *E. coli* are serotyped with *E. coli* antisera (*E. coli* antisera, Statens Serum Institut, Copenhagen, Denmark). Comparison of the isolates is done by Pulsed-Field-Gel-Electrophoresis.

Notification system in place

Notification of VTEC according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

See History of the disease

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2016, the number of human VETC cases notified to EMS reached a new maximum of 177 cases (2.03 cases per 100,000 population) (EMS/NRL-VTEC as of January 19, 2017). That increase of cases is not due to an outbreak but due to the effect that the costs for laboratory analysis of VTEC of suspected human samples has been covered by another province (Bundesland) and more samples were analysed and also found positive for VTEC. The average incidence during the last five years (2011-2015) has been lower at 1.55 cases per 100,000 population.

Relevance as a zoonotic disease

HUS is a rare complication of *E. coli* infection; however EHEC's themselves are not rare, which means that a systemic disease develops only under certain particular predispositions, most of which are currently unknown. Although raw or undercooked meat and unpasteurised dairy products are

likely candidates to transfer the bacterium to humans, the actual source of infection often remains unclear. The importance of hand hygiene after animal contact should be always considered.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via the monthly and yearly reports published from the Federal Ministry for Austria. The yearly report is published on the Website of the BMGF.

Table 29 Verocytotoxic *Escherichia coli* infections in humans - species/serotype distribution (EMS/NRL-VTEC), 2016

	cases	incidence/100,000 population	autochthonous cases	imported cases
HUS	14	0,16	13	1
- caused by O157 (VT+)	2	0,02	2	0
- caused by other VTEC	5	0,06	5	0
- unknown serovar (no isolate obtained)	7	0,08	6	1
VTEC infection (except HUS)	163	1,87	146	17
- caused by O157 (VT+)	23	0,26	21	2
- caused by other VTEC	82	0,94	77	5
- unknown serovar (no isolate obtained)	58	0,67	48	10
VTEC total	177	2,03	159	18

Data source: EMS/NRL-VTEC as of January 19, 2017

Table 30 Verocytotoxic *Escherichia coli* infections in humans - age distribution (EMS/NRL-VTEC), 2015

age groups	all VTEC infections			VTEC infections caused by O157			VTEC infections caused by other serotypes			HUS, caused by O157			HUS, other serotypes		
	all	m	f	all	m	f	all	m	f	all	m	f	all	m	f
< 1 year	13	7	6	1		1	12	7	5	0	0	0	0	0	0
1 to 4 years	53	29	24	12	6	6	41	23	18	1	0	1	5	3	2
5 to 14 years	11	5	6	3	1	2	8	4	4	0	0	0	1		1
15 to 24 years	24	13	11	1	1		23	12	11	0	0	0	0	0	0
25 to 44 years	28	13	15	2		2	26	13	13	0	0	0	2	1	1
45 to 64 years	27	9	18	2		2	25	9	16	0	0	0	1		1
65 years and older	21	7	14	4	1	3	17	6	11	1	0	1	3	1	2
Gesamtergebnis	177	83	94	25	9	16	152	74	78	2	0	2	12	5	7

Data source: EMS/NRL-VTEC as of January 19, 2017

4.4.3. Pathogenic *Escherichia coli* in foodstuffs

Monitoring system - Sampling strategy

In 2016, foodstuffs were sampled all over Austria according to the national control plan given in the ordinance „Nationaler Kontrollplan für das Jahr 2016 gem. § 31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2016“ (BMG-75500/0168-II/B/13/2015) from the Federal Ministry of Health and Women’s Affairs. This “Nationaler Kontrollplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2016-2018) according to the Art. 41ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004 and consists of several separated parts:

The inspection part (“Inspektionsteil”) determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be visited and inspected. Every food business has to be

inspected regularly. The inspection comprises sampling, hygienic investigations of the establishment and the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc. The part for sampling is comprised of scheduled (“Planproben”) and suspect samples (“Verdachtsproben”). In 2016, the part for sampling intended approximately 20,000 scheduled samples and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). This yearly part for sampling determines the number of samples for each stage (retail, processing plants, primary production) and for each food category that has to be investigated randomly. If specific suspicions (e.g. colour deviation, temperature, etc.) initiate the sampling by officials, these samples are categorised as suspect samples. Moreover any follow up sampling (e.g. due to RASFF, monitoring, positive samples, further information, etc.) is defined as suspect sample as well as food samples from private persons or sampling due to outbreak situations. In addition there are monitoring plans, so called campaigns, for specific food items (about 55-60 individual campaigns per year). In the course of those campaigns food items of special interest are investigated for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents. In order to gain in-depth information the sampling takes place during a specified time frame. In 2016, 4 different food campaigns were conducted throughout Austria dealing with zoonotic agents. Each campaign is described in detail and results are depicted in the respective chapters per pathogen.

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling

Sampling distributed evenly throughout the year

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken

Fresh meat, meat preparations, fruits, vegetables etc.

Monitoring system - Definition of positive finding

Detection of *stx1*- and/or *stx2*-positive *E. coli*.

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used

The sample is analyzed according to ISO/TS 13136. There is no further testing for negative PCR results in the bacterial enrichment. If the bacterial enrichment is PCR-positive, it is streaked on to solid media. At least 50 colonies are tested for the presence of *stx1* and/or *stx2*. The Shigatoxin producing *E. coli* is sent to the National Reference Center for *Escherichia coli* including verotoxin producing *E. coli* (VTEC) in Graz where the presence of the *stx*-genes, *eae*-genes and additional virulence factors is tested by PCR. Subsequently the VTEC is serotyped conventionally (antisera).

Preventive measures in place

No preventive measures in place

Control program/mechanisms - Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

No actions taken.

Control program/mechanisms - Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Harmonization of methods with regard to all possible VTEC serotypes.

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

All isolates detected in food have to be sent to the National Reference Centre for *Escherichia coli* including verotoxin producing *E. coli* in Graz, where the isolates are further analysed and stored.

Notification system in place

Results of the investigation

see tables

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2016, in total 1,346 samples were tested for VTEC, 722 samples of animal origin, 132 samples of non-animal origin and 492 samples of other processed food products and prepared dishes. In total 49 samples were positive for VTEC. Three (one raw milk cheese, and two samples of raw milk) out of

199 (1.5%, CI:1-4%) samples from milk, milk products and cheeses (all from cow's, sheep's or goat's milk) were positive for VTEC. No positive findings were made from dairy products or any other milk. No VTEC has been detected in raw milk at retail in 2016.

162 samples of fresh meat of several animals (bovine animals, deer, pig, rabbit, sheep, wild boar) were tested for VTEC resulting in 12 positive samples (7.5%, CI:4-13%), which is the similar prevalence as in 2015 (7.24%). The highest prevalence of VTEC was detected in fresh meat from venison in 21.2% (CI:11-38%, 7 out of 33 samples), comparable to 2014 (35.1% positivity rate in fresh meat samples from venison). No VTEC was detected in fresh sheep meat (4 tested samples).

277 samples of meat products and meat preparations (35) of several animals were tested for VTEC showing 6 positive samples (2.2%, CI:1-5%), which is lower than in 2015 (4.2%, CI:3-7%). All vegetables, fruits, herbs (124 samples tested) were negative for VTEC.

Ten of the 49 typed VTEC from food samples belong to the group of serotypes that cause more often disease in humans: Six isolates of VTEC O146 (4-times fresh meat from wild animals, and once each from unspecified fresh meat and processed food), and once each VTEC O26 (raw milk), VTEC O91 (processed food) VTEC O103 (fermented sausage), and VTEC O113 (fresh goat meat). VTEC O157 was not identified in the tested food samples. Two VTEC-isolates harbored the gene for the virulence factor intimin (VTEC O26 and VTEC O103).

Relevance of the findings in foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of human infection)

The relevance of these findings is delineated in the chapter food-borne outbreaks.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Campaign A-027-16: VTEC in food – fruits and vegetables - pre-cut – single (food/feed) – at retail – surveillance – official sampling – objective sampling

Monitoring system - Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health and Women's Affairs. Samples are taken at retail by competent authorities.

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: June to August

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken

Fresh fruits and vegetables, precut (like all kinds of melons, strawberries, kiwi, pineapple, salads, etc.), sold fresh

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Sample weight: 25 g

Monitoring system - Definition of positive finding

Detection of VTEC in 25 g

Results of the investigation

55 samples were tested for VTEC: none positive

Additional information

Samples were also tested for *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Campylobacter* and *Salmonella*.

4.4.4. Pathogenic *Escherichia coli* in animals

A. Verotoxigenic *Escherichia coli* in cattle (bovine animals)

No program in 2016.

B. Verotoxigenic *E. coli* (VTEC) in animal – Sheep

No program in 2016.

4.5. Tuberculosis

4.5.1. General evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Human tuberculosis has steadily declined during the last decades. Commission Decision 1999/467/EC of 15 July 1999 declared bovine herds of Austria officially tuberculosis-free. In humans the number of tuberculosis cases is decreasing. Cases of *M. bovis* or *M. caprae* are very seldom and reactivations of past infections. In 2016, in humans three *M. caprae* and one *M. bovis* case were confirmed. The *M. caprae* cases did not show the same molecular typing patterns as the *M. caprae* isolated from wild red deer and cattle.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Bovine tuberculosis poses no public health problem in Austria. Sheep, goats and pigs are free of bovine tuberculosis. In 2008 the first case of *M. caprae* in a bovine animal was detected in the federal province of Tyrol. Since this time several studies carried out in the period of 2008 to 2013 and surveillance data show, that *M. caprae* is endemic in wild red deer in single areas (hot spots) of the both federal provinces Tyrol and Vorarlberg. The spill over from red deer to pastured cattle during transhumance season is known. Therefore, after transhumance season, cattle of these regions are tested every year. Since then, every year a few bovines have been identified to be infected with *M. caprae*. In 2016, 37 bovines out of 17 herds were diagnosed with *M. caprae*.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

No findings of *M. bovis* in animals, although *M. caprae* was detected. In 2016, isolates from humans showed different molecular patterns as the bovine and deer isolates.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

In 2011 the Regulation on TB in red deer (Rotwild-TBC-Verordnung, BGBl. II Nr. 181/2011) has been implemented to control *M. caprae* in red deer.

Bovines and goats kept together with bovines shall be tested (using simultaneously bovine and avium tuberculin) for TB in defined areas of risk (where TB in wild red deer is known) according to the Regulation on TB in cattle (Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BGBl II Nr. 322/2008) and according to the epidemiological situation.

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Continuation of the existing control programs

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

4.5.2. Tuberculosis in humans

A. Tuberculosis due to *Mycobacterium bovis* in humans

Case definition

Definite: A case with isolation of *M. tuberculosis* complex (except *M. bovis* BCG) from any clinical specimen.

Other than definite: A case that meets the clinical criteria above but does not meet the laboratory criteria of a definite case.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

- Definite: Staining: Ziehl-Neelsen, Auramin-Rhodamin stains are performed on histological preparation and smears of the sample material
- Culture: After decontamination of the homogenised sample material in NALC-NaOH and centrifugation, the sample material is transferred in parallel on Loewenstein-Jensen agar containing glycerol and PACT and Stonebrink agar containing PACT and MGITmedium. The media are incubated at 37 °C for up to 8 weeks. Confirmation of the species by Amplicor (Roche)
- Other than definite: A skin test and an X-Ray of the thorax are performed.

Notification system in place

The person who diagnoses (laboratory/hospital/general practitioner) has to notify definite (*M. tuberculosis* and *M. bovis*) and other than definite cases (this excludes radiologists) to the local health authority (Federal Law BGBl. 127/1968: Tuberkulosegesetz, as amended; Epidemiegesetz 1950, as amended). *M. bovis* is notifiable since 2004 (National Regulation BGBl. Nr. 254/2004: Anzeigepflichtige übertragbare Krankheiten 2004).

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

The National Reference Center for tuberculosis (NRC-T) has been nominated since 1995. Since 1998 all data are compiled in a national database.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

One case of *M. bovis* and three cases of *M. caprae* were identified in 2016; the *M. caprae* isolates from humans showed different molecular typing results as the *M. caprae* isolated from animals in Western Austria and also no epidemiological links could be found.

Relevance as zoonotic disease

For each case esp. of *M. caprae* the infectious source has to be investigated.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure and the annual report of the National Reference Center for tuberculosis.

Table 32 Tuberculosis in humans - species/serotype distribution, 2016

	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population	cases with place of birth Austria	cases with place of birth other than Austria
Tuberculosis, total number of registered cases	635	7,30		
Tuberculosis, cases culture confirmed	474	5,45	153	321
<i>M. bovis</i>	1	0,01	1	0
<i>M. tuberculosis</i>	431	4,95	140	291
<i>M. caprae</i>	3	0,03	2	1
<i>M. tuberculosis</i> complex (not differentiated)	34	0,39	10	24
<i>M. africanum</i>	5	0,06	0	5

Data source: national surveillance data (as of April 27, 2017)

Table 33 Tuberculosis in humans - age distribution, 2016

Age group	TB due to <i>M. tuberculosis</i>			Tuberculosis due to <i>M. bovis</i>			Tuberculosis due to <i>M. caprae</i>			Tuberculosis due to MTC (not differentiated)		
	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F
< 1 year	4	1	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1 to 4 years	6	5	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5 to 14 years	5	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	2	1
15 to 24 years	96	72	24	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	9	1
25 to 44 years	139	85	54	0	0	0	1	0	1	8	7	1
45 to 64 years	100	75	25	0	0	0	0	0	0	7	3	4
65 years and older	81	47	34	1	0	1	2	2	0	6	2	4
Age unknown	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
All age groups	431	290	141	1	0	1	3	2	1	34	23	11

Data source: national surveillance data (as of April 27, 2017)

4.5.3. *Mycobacterium* spp. in animals

A. *Mycobacterium bovis* in bovine animals

Status as officially free of bovine tuberculosis during the reporting year - The entire country free

Yes

Status as officially free of bovine tuberculosis during the reporting year - Free regions

All regions

Status as officially free of bovine tuberculosis during the reporting year - Additional information

According to Council Directive 64/432/EEC from June 26, 1964, Austria has the status Officially Tuberculosis Free (OTF) Member State declared in the Commission Decision 1999/467/EC from July 15th, 1999, replaced by Commission Decision 2003/467/EC from June 23rd, 2003. Therefore, as of May 2000 the nationwide intradermal testing has been suspended and the disease is now monitored as a part of ante- and post mortem inspection of all bovine animals and goats (which were kept together with bovines) slaughtered.

According to the national Regulation the "Rindertuberkuloseverordnung" (BGBl. II no. 322/2008) all Mycobacteria belonging to the *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex (MTC) are compulsory notifiable. The "Rindertuberkuloseverordnung" shall apply to bovine animals and to goats, which are kept together with bovine animals.

Monitoring system - Sampling strategy

According to the monitoring system of ante and post mortem inspection of slaughtered animals, samples are taken from carcasses which show pathological-anatomical alterations, characteristic for tuberculosis at slaughterhouse. Laboratory examination and diagnosis is done by the national reference laboratory for tuberculosis in animals (AGES Mödling).

The BMGF orders annual testing of cattle and goats kept together with bovines in specific risk areas (where TB in wild red deer is known; special testing zones and special monitoring zones according to §1 (4) and (5) of Rindertuberkuloseverordnung ,BGBl. II no. 322/2008 applying the simultaneous intradermal tuberculin test) of the provinces Tyrol and Vorarlberg after the end of transhumance season, subsequently to the detection of *M. caprae* positive cases in wild red deer.

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling

After official announcement census testing carried out in specific risk areas including all animals older than 6 months (cattle and goats kept together with bovines) applying the simultaneous intradermal tuberculin test.

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken

Organs/tissues: Sampling is carried out according to Annex 4 of the Rindertuberkuloseverordnung.

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

The alterations and lymph nodes are excised and sent to the national reference laboratory for tuberculosis in animals (AGES Mödling).

Monitoring system - Case definition

According to Rindertuberkuloseverordnung tuberculosis is defined as an infection with Mycobacteria of the *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex.

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Live bovine animals and goats: Intradermal testing (simultaneous testing using bovine and avium tuberculin): The test is performed according to Council Directive 64/432/EEC of 26 June 1964 and the national Rindertuberkuloseverordnung (BGBl. II no.322/2008). A reactor is an animal which is not negative (either doubtful or positive) to intradermal testing.

Staining: Ziehl-Neelsen stains are performed on histological preparation and smears of the sample material.

Culture is performed in the AGES National Reference Laboratory for tuberculosis in animals in Mödling After decontamination of the homogenized sample material (2g, homogenized, add 10 ml buffer) in NALC-NaOH 1% (25 min), neutralization (Sörensen Buffer sol.) and centrifugation (3500g, 20 min), the sample material is transferred on commercial media (BD - Becton Dickinson: Loewenstein-Jensen agar containing antibiotics (PACT) and Stonebrink agar containing pyruvate and PACT). The media are incubated at 37° C +/-1° C up to 12 weeks. MTC species are identified with the GenoType MTBC assay (Hain Lifescience GmbH, Nehren, Germany). Identification of Mycobacteria species and genotyping of isolates is undertaken using molecular biological methods, such as polymerase chain reaction (PCR), DNA-striptechnology, restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP), spoligotyping and MIRU-VNTR (mycobacterial interspersed repetitive unit variable number tandem repeat) analysis.

Vaccination policy

Vaccination is prohibited in Austria.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Subsequent to the detection of *M. caprae* positive wild red deer in specific areas of the provinces Tyrol and Vorarlberg the BMGF has ordered annual testing of cattle and goats kept together with bovines in specific risk areas (special testing zones and special monitoring zones according to §1 (4) and (5) of Rindertuberkuloseverordnung (BGBl. II no. 322/2008) applying the simultaneous intradermal tuberculin test.

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place

According to Rindertuberkuloseverordnung (BGBl. II no. 322/2008) all live animals suspected being infected shall be killed for diagnostic purposes. All animals of the holding of origin of such animals must be tested immediately (simultaneous intradermal test) and epidemiologic investigations must be carried out. The status of disease freedom of the holding which is suspected of being infected is suspended and subsequently withdrawn in case of confirmation of the disease. The holding is banned immediately after suspicion. Milk from such holdings shall be used for human consumption only according to the specifications laid down in Annex III, Section IX, Chapter I of the Regulation EC No 853/2004 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 29 April 2004 laying down specific hygiene rules for food of animal origin or shall be used after boiling for feeding the animals of the affected holding only. The status freedom of disease of an infected holding is regained after culling of all animals that did not reveal a negative result and disinfection under official control.

Control program/mechanisms - Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

See Other preventive measures in place.

Control program/mechanisms - Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

No suggestions to EU

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

See Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place.

Notification system in place

The notification of bovine animals and goats kept together with bovines suspected of being infected is compulsory.

Results of the investigation

In 2016, *M. bovis* was not detected in cattle. Although in total, 37 bovines from 17 herds were diagnosed as infected with *M. caprae*.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

No findings of *M. bovis* in cattle. In 2016, 37 bovines from 17 herds were infected with *M. caprae*. Due to the fact that *M. caprae* is endemic in wildlife deer in certain areas of the Western parts of Austria (and South-Western parts of Germany), the testing of animals according to Rindertuberkuloseverordnung within special testing zones and special monitoring zones will be carried on for the time being.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

In case of the suspicion of the disease in a holding, all measures which shall be taken according to the Rindertuberkuloseverordnung shall be notified in written to the zoonosis coordinator of the province affected by.

Additional information

M. caprae is differentiated in Austria. The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure. See also the publication: Fink M, Schleicher C, Gonano M, Prodingner WM, Pacciarini M, Glawischnig W, et al., 2015. Red deer as maintenance host for bovine tuberculosis, Alpine Region. Emerg Infect Dis [Internet]. 2015 Mar [date cited]. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3201/eid2103.141119>.

B. *Mycobacterium* spp. in animal - all animals - at slaughter – Control programme - mandatory - official sampling (all slaughtered animals except those mentioned above)

Monitoring system – Sampling strategy

According to the federal law for zoonoses (BGBl. I no. 2005/128) following shall be subject to monitoring: tuberculosis caused by *M. bovis* according to the epidemiological situation.

According to federal law Lebensmittelsicherheits- und Verbraucherschutzgesetz (LMSVG, BGBl. I no. 13/2016) and the Regulation Tierseuchen-Untersuchungspflicht-Verordnung BGBl. II no. 90/2007) all slaughter animals shall be subject to ante and post-mortem inspection. Samples from tuberculosis suspected animals are taken after slaughter. Tissues of slaughtered animals which are visibly altered, seen by the unaided eye and lymph nodes.

Monitoring system – Frequency of the sampling

Continuous post-mortem inspections of each slaughtered animal

Monitoring system – Type of specimen taken

Macroscopic tuberculous alterations and lymph nodes

Monitoring system – Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

The altered tissue and lymph nodes are excised and sent to the NRL for tuberculosis in animals

Monitoring system – Case definition

According to the Regulation (EC) no 854/2004, Annex I, Chapter IX lit. E

Monitoring system – Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Staining: Ziehl-Neelsen stains are performed on histological preparation and smears of the sample material.

Culture performed in the AGES National Reference Laboratory for Tuberculosis in Animals in Mödling After decontamination of the homogenized sample material (2g homogenized add 10 ml buffer) in NALC-NaOH 1% (25 min), neutralization (Sörensen Buffer sol.) and centrifugation (3500g, 20 min), the sample material is transferred on commercial media (BD - Becton Dickinson: Loewenstein-Jensen agar containing antibiotics (PACT) and Stonebrink agar containing pyruvate and PACT). The media are incubated at 37° C +/-1° C up to 12 weeks. MTC species are identified with the GenoType MTBC assay (Hain Lifescience GmbH, Nehren, Germany).

Preventive measures in place

Vaccination policy

Vaccination is prohibited in Austria.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

See other chapters.

Control program/mechanisms – The control program/strategies in place

The control strategy is based on the compulsory ante-mortem and post-mortem inspection of all animals slaughtered.

Control program/mechanisms – Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

No need at the moment

Control program/mechanisms – Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

No suggestions to EU

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Measures are taken according to the Regulation (EC) no 654/2004, Annex I, Chapter IX lit. E

Notification system in place

The detection of tuberculosis is notifiable.

Results of the investigation including the origin of the positive animals

M. bovis or *M. caprae* was not detected in any animal tested.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

No cases of *M. bovis* in Austria in 2016.

Results of the investigation – Investigations of the human contacts with positive cases

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Table 34 Bovine tuberculosis in 2016

Member State: Austria..... Date of the report: 19.05.2017..... Year: 2016.....

The official post-mortem examination for all slaughtered bovine animals is implemented: Yes

Region ⁽¹⁾	Total number of existing bovine		Officially free herds*		Infected herds*		Routine tuberculin testing		Number of tuberculin tests carried out before the introduction into the herds (Annex A(I)(2)(c) third indent ⁽¹⁾ of Directive 64/432/EEC)	Number of animals with suspicious lesions of tuberculosis examined and submitted to histopathological and bacteriological examinations	Number of animals detected positive in bacteriological examination (* <i>M. caprae</i>)
	Herds	Animals	Number of herds	%	Number of herds	%	Interval between routine tuberculin tests ⁽²⁾	Number of animals tested			
Austria	61,919	1,954,008	61,902	99.973	17	0.027	a) and (g)	21,126	43	86	37
Total	61,919	1,954,008	61,902	99.973	17	0.027	a) and (g)	21,126	43	86	37

Source of information: Central Veterinary Services

(1) Detailed regional information is required, unless the officially free status has been granted to the whole territory of the Member State.

(2) Use the following letter codes: (a) no routine tests; (b) tests once a year; (c) tests every two years; (d) tests every three years concerning 24 month-old animals; (f) tests every 4 years; (g) others (please give details) Sonderuntersuchungs- bzw. überwachungsgebiet.

* Additional information: In 2016, in 37 bovines out of 17 herds an infection with *M. caprae* could be confirmed. The control measures for *M. caprae* are the same as for *M. bovis*.

Table 35 Tuberculosis in other animals, 2016

Animal species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling Details	Source of information	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Mycobacterium tuberculosis</i> complex	<i>M. bovis</i>	<i>M. caprae</i>
Sheep	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programme - official sampling - census sampling	compulsory ante-mortem and post-mortem inspection	CVS	animal	130,740	0	0	0
Goats	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programme - official sampling - census sampling	compulsory ante-mortem and post-mortem inspection	CVS	animal	7,304	0	0	0
Pigs	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programme - official sampling - census sampling	compulsory ante-mortem and post-mortem inspection	CVS	animal	5,197,563	0	0	0

CVS: Central veterinary services

4.6. Brucellosis

4.6.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In Austria, human brucellosis cases are considered to be an imported infectious disease. The Austrian cattle, sheep and goat population bears the status Officially Brucellosis Free (OBF) and Officially *Brucella melitensis* free (OBmF).

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Four human cases were identified in 2016, three of them imported (*B. melitensis* cases) and one of unknown status (*B. abortus* case). The number of brucellosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

No findings in Austria, OBF and OBmF

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

A new national regulation has been implemented concerning the examination of milk- and blood-samples in cattle (Bovine health surveillance and monitoring regulation, Federal Law Gazette II no. 334/2013).

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Continuation of the existing control programs

Additional information

If zoonotic agents that are listed in the national Zoonoses Act are isolated from human specimen, food or animals, the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

4.6.2. Brucellosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

The number of Brucellosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to the EMS.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

Any person with fever

AND at least one of following seven symptoms:

- Sweating (profuse, malodorous, specially nocturnal)
- Chills
- Arthralgia
- Weakness
- Depression
- Headache
- Anorexia

Laboratory criteria

At least one of the following two:

- Isolation of *Brucella* spp. from a clinical specimen
- *Brucella* specific antibody response (Standard Agglutination Test, Complement Fixation, ELISA)

Case classification

Possible case

- NA

Probable case

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria and with an epidemiological link

Confirmed case

- Any person meeting the clinical and the laboratory criteria

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

- Serological examination: Serum samples are tested in the Complement Fixation Test (CFT) with reference standard antisera from CVL-Weybridge. Participation in international ring trials: Brucellosis European Ring Trial 2000 and 2002 (VLA Weybridge) with ELISA, CFT, RBT and SAT.

- Bacteriological: Multiple blood samples are inoculated in blood culture broth over several consecutive days. The incubation lasted 4 to 6 weeks, once per week medium is transferred on *Brucella* agar and incubated 5-10 % CO₂ atmosphere (Anonymus: Standardisierung und Qualitätssicherung in der mikrobiologischen Diagnostik. Richtlinien. Bundesministerium für Soziale Sicherheit und Generationen. ISBN 3-84123-126-0, Wien, 2001, pg. 56).

- The genus is identified by microscopic examination, catalase-, oxidase- and the slide agglutination test using *Brucella* antiserum. The species is identified by CO₂ requirement, H₂S formation, urease activity, growth on media containing standard concentrations of basic fuchsin or thionin and agglutination with monospecific antisera and by PCR (Real-time detection of *Brucella abortus*, *Brucella melitensis* and *Brucella suis*. 2001: Redkar et al., Mol Cell Probes. 2001 Feb;15(1):43-52.)

Notification system in place

Notification of Brucellosis according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Austria is OBF and OBmF. All cases reported in Austria are epidemiologically linked to travel in endemic countries or to foreign workers from endemic countries.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Due to OBF and OBmF, this zoonosis has no relevance in Austria.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via the monthly and yearly reports published from the Federal Ministry for Austria. The yearly report is published on the Website of the BMGF.

Table 36 Brucellosis in humans - species/serotype distribution (EMS/NRL-B), 2016

	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population	autochthonous cases	Imported cases	Unknown status
Brucellosis	4	0.04	0	3	1
<i>Brucella melitensis</i>	3	0,03	0	3	0
<i>Brucella abortus</i>	1	0,01	0	0	1

Data source: EMS/NRL-B (as of January 7, 2017)

Table 37 Brucellosis in humans - age distribution (EMS/NRL-B), 2016

Age group	Brucellosis			<i>B. melitensis</i>			<i>B. abortus</i>		
	all	m	f	all	m	f	all	m	f
< 1 year	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1 to 4 years	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5 to 14 years	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
15 to 24 years	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
25 to 44 years	2	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1
45 to 64 years	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0

Brucellosis									
65 years and older	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
All age groups	4	3	1	3	3	0	1	0	1

Data source: EMS/NRL-B (as of January 7, 2017)

4.6.3. *Brucella* in foodstuffs

Due to the fact that Austria is OBF and OBmF, food is not investigated for *Brucella* spp.

4.6.4. *Brucella* spp. in animals

A. *Brucella abortus* in bovine animals

Status as officially free of bovine brucellosis during the reporting year - The entire country free

Yes

Status as officially free of bovine brucellosis during the reporting year - Free regions

-

Status as officially free of bovine brucellosis during the reporting year - Additional information

Upon the request of the Commission Decision of July 15th 1999, CD 1999/466/EC, as amended, by the Council Directive 64/432/EEC of 26 June 1964, Austria achieved the status: officially brucellosis-free for bovine herds. Testing of milk- and blood-samples in cattle is also implemented in the national regulation (Bovine Health Surveillance and Monitoring Regulation, Federal Law Gazette II no. 334/2013).

Monitoring system - Sampling strategy

In milk producing holdings and non-milk producing holdings a risk based blood sampling plan was performed. Abortion or premature birth: Abortive material and blood of the cow is sampled.

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling

Holdings with and without milk production: A risk based sampling plan has been calculated stratified according to the different provinces (Bovine Health Surveillance and Monitoring Regulation, Federal Law Gazette II no. 334/2013). In case of not-negative bulk milk samples, blood samples in the affected holding were investigated. If blood serology does not show a definitive negative result diagnostic slaughtering of the affected animal has to be carried out. Abortion or premature birth in context with epidemiological investigation: must be notified to the district veterinarian (§7 and §25 of Bovine Health Surveillance and Monitoring Regulation, Federal Law Gazette II no. 334/2013). Tissues from the aborted fetus and blood from the affected cows are sampled immediately post abortion and tested for brucellosis by microbiological and serological methods.

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken

Bulk milk, Blood samples, Aborted fetus. Diagnostic slaughtering: organs and lymph nodes of the genital tract; udder and accessory lymph nodes; fetus (stomach, lungs); retropharyngeal lymph node. Abortion or premature birth: Tissue and blood samples from the animal that had an abortion.

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Based on: Bovine Health Surveillance and Monitoring Regulation, Federal Law Gazette II no. 334/2013.

Bulk milk sampling and in holdings without milk production blood samples are taken according to the risk based sampling plan. Samples are sent to approved laboratories (according to Annex A of regulation).

Abortion or premature birth: Aborted tissue and blood samples sent to the NRL.

Monitoring system - Case definition

An animal is considered to be positive for bovine brucellosis, in case of positive blood-serological test result and the epidemiological situation of the herd indicates the possibility that a *Brucella abortus*-infection has been introduced to the herd or in case of bacteriological isolation. If a single animal reactor is detected in the holding, tracing back is an important tool to get sufficient information about the reacting animal.

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Bulk milk: Testings according to Council Directive 64/432/EEC and the manual of Diagnostic Tests and Vaccines for Terrestrial Animals of the OIE. Blood samples: Testings according to Council Directive 64/432/EEC and the manual of Diagnostic Tests and Vaccines for Terrestrial Animals of the OIE: Routinely single serum samples or serum pools (5 sera in one pool) were tested in the Indirect-ELISA (I-ELISA) using the three OIE ELISA *Brucella* Standard Sera (OIE ELISAwSS, OIE ELISAspSS, OIE ELISAnSS) and the OIE *Brucella abortus* Positive International Standard Antiserum (OIEISS) to calibrate the method (Commission Regulation 535/2002/EC of 21 March 2002 amending Annex C to Council Directive 64/432/EEC and amending Decision 2000/330/EC). Following a positive or suspected test result in the I-ELISA single serum samples were tested in the Complement Fixation Test (CFT), Rose Bengal test (RBT) and two ELISAs for verification. Participation in international ring trials: Participation in international ring trials (AHVLA, ANSES) with ELISA, CFT, RBT and Serum Agglutination Test (SAT). The National Reference Laboratory for Brucellosis, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control in Moedling organized the national Brucellosis Ring Trials for those Austrian Veterinary Institutes which are involved in brucellosis surveillance and diagnosis. Abortion or premature birth: Aborted material was tested bacteriologically: Smears of the samples are stained by Stableforth's method. Columbia agar (bioMérieux) and Columbia agar (BD) containing selective additives (Oxoid) were inoculated. The culture media were incubated for 5 days at 37° C in an atmosphere containing 10% CO₂. If suspicious colonies appeared specification was performed by microscopic examination, catalase-, oxidase- and the slide agglutination test using *Brucella* antiserum. The species was differentiated by CO₂ requirement, H₂S formation, urease activity, growth on media containing standard concentrations of basic fuchsin or thionin and agglutination with monospecific antisera and by PCR (Real-time detection of *Brucella abortus*, *Brucella melitensis* and *Brucella suis*. 2001: Redkar et al., Mol Cell Probes. 2001 Feb;15(1):43-52.).

Vaccination policy

Vaccination is not allowed (§6 Bovine Health Surveillance and Monitoring Regulation, Federal Law Gazette II no. 334/2013)

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Monitoring program and investigation of abortions

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place

Control programme according to the Bovine Health Surveillance and Monitoring Regulation, Federal Law Gazette II no. 334/2013). Abortion or premature birth: compulsory notification according §7 and §25 Bovine Health Surveillance and Monitoring Regulation, Federal Law Gazette II no. 334/2013.

Control program/mechanisms - Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

No actions, because OBF

Control program/mechanisms - Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

No suggestions

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

According to the Bovine Health Surveillance and Monitoring Regulation, Federal Law Gazette II no. 334/2013.

Notification system in place

Abortion or premature birth; Notification of abortions in context with epidemiological investigations: Bovine Health Surveillance and Monitoring Regulation, Federal Law Gazette II no. 334/2013 and Venereal diseases act, Federal Law Gazette no. 22/1949 as amended; The livestock owner has to notify the abortion

within 24 hours to the mayor (Gemeinde). The mayor has to forward the notification to the district veterinarian (Bezirksverwaltungsbehoerde). If the cow is being treated by a veterinarian or the veterinarian has been informed about the abortion, then the veterinarian has to notify to the official authority (Bezirksverwaltungsbehoerde).

Results of the investigation

In 2016, no cases detected.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

OBF

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Not of relevance in Austria.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

B. Brucella melitensis in sheep and goats

Status as officially free of caprine brucellosis during the reporting year - The entire country free

Yes

Status as officially free of caprine brucellosis during the reporting year - Free regions

Status as officially free of caprine brucellosis during the reporting year - Additional information

Monitoring system - Sampling strategy

The entire country is free of *B. melitensis*. According to Commission Decision Nr. 93/52/EWG, as amended, Austria has the status officially *B. melitensis* free (ObmF). To maintain that status according to Federal Law Gazette II no. 308/2015 (Sheep and Goat Health Surveillance and Monitoring Regulation) a representative number of samples have to be examined with a confidence level of 95 % to detect infected holdings at a target prevalence of 0.2 %. Sampling was performed by the competent authority or under its supervision, by bodies to which it had delegated this responsibility. Samples were taken in the holdings. In cases of abortion, aborted material and blood samples from the affected animal were also investigated.

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling

The sampling was performed mainly during the cold season, between November and May when the animals have been kept in the stables.

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken

Monitoring: Blood samples according to a sampling plan. Clinical cases: Aborted material and blood samples from the affected animal.

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Individual blood samples and aborted material are taken within the holdings and sent to the approved laboratories.

Monitoring system - Case definition

An animal is considered to be infected with *B. melitensis* in case of bacteriological isolation or a positive serological test result.

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Routinely single serum samples were tested in the Indirect ELISA. Confirmation of suspected or positive results was performed by the Complement Fixation Test (CFT) with reference standard antisera from

AHVLA and ANSES. Participation in international ring trials on Brucellosis with ELISA, CFT and RBT. The National Reference Laboratory for Brucellosis, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control in Moedling organized the national Brucellosis Ring Trials for all national Veterinary Institutes. Bacteriology: Smears of the samples were stained by Stableforth's method. Columbia agar (bioMérieux) and Columbia agar (BD) containing selective additives (Oxoid) were used. After inoculation the media were incubated for 5 days at 37° C in an atmosphere containing 10 % CO₂. If suspicious colonies appeared specification was performed by microscopic examination, catalase-, oxidase- and the slide agglutination test using *Brucella* antiserum. The species was differentiated by CO₂ requirement, H₂S formation, urease activity, growth on media containing standard concentrations of basic fuchsin or thionin and agglutination with monospecific antisera and by PCR (Real-time detection of *Brucella abortus*, *Brucella melitensis* and *Brucella suis*. 2001: Redkar et al., Mol Cell Probes. 2001 Feb;15(1):43-52.).

Vaccination policy

According to Federal Law Gazette II no. 308/2015 (Sheep and Goat Health Surveillance and Monitoring Regulation) vaccination is not allowed.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Monitoring program and investigation of abortions

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place

To maintain the status officially brucellosis (*B. melitensis*) free, according to Federal Law Gazette II no. 308/2015 (Sheep and Goat Health Surveillance and Monitoring Regulation) a representative number of samples have to be examined with a confidence level of 95 % to detect infected holdings at a prevalence of 0.2 %. Sampling is performed by the appropriate authority or under its supervision, by bodies to which it has delegated this responsibility. Samples are taken in the holdings. Notification and clarification of each clinical case by bacteriology and serology.

Control program/mechanisms - Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

ObmF

Control program/mechanisms - Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

According to Federal Law Gazette II no. 308/2015 (Sheep and Goat Health Surveillance and Monitoring Regulation) reactors have to be culled, the carcasses have to be incinerated in an incineration plant.

Notification system in place

Notification of brucellosis or a suspicion of brucellosis according to BGBl. 391/1995 (Brucellose-Verordnung).

Results of the investigation

In 2016, no cases detected.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

ObmF

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Additional information

According to Guideline 64/432/EEC as amended.

D. *Brucella suis* in animal – Pigs

Monitoring system - Sampling strategy

No monitoring program, only targeted, following abortion and in positive cases of contact holdings.

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling

Targeted, following abortion and in positive cases contact holdings.

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken

Monitoring: Blood samples; Clinical cases: Abortion material and blood samples from the affected animal; tissues: according to decree 74700/0132-IV/B/5/2008

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Individual blood samples and abortion material are taken from animals in the holdings and sent to the approved laboratories.

Monitoring system - Case definition

An animal is considered to be serologically positive for brucellosis following one/more positive CFT Complement Fixation Test (CFT) and RBT Rose Bengal test (RBT) results (*B. abortus* used antigen). A bacteriological isolation may also be possible as in the case of *B.suis*.

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Brucella ELISA and CFT are used. Participation in international ring trials: Brucellosis European Ring Trial 2000 and 2002 (AHVLA and ANSES) with ELISA, CFT and RBT. The National Reference Laboratory for Brucellosis, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control in Moedling organized the national Brucellosis Ring Trials for all Veterinary Institutes. Bacteriology: - Smears of the samples are stained by Stableforths method.- Columbia agar (bioMrieux) and Columbia agar (BD) containing selective additives (Oxoid) were used. After inoculation the media were incubated for 5 days at 37 C in an atmosphere containing 10 % CO₂. If suspicious colonies appeared specification was performed by microscopic examination, catalase-, oxidase- and the slide agglutination test using Brucella antiserum. The species was differentiated by CO₂ requirement, H₂S formation, urease activity, growth on media containing standard concentrations of basic fuchsin or thionin and agglutination with monospecific antisera and by PCR (Real-time detection of Brucella abortus, Brucella melitensis and Brucella suis. 2001: Redkar et al., Mol Cell Probes. 2001 Feb;15(1):43-52.).

Vaccination policy

No vaccination

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

No other measures foreseen

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place

Targeted, following abortion and in positive cases contact holdings.

Control program/mechanisms - Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Targeted, following abortion and in positive cases contact holdings.

Control program/mechanisms - Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

No suggestions

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

No mandatory measures but notification is required.

Notification system in place

B.suis has been a notifiable disease since 1993 according to BGBl 1993/756, Tierseuchen-Anzeigepflichtverordnung, as amended.

Results of the investigation including the origin of the positive animals

There was no case of *Brucella suis* in 2016.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Due to the results of the passive monitoring in pigs we conclude that there is no need for an active monitoring program.

Results of the investigation - Investigations of the human contacts with positive cases

Currently of no relevance in Austria

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Table 38 Bovine Brucellosis data from countries and regions that do not receive European Union co-financing (non co-financed), 2016

Member State: Austria Date of report: 18.05.2017 Year: 2016.....

Region ⁽¹⁾	Total number of existing bovine		Officially free herds		Infected herds		Surveillance ⁽²⁾						Investigations of suspect cases								
			Number of herds	%	Number of herds	%	Serological tests			Examination of bulk milk samples			Information on abortions			Epidemiological investigation					
	Herds	Animals					Number of bovine herds tested	Number of animals tested	Number of infected herds	Number of bovine herds tested	Number of animals or pools tested	Number of infected herds	Number of notified abortions whatever cause	Number of isolations of <i>Brucella</i> infection	Number of abortions due to <i>Brucella abortus</i>	Number of animals tested with serological blood tests	Number of suspended herds	Serologically	BS T	Number of animals examined microbiologically	Number of animals positive microbiologically
Austria	61,919	1,954,008	61,919	100	0	0	1,281	11,805	0	1,287	1,287	0	367	0	0	906	8	0	0	94	0
Total	61,919	1,954,008	61,919	100	0	0	1,281	11,805	0	1,287	1,287	0	367	0	0	906	8	0	0	94	0

Source of information: Central Veterinary Services

(1) Detailed regional information is required, unless the officially free status has been granted to the whole territory of the Member State.

(2) Please give details.

Table 39 Ovine and caprine brucellosis - data from countries that do not receive co-financing for control or eradication programme, 2016

Member State: Austria..... Date of report: 2.05.2017..... Year: 2016.....

Region (1)	Total number of existing ovine/caprine		Officially free herds		Infected herds		Surveillance (2)			Investigations of suspect cases				
	Herds	Animals	Number of herds	%	Number of herds	%	Number of herds tested	Number of animals tested	Number of infected herds	Number of animals tested with serological blood tests	Number of animals positive serologically	Number of animals examined micro-biologically	Number of animals positive micro-biologically	Number of suspended herds
Austria	25,834	591,523	25,834	100	0	0	1,559	20,551	0	14	0	0	0	4
Total	25,834	591,523	25,834	100	0	0	1,559	20,551	0	14	0	0	0	4

Source of information: Central Veterinary Services, Provincial Veterinary Services

(1) Detailed regional information is required, unless the officially free status has been granted to the whole territory of the Member State.

(2) Please give details.

Total number of existing ovine/caprine herds: Number is less than in Table 1 (Susceptible animal populations) because mixed farms are deducted from the sum.

4.7. Yersiniosis

4.7.1. General evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Yersiniosis is not considered a major food borne illness in Austria. The incidence of human disease is low when compared to salmonellosis or campylobacteriosis and has been stable over the last years.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The number of yersiniosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to the EMS. The sources of infections are unclear. Neither studies on sporadic cases nor scientific outbreak investigations were performed in Austria so far.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Additional information

If zoonotic agents that are listed in the national Zoonoses Act, are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

4.7.2. Yersiniosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

The number of yersiniosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed (NRC-Y) cases notified to the EMS.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

Any person with at least one of the following five symptoms:

- Fever
- Diarrhoea
- Vomiting
- Abdominal pain (pseudoappendicitis)
- Tenesmus

Laboratory criteria

- Isolation of human pathogenic *Y. enterocolitica* or *Y. pseudotuberculosis* from a clinical specimen

Case classification

Possible case

- NA

Probable case

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria and with an epidemiological link

Confirmed case

- Any person meeting the clinical and the laboratory criteria

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Sample material is plated directly on cefsulodin-irgasan-novobiocin (CIN) agar and incubated for 18 hours at 30 °C. Suspicious colonies are identified in an Api 20 E reaction and API 50 CHE reaction. *Y. enterocolitica* is agglutinated with sera against serogroups O:3; O:5,27; O:9 and O:8. Biovar and pathogenicity are defined.

Notification system in place

Notification of yersiniosis according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Yersiniosis is the fourth most bacterial food borne pathogen in Austria although compared to salmonellosis and campylobacteriosis, the number of notified cases are much lower.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The number of human cases has been similar in the last years.

Relevance as zoonotic disease

In Austria yersiniosis is much less identified than salmonellosis and campylobacteriosis.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via the monthly and yearly reports published from the Federal Ministry for Austria. The yearly report is published on the Website of the BMGF.

Table 40 Yersiniosis in humans - species/serotype distribution (EMS/NRC-Y), 2016

Yersiniosis	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population
<i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i> , pathogenic	83	0,95
<i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i> O:2 biovar 4	1	0,01
<i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i> O:3 biovar 4	71	0,82
<i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i> O:4 biovar 3	1	0,01
<i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i> O:9 biovar 2	9	0,10
<i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i> O:9 biovar 3	1	0,01
<i>Yersinia pseudotuberculosis</i>	3	0,03

Data source: EMS as of January 10, 2017

Table 41 Yersiniosis in humans - age distribution (EMS/NRC-Y), 2016

age groups	Yersiniosis			<i>Y. enterocolitica</i>			<i>Y. enterocolitica</i> O:3			<i>Y. enterocolitica</i> O:9			Y. pseudotuberculosis		
	all	m	f	all	m	f	all	m	f	all	m	f	all	m	f
< 1 year	1	1		1	1		1	1		0	0	0	0	0	0
1 to 4 years	14	10	4	14	10	4	13	9	4	1	1		0	0	0
5 to 14 years	19	11	8	18	11	7	17	10	7	1	1		1	0	1
15 to 24 years	11	6	5	11	6	5	9	6	3	1		1	0	0	0
25 to 44 years	22	13	9	21	12	9	16	10	6	4	2	2	1	1	0
45 to 64 years	15	8	7	14	8	6	12	8	4	2		2	1	0	1
65 years and older	4	2	2	4	2	2	3	1	2	1	1		0	0	0
Gesamtergebnis	86	51	35	83	50	33	71	45	26	10	5	5	3	1	2

Data source: EMS as of January 10, 2017

4.7.3. *Yersinia* in foodstuffs

Monitoring system - Sampling strategy

In 2016, foodstuffs were sampled all over Austria according to the national control plan given in the ordinance „Nationaler Kontrollplan für das Jahr 2016 gem. § 31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2016“ (BMG-75500/0168-II/B/13/2015) from the Federal Ministry of Health and Women’s Affairs. This “Nationaler Kontrollplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2016-2018) according to the Art. 41ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004 and consists of several separated parts:

The inspection part (“Inspektionsteil”) determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be visited and inspected. Every food business has to be inspected regularly. The inspection comprises sampling, hygienic investigations of the establishment and the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc.

The part for sampling is comprised of scheduled (“Planproben”) and suspect samples (“Verdachtsproben”). In 2016, the part for sampling intended approximately 20,000 scheduled samples and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). This yearly part for sampling determines the number of samples for each stage (retail, processing plants, primary production) and for each food category that has to be investigated randomly.

If specific suspicions (e.g. colour deviation, temperature, etc.) initiate the sampling by officials, these samples are categorised as suspect samples. Moreover any follow up sampling (e.g. due to RASFF, monitoring, positive samples, further information, etc.) is defined as suspect sample as well as food samples from private persons or sampling due to outbreak situations.

In addition there are monitoring plans, so called campaigns, for specific food items (about 55-60 individual campaigns per year). In the course of those campaigns food items of special interest are investigated for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents. In order to gain in-depth information the sampling takes place during a specified time frame. In 2016, 4 different food campaigns were conducted throughout Austria dealing with zoonotic agents. Each campaign is described in detail and results are depicted in the respective chapters per pathogen.

Monitoring system - Definition of positive finding

Isolation of *Yersinia* sp. from a sample.

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Bacteriological method: EN ISO 10273:2003 in combination with the PCR Screening: ISO/TS 18867

Results of the investigation

See table

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

see table

Relevance of the findings in foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of human infection)

Nil

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the zoonosis brochure 2016.

Table 42 *Yersinia* spp. in food, 2016

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sampling Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Yersinia</i>
Meat from bovine animals - fresh	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
	Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	2
Meat from pig - fresh	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	16	4
	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	48	21
		EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
	Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
Meat, mixed meat - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	1
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified	Retail	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	296	1

4.7.4. *Yersinia* spp. in animals

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling

Not relevant in Austria therefore no testing.

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Not relevant in Austria therefore no testing.

Vaccination policy

No vaccination.

Control program/mechanisms - Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

EU wide harmonized monitoring program.

Notification system in place

Findings of *Yersinia* are not notifiable in animals.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

No changes in recent years.

4.8. Trichinellosis

4.8.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

No documented autochthon human infestations since several years. In 2016, 2 human cases of unknown origin were notified.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The number of trichinellosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of cases reported to the EMS. No documented autochthonous human infestations in 2016. In the years 2013-2016 examinations in the two Austrian provinces Tyrol and Vorarlberg revealed larvae of *Trichinella* in 1.7% of the tested foxes in Tyrol (8 out of 476 tested) and 6.8% in Vorarlberg (29 out of 428 tested) (Glawischnig W und Schleicher C, 2017. Abschlussberichte: Untersuchungen zum aktuellen Vorkommen von *Trichinella* spp. bei Füchsen in Tirol und in Vorarlberg). Foxes constitute the ideal indicator to study the occurrence and distribution of *Trichinella* in the wild animal population. All identified *Trichinella* in this study belonged to the species *T. britovi*, which has been found to be the most prevalent in wild animals in Middle Europe.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

In 2016, no cases in animals that were used for food production, farmed or wild, were detected.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

No new measures implemented

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Reconsider the necessity of routine *Trichinella* meat inspection in pig carcasses

Additional information

If zoonotic agents that are listed in the national Zoonoses Act, are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

4.8.2. Trichinellosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

The number of trichinellosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to the EMS.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

Any person with at least three of the following six symptoms:

- Fever
- Muscle soreness and pain
- Diarrhoea
- Facial oedema
- Eosinophilia
- Subconjunctival, subungual and retinal haemorrhages

Laboratory criteria

At least one of the following two:

- Demonstration of *Trichinella* larvae in tissue obtained by muscle biopsy
- *Trichinella* specific antibody response (IFA test, ELISA or Western Blot)

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

ELISA and Westernblot

Notification system in place

Notification of trichinellosis according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

The last autochthonous cases have been reported in 1970

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2016, 2 imported cases of trichinellosis were notified. In the years 2012-2015, no human cases were reported in Austria.

Relevance as zoonotic disease

No relevance in Austria

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via the monthly and yearly reports published from the Federal Ministry of Health and Women's Affairs. The yearly report is published on the Website of the BMGF.

Table 43 Trichinellosis in human - species/serotype distribution (EMS), 2016

	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population	Imported cases	Unkown
Trichinellosis	2	0.02	2	0
<i>Trichinella</i> sp.	2	0.02	2	0

Data source: EMS (as of February 22, 2017)

4.8.3. *Trichinella* spp. in animals

A. *Trichinella* spp. in horses

Monitoring system - Sampling strategy

Targeted sampling of all slaughtered horses; the sampling is performed by competent authorities; the samples are taken at slaughterhouses; the sampling is part of a permanent monitoring scheme

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling

Permanent post-mortem sampling of each slaughtered horse

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken

Muscles from tongue, masseter, diaphragm and neck.

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

A given weight of muscle is excised out of the carcass.

Monitoring system - Case definition

Trichinella spp. detected with one of the given methods.

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 2015/1375, magnetic stirrer method for pooled-sample digestion

Vaccination policy

No vaccination

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

No other preventive measures.

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place

Lebensmittelsicherheits- und Verbraucherschutzgesetz (LMSVG, BGBl. I 2006/13, as amended),
Fleischuntersuchungsverordnung (BGBl II 2006/109 as amended)

Control program/mechanisms - Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

No recent actions.

Control program/mechanisms - Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 854/2004 as amended.

Notification system in place

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 854/2004 as amended.

Results of the investigation including the origin of the positive animals

No findings in horses.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

No findings in horses.

Results of the investigation - Investigations of the human contacts with positive cases

No documented autochthon human infestations since several years. In 2016, 2 human cases of imported origin were notified.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

B. *Trichinella* spp. in animal - wild boars

Monitoring system - Sampling strategy

Sampling of all hunted or harvested wild boars; the sampling is performed by hunters with special knowledge about *Trichinella* investigation or by competent authorities; the sampling is stratified by geographical regions depending to the habitats of wild boar in Austria; samples are taken either immediately after shooting the animal or at the cold storage depots; the sampling is part of a monitoring scheme.

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling

All farmed wild boars are controlled for *Trichinella*.

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken

Diaphragm muscles (crus), tongue, masseter and abdominal muscles.

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

A given weight of muscle is excised out of the carcass.

Monitoring system - Case definition

Trichinella spp. detected with one of the given methods.

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 2015/1375, magnetic stirrer method for pooled-sample digestion

Vaccination policy

Nil

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place**Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place****Control program/mechanisms - Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses**

Lebensmittelsicherheits- und Verbraucherschutzgesetz (LMSVG, BGBl. I 2006/13, as amended),
Fleischuntersuchungsverordnung (BGBl II 2006/109 as amended)

Control program/mechanisms - Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Nil

Notification system in place

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 854/2004 as amended.

Results of the investigation including the origin of the positive animals

In 2016 no case of *Trichinella* was found neither in farmed nor in wild wild boars.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2016 no case of *Trichinella* was found neither in farmed nor in wild wild boars.

Results of the investigation - Investigations of the human contacts with positive cases

No documented autochthon human infestations since several years. In 2016, 2 human cases of imported were notified.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

***C. Trichinella* spp. in pigs**

Monitoring system - Sampling strategy - General

Targeted sampling of all slaughtered pigs except pigs slaughtered by the farmer for his own consumption; the sampling is performed by competent authorities; the samples are taken at slaughterhouses; the sampling is part of a permanent monitoring scheme.

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling - General

Permanent post-mortem sampling of each slaughtered pig

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken - General

Muscles: Diaphragm (crus), tongue, masseter and abdominal muscles.

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques) - General

A given weight of muscle is excised out of the carcass.

Monitoring system - Case definition - General

Trichinella spp. detected with one of the given methods

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used - General

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 2015/1375, magnetic stirrer method for pooled-sample digestion

Preventive measures in place

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 854/2004, as amended.

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place

Lebensmittelsicherheits- und Verbraucherschutzgesetz (LMSVG, BGBl. I 2006/13, as amended),
Fleischuntersuchungsverordnung (BGBl II 2006/109 as amended)

Control program/mechanisms - Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

No recent actions.

Control program/mechanisms - Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Reconsider the necessity of routine *Trichinella* meat inspection in pig carcasses

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

The carcass is condemned

Notification system in place

Each detected case must be notified to the authority.

Results of the investigation including description of the positive cases and the verification of the *Trichinella* species

No findings of *Trichinella* in farmed pigs

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

No findings of *Trichinella* in farmed pigs.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

In 2016, 2 imported cases of trichionellosis were notified. In the years 2012-2015, no human cases were reported in Austria.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Table 44 *Trichinella* spp. in animals, 2016

Animal species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling Details	Source of information	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Trichinella</i> spp.
Pigs							
Pigs - fattening pigs - not raised under controlled housing conditions	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official and industry sampling - census sampling	CVS	animal	5,109,372	0	
Pigs - breeding animals - not raised under controlled housing conditions - sows	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official and industry sampling - census sampling	CVS	animal	86,849	0	
Pigs - breeding animals - not raised under controlled housing conditions - boars	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official and industry sampling - census sampling	CVS	animal	1,342	0	
Domestic solipeds							
horses	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official and industry sampling - census sampling	CVS	animal	602	0	
Wild boars							
Wild boars, wild	hunting	Control and eradication programmes - official and industry sampling - census sampling	CVS	animal	22,468	0	
Wild boars, farmed	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official and industry sampling - census sampling	CVS	animal	696	0	
Nutria			CVS	animal	2	0	
Badger			CVS	animal	9	0	

CVS: Central Veterinary Services

4.9. Echinococcosis

4.9.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Austria is a low risk country for both forms of echinococcosis.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The number of echinococcosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases reported to the EMS.

From 2013 to 2016, the Institute for Veterinary Disease Control Innsbruck of the AGES performed investigations about the prevalence of *E. multilocularis* in foxes in the two Austrian provinces Tyrol and Vorarlberg. The examinations showed that 33% of foxes in Tyrol (145 out of 434 foxes tested) and 45% in Vorarlberg (183 out of 405 foxes tested) were infested with *E. multilocularis* (Glawischnig W und Walser F, 2017. Abschlussberichte: Untersuchungen zum aktuellen Vorkommen des Fünfgliedrigen Fuchsbandwurmes bei Füchsen in Tirol und in Vorarlberg).

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Alveolar echinococcosis: Due to the infestation rates of red foxes in Austria (0-40 %) there is a relatively elevated risk for hunters, cat owners and farmers.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Tools for preventive serological screening of hunters (and also other persons) have been established to detect *Echinococcus multilocularis* infections in an early stage. The early detection of the infection is the prerequisite for a successful curative treatment.

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Additional information

If zoonotic agents that are listed in the national Zoonoses Act are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

4.9.2. Echinococcosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

The number of Echinococcosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to the EMS.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

Not relevant for surveillance purposes

Diagnostic criteria

At least one of the following five findings:

- Histopathology or parasitology compatible with *Echinococcus multilocularis* or *E. granulosus* (e.g. direct visualisation of the protoscolex in cyst fluid)
- Detection of *Echinococcus granulosus* pathognomonic macroscopic morphology of cyst(s) in surgical specimens
- Typical organ lesions detected by imaging techniques (e.g.: computerised tomography, sonography, MRI) AND confirmed by a serological test
- *Echinococcus* spp. specific serum antibodies by high-sensitivity serological test AND confirmed by a high specificity serological test

- Detection of *Echinococcus multilocularis* or *E. granulosus* nucleic acid in a clinical specimen

Case classification

Possible case

- NA

Probable case

- NA

Confirmed case

- Any person meeting the diagnostic criteria

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

ELISA and Westernblot technique, participant of the UK National External Quality Assessment Service for Microbiology, National Reference Laboratory for Echinococcosis.

Notification system in place

Notification of echinococcosis according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesezt, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

- Alveolar echinococcosis has been known in Austria since 1897; annual incidence (1897- 2004): 0-6 cases, mean incidence: 2.4 cases/year (only autochthonous cases); geographic distribution in Austria: mainly in the western provinces (Vorarlberg, Tyrol, Salzburg), but cases have been reported in every province; outbreaks are not known.
- Cystic echinococcosis has been known in Austria at least since 1819; Cases of cystic echinococcosis have been registered in the Clinical Institute of Hygiene and Medical Microbiology (Medical University Vienna) regularly since the beginning of the 1980ies. Annual incidence (1984 - 2006): 20 - 60 cases; mean incidence: 31 cases per year, one third of patients are of Austrian origin; two thirds are from abroad. Geographic distribution in Austria is unknown; a few autochthonous infections could be observed mainly in the eastern and southern provinces (Lower Austria, Burgenland, and Styria); outbreaks are not known.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

- Alveolar echinococcosis: We expect the future incidence to be low; sources of infestation: fox faeces (contaminated hands and fingers, vegetables, water).
- Cystic echinococcosis: We expect the future incidence to be low; sources of infestation: dog faeces, presumably in a very few foci (in or around farmers houses)

Relevance as zoonotic disease

Low incidence of both forms of echinococcosis

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via the monthly and yearly reports published from the Federal Ministry for Austria. The yearly report is published on the Website of the BMGF.

Table 45 Echinococcosis in humans - species/serotype distribution (EMS), 2015

	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population	autochthonous cases	imported cases	unknown
Echinococcosis	26	0,30	10	9	7
Hydatid echinococcosis	22	0,25	8	8	6
Alveolar echinococcosis	4	0,05	2	1	1

Data source: EMS as of February 22, 2017

Table 46 Echinococcosis in humans - age distribution (EMS), 2015

Age group	Hydatid echinococcosis			Alveolar echinococcosis		
	all	m	f	all	m	f
< 1 year	0	0	0	0	0	0
1 to 4 years	0	0	0	0	0	0
5 to 14 years	0	0	0	2	1	1
15 to 24 years	1	0	1	4	3	1
25 to 44 years	0	0	0	10	4	6
45 to 64 years	1	1	0	5	2	3
65 years and older	2	2	0	1	0	1
All age groups	4	3	1	22	10	12

Data source: EMS as of February 22, 2017

4.9.3. *Echinococcus* spp. in animals

Monitoring system - Sampling strategy

Targeted sampling of all in abattoirs slaughtered animals; the sampling is performed by competent authorities in course of the post-mortem meat inspection; the sampling is part of a permanent monitoring scheme.

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling

Permanent post-mortem sampling of each slaughtered animal

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

All organs and muscles that were used for human consumption

Monitoring system - Case definition

Each carcass in which cysts, cystic or alveolar hydatids are detected in muscles or organs

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used

All organs and muscles that were used for human consumption were visually inspected, palpated and cuttings were performed

Vaccination policy

No vaccination

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

No measures

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place

Post-mortem meat inspection act according to BGBl. 1982/522, Fleischuntersuchungsgesetz, as amended

Control program/mechanisms - Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Control program/mechanisms - Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Carcasses with very low number of detected cysts are made fit for consumption by deep-freezing overseen by the official veterinarian; if higher numbers of cysts are found the carcasses are declared unfit for human consumption.

Notification system in place

Results of the investigation including the origin of the positive animals

See table

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

No changes in the last years.

Results of the investigation - Investigations of the human contacts with positive cases

No information available.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Cystic or alveolar echinococcosis in animals that are used for food production do not play a role for the infection of humans; it is primarily a hygienic problem.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Table 47 *Echinococcus* sp. in animals, 2016

Animal species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Source of information	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Echinococcus</i> spp.	<i>E. multilocularis</i>	<i>E. granulosus</i>	<i>Echinococcus</i> spp., unspecified
Cattle*	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official sampling - census sampling	x	animal	686,525	92	-	-	92
Sheep	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official sampling - census sampling	x	animal	130,740	28	-	-	28
Goats	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official sampling - census sampling	x	animal	7,304	0	-	-	0
Pigs	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official sampling - census sampling	x	animal	5,197,563	0	-	-	0

* cattle including calves

x: Central Veterinary Services

All detected cysts are reported as echinococcus but not differentiated (could also be other species than *Echinococcus* spp.).

4.10. Toxoplasmosis

4.10.1. General evaluation

Toxoplasmosis in humans is not notifiable. Samples from pregnant women (amniotic liquor) in Austria are tested in the Toxoplasmosis-Laboratory via PCR. If toxoplasma is detected, umbilical cord blood is tested as a kind of quality control. Neonates from infected mothers are controlled as follow-up.

4.10.2. *Toxoplasma* in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

Toxoplasmosis in humans is not notifiable. To determine the incidence of primary gestational infections with *Toxoplasma gondii* and congenital toxoplasmosis in Austria, a nationwide prenatal serological screening program exists since 1974, the Austrian Toxoplasmosis Register. In Austria, *Toxoplasma* screening of pregnant women is part of the “motherchild-booklet” and covered by national healthcare providers and the Ministry of Health.

First-line serologic screening is scheduled within the first trimester, and analyses are performed by clinical laboratories. Seronegative women have to be retested bimonthly. In case of primary gestational infection (PGI), treatment is administered until birth.

Case definition

Women with seroconversions and potential infections were classified as having PGI. Infants were classified as follows: (1) congenital toxoplasmosis, determined by the persistence of anti-*Toxoplasma* immunoglobulin G (IgG) antibodies beyond the age of 1 year, positive PCR from amniotic fluid, or histopathological isolation of parasite; or (2) non-infected infants, with maternally transmitted antibodies, identified by negative *Toxoplasma*-specific IgG during the first year of life.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Since 1992, amniocentesis and *Toxoplasma*-specific polymerase chain reaction (PCR) have been used for diagnosis in affected women and to determine treatment management. If *Toxoplasma* was detected, umbilical cord blood is tested as a kind of quality control. Serum samples were analyzed routinely by different automated test systems in clinical laboratories. In general, all institutions were certified for quality management according to the International Organization for Standardization from Quality Austria. Neonates from infected mothers are controlled as follow-up. In case of undetermined infection status, the in-house Sabin-Feldman dye test and immunoglobulin M immunosorbent agglutination assay (bioMérieux) were performed at the Reference Laboratory. The PCR analyses of amniotic fluid samples were only performed with the same protocol at the Medical University of Vienna

Notification system in place

Toxoplasmosis in humans is not notifiable.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In this 17-year period, 1992-2008, congenital toxoplasmosis incidence of 8.45 (95% CI, 7.98–8.95) PGIs per 10,000 women, and 1.0 (95% CI, 0.84–1.18) per 10,000 births was reported. Incidence of symptomatic congenital toxoplasmosis was 0.12 per 10,000 live births. This resulted in a mean transmission rate of 13%. In detail, the transmission was <9% (95% CI, 2.9%–14.2%) In 14 of 141 (10%) infected infants, the serological diagnosis was performed at birth. Congenital toxoplasmosis was confirmed in 141 cases, resulting in a morbidity of 1.4% (95% CI, 0.83%–2.27%) and mortality of 0.6% (95% CI, 0.24%–1.20%). In 14 of 141 (10%) infected infants, the serological diagnosis was performed at birth.

Results of the investigation

In 2016, maternally infections were diagnosed in 88 cases, congenital toxoplasmosis in eight cases. Four more patients are still under antiparasitic treatment but the infectious status has not been confirmed due to age (< 9 months).

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The Austrian Toxoplasmosis Register reveals a decrease of the incidence of congenital toxoplasmosis since the implementation of the mandatory prenatal screening compared with historical data. Prior to screening, the rate of congenital toxoplasmosis was 78 per 10,000 live births. In the 17-year study period, the authors of the study (see additional information) observed a decrease of congenital toxoplasmosis to 1 per 10,000 births. In addition, they found 9 per 10,000 PGIs per year.

Relevance as zoonotic disease

Toxoplasmosis is a relevant zoonotic disease, because infection only occurs via orally ingestion of oocysts after contact with cats and food contaminated with cat faeces or via consumption of cysts-containing undercooked or raw meat.

Additional information

The information about “*Toxoplasma* in humans” is taken from: Prusa AR, Kasper DC, Pollak A, Gleiss A, Waldhoer T, Hayde M (2015) The Austrian Toxoplasmosis Register, 1992-2008. Clin Infect Dis. 2015 Jan 15;60(2).

Table 48 Toxoplasmosis cases in pregnant and fetus (NRL-T), 2016

	N
Maternally infections	88
Congenital cases	8*

* 4 more patients are still under antiparasitic treatment but the infectious status has not been confirmed due to age (< 9 months)

Data source: National Toxoplasmosis Register as of May 15, 2017
 (Toxoplasrose Diagnostik in der Schwangerschaft und kindliches Follow-up
 Nationales Toxoplasrose Register
 Klinische Abteilung für Neonatologie, pädiatrische Intensivmedizin und Neuropädiatrie
 Univ. Klinik für Kinder- und Jugendheilkunde
 Medizinische Universität Wien
 1090 Wien, Währinger Gürtel 18-20)

4.11. Rabies

4.11.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Rabies in humans was a major public health issue in the 1960s.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2016, no case of rabies was detected in humans or animals in Austria.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Not of relevance

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

In 2016, due to official rabies free status in Austria (since 28.9.2008) oral vaccination of foxes has been suspended; monitoring is carried out on indicator animals (foxes, badgers, racoons, racoon dogs found dead, victims of road traffic or clinical suspect), according to EFSA's recommendation "Development of harmonised schemes for monitoring and reporting of rabies in animals in the European Union" (<http://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/supporting/doc/67e.pdf>).

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Not of relevance

Additional information

Not of relevance

4.11.2. Rabies in humans

Case definition

Clinical criteria

Any person with an acute encephalomyelitis

AND

At least two of the following seven symptoms:

- Sensory changes referred to the site of a preceding animal bite
- Paresis or paralysis
- Spasms of swallowing muscles
- Hydrophobia
- Delirium
- Convulsions
- Anxiety

Laboratory criteria

At least one of the following four:

- Isolation of Lyssa virus from a clinical specimen
- Detection of Lyssa virus nucleic acid in a clinical specimen (e.g. saliva or brain tissue)
- Detection of viral antigens by a DFA in a clinical specimen
- Lyssa virus specific antibody response by virus isneutralisation assay in serum or CSF

Laboratory results need to be interpreted according to the vaccination or immunisation status

Case classification

Possible case

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria

Probable case

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria and with an epidemiological link
- Confirmed case
- Any person meeting the clinical and the laboratory criteria

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Liquor, smears from pharynx, swab from conjunctivae biopsy at the nape of the neck and serum were examined in the fluorescent antibody test (FAT), immunohistochemistry and RT-PCR (Ito M., Itou T., Sakai T., et al. (2001). Detection of Rabies Virus RNA isolated from several species of animals in Brazil by RT-PCR. Journal of Veterinary medicine Science 63(12): 1309-1313.).

Notification system in place

Notification of rabies according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

No case in Austria in 2016

Table 49 Rabies in humans, 2016

	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population	Autochtone cases	Imported cases
Rabies	0	0	0	0
Human exposure	0	0	0	0

Data source: EMS as of April 27, 2016

4.11.3. Lyssavirus (rabies) in animals

Monitoring system - Sampling strategy

Wild animals: According to the degree Überwachung der Tollwut 2013 (BMG-74600/0309-II/B/11/2012) monitoring is carried out on indicator animals (foxes, badgers, racoons, racoon dogs found dead, victims of road traffic or clinical suspect).

Other animals: Sampling is targeted when animals are observed with central nerval symptoms or after biting a person. The suspicious animal is killed or euthanized and the carcass or head is sent to the laboratory.

Monitoring system - Frequency of the sampling

Wild animals: Monitoring is carried out on indicator animals (foxes, badgers, racoons, racoon dogs found dead, victims of road traffic or clinical suspect), according to EFSA's recommendation Development of harmonised schemes for monitoring and reporting of rabies in animals in the European Union.

Other animals: If a case is suspected

Monitoring system - Type of specimen taken

Brain (brain stem and/or hippocampus)

Monitoring system - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Wild animals: Whole animals or heads of the dead animals are sent to the laboratories; sometimes brain tissue (derived from other laboratories). Brain tissue (e.g. 1 cm) is examined.

Other animals: Routinely 2 parts from the brain will be taken: hippocampus and brain stem.

Monitoring system - Case definition

An animal is considered positive if the fluorescent antibody tests (FAT) or the rabies tissue culture infection test or the mouse inoculation test show a positive result.

Monitoring system - Diagnostic/analytical methods used

The routine test is the fluorescent antibody test (FAT). RTCIT (rabies tissue culture infection test) is performed on mouse neuroblastoma cells. MIT (mouse inoculation test) is only performed on demand, not for routine confirmation.

Vaccination policy

Due to official status rabies free no vaccination of foxes. Voluntary vaccination of pets.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

No measures

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place

Wild animals: Fuchs-Tollwutbekämpfungsverordnung 2010 BGBl II 2010/329, Tierseuchengesetz TSG RGBI 1909/177 as amended, BGBl I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, 41, 42, Tierseuchengesetz-Durchführungsverordnung 1909/178 as amended: BGBl 1955/76 TSG-DVO zum IV. Abschnitt Wutkrankheiten; degree Überwachung der Tollwut 2013 (BMG-74600/0309-II/B/11/2012).
Other animals: According to Tierseuchengesetz TSG RGBI 1909/177 as amended, BGBl I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, 41, 42

Control program/mechanisms - Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Not of relevance

Control program/mechanisms - Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Not of relevance

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Tierseuchengesetz TSG RGBI 1909/177 as amended, BGBl I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, 41, 42, and vaccination of the fox population. If a rabies suspicious pet bites a person, the person is treated.

Notification system in place

According to Tierseuchengesetz TSG RGBI 1909/177 as amended, BGBl I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, 41, 42

Results of the investigation including the origin of the positive animals

No cases in animals

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Austria has been declared as rabies free since 28.9.2008.

Results of the investigation - Investigations of the human contacts with positive cases

No human cases

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

No human cases

Additional information

On 28th of September 2008, Austria has been declared free of rabies. In 2013, oral vaccination of foxes was suspended all over Austria.

Table 50 Rabies in animals, 2016

Animal species	Sampling stage	Sampling context	sampler	Sampling strategy	Sample type	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Lyssa</i> virus (rabies)
Foxes - wild	Hunting	Monitoring - passive	Official sampling	Selective sampling	animal sample - brain	88	0
Foxes - wild	Hunting	Monitoring - passive	Official sampling	Suspect sampling	animal sample - brain	108	0
Badgers - wild	Hunting	Monitoring - passive	Official sampling	Selective sampling	animal sample - brain	13	0
Badgers - wild	Hunting	Monitoring - passive	Official sampling	Suspect sampling	animal sample - brain	8	0
Bats - wild	Unspecified	Monitoring - passive	Not applicable	Selective sampling	animal sample - brain	4	0
Bats - wild	Unspecified	Monitoring - passive	Not applicable	Suspect sampling	animal sample - brain	3	0
Dogs - pet animals	Unspecified	Clinical investigations	Official sampling	Suspect sampling	animal sample - brain	24	0
Cats - pet animals	Unspecified	Clinical investigations	Official sampling	Suspect sampling	animal sample - brain	24	0
Deer - wild - roe deer	Hunting	Unspecified	Not applicable	Suspect sampling	animal sample - brain	3	0
Cattle (bovine animals) - unspecified	Farm	Clinical investigations	Official sampling	Suspect sampling	animal sample - brain	2	0
Solipeds, domestic - horses	Farm	Clinical investigations	Official sampling	Suspect sampling	animal sample - brain	11	0
Rodents - wild	Hunting	Unspecified	Not applicable	Suspect sampling	animal sample - brain	3	0
Rats - wild	Unspecified	Unspecified	Not applicable	Suspect sampling	animal sample - brain	1	0
Marten - wild	Hunting	Unspecified	Not applicable	Suspect sampling	animal sample - brain	15	0
Ferret - pet animals	Unspecified	Clinical investigations	Official sampling	Suspect sampling	animal sample - brain	1	0

Immunofluorescence antibody test (IFAT) and/or PCR and/or cell culture

* indicator animals(foxes,badgers,racoons,racoon dogs food dead, victims of road traffic) according to EFSA's recommendation "Development of harmonised schemes for monitoring and reportig of rabies in animals inthe European Union"

Data source: NRL-Rabies as of 1.04.2017

4.12. Q-Fever

4.12.1. General evaluation of the situation

No information

4.12.2. Q-fever in humans

Not notifiable in Austria, therefore no data available

4.12.3. *Coxiella burnetii* in animals

Not notifiable in Austria

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

There is no official surveillance for *Coxiella burnetii* in animals.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

The diagnostic method is the complement fixation reaction, detecting phase 1 and phase 2 antigens. Organs are tested by real time PCR or immunohistochemistry (IHC) and swabs by real time PCR.

Vaccination policy

No vaccination.

Control programme/ mechanisms

The control programmes/ strategies in place

Nil

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Notification system in place

Q-fever in animals is not a notifiable disease

Results of the investigation

There is no official surveillance program therefore no representative results for Austria are available.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Q-fever in humans is not a notifiable disease. In Austria the number of sheep per holding is low (3.9 animals per holding in average) compared to countries that have a problem with Q-fever; therefore no change of the epidemiological situation in Austria is expected.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

Nil

5. Antimicrobial Resistance Information on Specific Zoonotic and Indicator Bacteria

Antimicrobial resistance is the ability of certain microorganisms to survive or grow in the presence of a given concentration of antimicrobial agent that usually would kill or inhibit the microorganism species in question. Antimicrobial resistant *Salmonella* strains may be transferred from animals or foodstuffs to humans.

5.1. *Salmonella*

5.1.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Resistance monitoring of faeces isolates from different slaughtered animals has been started in Austria in 2004. Since 2007, the monitoring of AMR in *Salmonella* from poultry (obtained from national control program) has been performed according to Commission Decision 2007/407/EC. The microdilution method applying ECOFFs was used for antimicrobial susceptibility testing (AST) of poultry-isolates. In 2014, the new legislation (CID 2013/652/EU) was implemented in Austria.

All human *Salmonella*-isolates have to be sent to the NRC-S for typing and AST. AST of all human isolates are performed in the disk diffusion tests using EUCAST-clinical breakpoints.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Humans: 1.480 isolates have been tested, 74.7% of those were susceptible to all antimicrobials tested. Ten percent of isolates were multiple resistant (to ≥ 3 antimicrobial classes). Highest resistance rates were found in *S. Typhimurium* (n = 182) to ampicillin, sulfonamides and tetracyclines (all 31%), in *S. Typhimurium*, monophasic strain (n = 61) to ampicillin, sulfonamides and tetracyclines (all 90%), and in *S. Infantis* (n = 68) to (fluoro-)chinolones, sulfonamides and tetracyclines (all 70%); eleven percent of 725 *S. Enteritidis* isolates showed resistances to (fluoro-)chinolones. Multiple resistances were found in 20% of *S. Typhimurium*, in 79% of ST monophasic strain, and in 62% of *S. Infantis*.

Broiler meat: 226 isolates have been tested, only 27.4% of those were susceptible to all antimicrobials tested. Multiple resistances were found in 66% of isolates. This is due to the fact that 160 isolates belong to the serovar *Infantis* showing resistance rates $>95\%$ to (fluoro-)chinolones, sulfonamides and tetracyclines. Multiple resistances were found in 91% of *S. Infantis* isolates. And out of 157 *Salmonella*-isolates from unspecified poultry meat 125 are *S. Infantis* presenting resistance rates of 100% to (fluoro-)chinolones, sulfonamides and tetracyclines (98% multi resistant).

Turkey meat: 43 isolates have been tested, 55.8% of those were susceptible to all antimicrobials tested, and 35% were multi resistant. Thirteen isolates were *S. Typhimurium*, all fully susceptible. Three of 7 *S. Infantis* showed the common resistance patterns (all multi resistant) and serovars other than SE, ST, SI, S. Thompson, S. Coeln, S. Senftenberg, and *S. Montevideo* (n = 18) showed high resistance rates to (fluoro)chinolones (90%), ampicillin (72%), and tetracyclines (67%), but no resistance to sulfonamides.

Carcases of broiler flocks: In 2016, *Salmonella* were isolated from 34 slaughter batches (36 isolates) in three abattoirs. Seven different serovars have been identified, in one slaughterhouse all isolates belonged to one serovar, *S. Infantis* (17-times); all these isolates showed resistance to chinolones, 15 also to tetracyclines and 14 isolates were multiple resistant (resistant to sulfonamides). All other isolates, *S. Montevideo* and *S. Coeln* (seven isolates each), *S. Agona* (two isolates) and *Salmonella* group C1, *S. Senftenberg*, and *S. Typhimurium* (one isolate each) were fully susceptible. Resistances to 3rd generation cephalosporines and colistin were not detected.

Carcases of turkey flocks: In 2016, in turkey abattoirs *Salmonella* were not detected in course of the process controls.

Laying hens: 46 isolate have been tested, seven isolates were non-wild types (non-WT; 15.2%; *S. Mbandaka* (three isolates), *S. Infantis* (two isolates), *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Muenchen* (one isolate each)). Two isolates showed multiple resistances (*S. Infantis*, resistant to chinolones, tetracyclines and sulfonamides). Interestingly, besides other serovars, one of the *S. Infantis*-isolates belonged to wild types (WT). Resistances to 3rd generation cephalosporines and colistin were not detected.

Broilers: 179 isolates have been tested, 98 isolates were non-WTs (54.8%; *S. Infantis* (96 isolates), *S. Agona* and *S. Thompson* (one isolate each)). Multiple resistances were detected in 92 isolates, in *S. Infantis* and one isolate of *S. Agona* (resistant to ampicillin, sulfonamides and trimethoprim). Interestingly, besides other serovars, ten of the *S. Infantis*-isolates belonged to wild types (WT). Resistances to 3rd generation cephalosporines and colistin were not detected.

Turkeys: Eleven isolates have been tested; five isolates were non-WTs (*S. Infantis* and *S. Stanley* (two isolates each) and *S. Coeln*). The two isolates of *S. Infantis* and the *S. Coeln*-isolate showed multiple resistances (resistant to chinolones, tetracyclines and sulfonamides or ampicillin, sulfonamides and tetracyclines). Interestingly, besides other serovars, one of the *S. Infantis*-isolates belonged to wild types (WT). Resistances to 3rd generation cephalosporines and colistin were not detected.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

The occurrence of certain *Salmonella* serovars and special antimicrobial resistance patterns in human cases concurrently with the finding of those types in food samples or animal samples can indicate the source of infection or the reservoir of the pathogen; further epidemiological investigation can be performed more targeted.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

The number of human salmonellosis cases is still decreasing therefor no recent actions were implemented. The National Action Plan to control antimicrobial resistance, published on the homepage of the Federal Ministry of Health and Women Affairs (http://www.bmgfi.gv.at/cms/home/attachments/9/2/1/CH1318/CMS1416214760260/nap_amr.pdf).

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil.

Additional information

Publication of the results in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria, 2016 (AURES 2016).

5.1.2. Antimicrobial resistance of *Salmonella* spp. isolates from humans

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In 2015 all 1,630 isolates from humans (primary, secondary isolates, from infected person without clinical signs) were tested in the National Reference Centre for *Salmonella* for their antimicrobial susceptibility using the diffusion test – or for certain isolates of special interest the ϵ -test – and applying EUCAST clinical breakpoints or if not available those from CLSI. To identify low-level resistance to ciprofloxacin, pefloxacin was tested; in suspicion of high-level resistance to ciprofloxacin the ϵ -test was performed.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Resistance rates increased in the last years. In 2015, resistance rates to certain antimicrobials (ampicillin, sulfonamides, tetracycline) were above 10%, or above 20% (quinolones). The reason for the increase in resistance rates is due to the higher incidence of multiresistant *S. Typhimurium*, *S. Infantis*, and *S. Kentucky* strains.

In 2015, 7 isolates showed resistance to 3rd-generation-cephalosporines, but no resistance to meropenem could be found.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

National Action Plan to control antimicrobial resistance

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Reconsider the target serovars in poultry and add new serovars of importance, e.g. those with (multi)resistant phenotypes

Additional information

Annual publication of the results in the NRC-S Report (Jahresbericht) and the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria (AURES)

5.1.3. Antimicrobial resistance of *Salmonella* spp. isolates from animals and food

A. Antimicrobial resistance of *Salmonella* spp. in poultry meat

Description of sampling designs

All poultry flocks were subjected to the the national control program, established in accordance with Article 5(1) of Regulation (EC) No 2160/2003 (see chapter *Salmonella* in animals). All *Salmonella* isolated from poultry flocks were typed and susceptibility tested using the disk diffusion test in the NRC-S.

B. Antimicrobial resistance of *Salmonella* spp. in poultry flocks

Description of sampling designs

All *Salmonella* isolated from poultry flocks (the flock is the epidemiological unit) at primary production of laying hens, broilers and fattening turkeys sampled in accordance with Article 5(1) of Regulation (EC) No 2160/2003, were sent to the NRC-S for typing and for antimicrobial susceptibility testing according to Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU.

Stratification procedures per animal populations and food categories

Per poultry population, all *Salmonella* isolates were subjected to antimicrobial susceptibility testing.

Randomisation procedures per animal populations and food categories

Per poultry population, all *Salmonella* isolates were subjected to antimicrobial susceptibility testing. The sampling was performed by the competent authorities or by the industry. The samples were taken at primary production at the farm. Laying hens were tested for the first time at the age of 22-26 weeks and following every 15 weeks, and all flocks (also broilers and turkeys) within the last 3 weeks prior to slaughter.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Frequency of the sampling

All flocks were subjected to sampling according to Article 5(1) of Regulation (EC) No 2160/2003 (census sampling). Laying hens were tested every 15 weeks and all poultry flocks within the last 3 weeks prior to slaughter.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Type of specimen taken

Environmental samples; For details see chapter "*Salmonella* in animals"

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

For details see chapter "*Salmonella* in animals"

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

All *Salmonella* spp. isolated were sent to the NRC-S where the susceptibility testing was performed using the micro-dilution-method (sensititre^R) in accordance with the Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU and the disk diffusion method.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Methods used for collecting data

Each sample taken at primary production was accompanied by an electronic order form from the Poultry Health Data (PHD).

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007

Laboratory used for detection for resistance - Antimicrobials included in monitoring

NRC-S: All isolates were subjected to susceptibility testing as described by the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI), which is accepted as an international reference method (ISO standard 20776-1:2006 (ISO, 2006)), as stated in Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU (Annex, Part A, Table 1, panel 1). In case of observed resistance to 3rd-generation-cephalosporines or meropenem the testing with panel 2 (Table 4) was performed.

Laboratory used for detection for resistance - Cut-off values used in testing

Application of European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (EUCAST) epidemiological cut-off values (ECOFFs) for the interpretation of microbiological resistance (as stated in CID 2013/652/EU).

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place

The control program is in line with the EU Commission and described in the National Action Plan (NAP) published on the homepage of the Federal Ministry of Health and Women's Affairs (http://www.bmgfj.gv.at/cms/home/attachments/9/2/1/CH1318/CMS1416214760260/nap_amr.pdf).

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

No measures foreseen in case of resistant isolates.

Notification system in place

No notification foreseen in case of resistant isolates.

Results of the investigation

In 2016, 236 isolates of *Salmonella* (25 different serovars) were susceptibility tested, 46 isolates from flocks of laying hens, 179 from flocks of broilers and 11 from flocks of turkeys. Resistances to 3rd generation cephalosporines and colistin were not detected.

From laying hens, seven isolates were non-wild types (non-WT; 15.2%; *S. Mbandaka* (three isolates), *S. Infantis* (two isolates), *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Muenchen* (one isolate each)). Two isolates showed multiple resistances (*S. Infantis*, resistant to chinolones, tetracyclines and sulfonamides). Interestingly, besides other serovars, one of the *S. Infantis*-isolates belonged to wild types (WT).

From broilers, 98 isolates were non-WTs (54.8%; *S. Infantis* (96 isolates), *S. Agona* and *S. Thompson* (one isolate each)). Multiple resistances were detected in 92 isolates, in *S. Infantis* and one isolate of *S. Agona* (resistant to ampicillin, sulfonamides and trimethoprim). Interestingly, besides other serovars, ten of the *S. Infantis*-isolates belonged to wild types (WT).

From turkeys, five isolates were non-WTs (*S. Infantis* and *S. Stanley* (two isolates each) and *S. Coeln*). The two isolates of *S. Infantis* and the *S. Coeln*-isolate showed multiple resistances (resistant to chinolones, tetracyclines and sulfonamides or ampicillin, sulfonamides and tetracyclines). Interestingly, besides other serovars, one of the *S. Infantis*-isolates belonged to wild types (WT).

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Poultry and their products (eggs, meat and meat products) are important sources of infections for humans.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Poultry and their products (eggs, meat and meat products) are important sources of infections for humans.

Additional information

Publication of the results in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria, 2016 (AURES 2016).

C. Antimicrobial resistance of *Salmonella* spp. from carcasses of broilers sampled according to Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005 (HACCP and own checks, objective sampling)

Description of sampling designs

All *Salmonella* from broiler slaughterhouses in accordance with point 2.1.4 of Chapter 2 of Annex I to Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005 were sent to the NRC-S for typing and for antimicrobial susceptibility testing according to Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU.

Stratification procedures per animal populations and food categories

Carcasses of broilers are sampled according to Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005 (HACCP and own checks, objective sampling).

Randomisation procedures per animal populations and food categories

Carcasses of broilers are sampled according to Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005 (HACCP and own checks, objective sampling).

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Frequency of the sampling

Carcasses of broilers are sampled according to Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005 (HACCP and own checks, objective sampling).

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Type of specimen taken

Carcasses of broilers are sampled according to Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005 (HACCP and own checks, objective sampling).

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Carcasses of broilers are sampled according to Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005 (HACCP and own checks, objective sampling).

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

All *Salmonella* spp. isolated were sent to the NRC-S where the susceptibility testing was performed using the micro-dilution-method (sensititre^R) in accordance to Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU and the disk diffusion method. According to Food Safety and Consumer Protection Law (Lebensmittelsicherheits- und Verbraucherschutzgesetz – LMSVG), Articles 38 (1) Z 6 (duties of the business operator) und § 74 (duties of the analyzing laboratories) all *Salmonella* isolated must be sent to the NRC-S.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Methods used for collecting data

The slaughterhouses collected the data and provided those to the NRC-S.

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007

Laboratory used for detection for resistance - Antimicrobials included in monitoring

NRC-S: All isolates were subjected to susceptibility testing as described by the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI), which is accepted as an international reference method (ISO standard 20776-1:2006 (ISO, 2006)), as stated in Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU (Annex, Part A, Table 1, panel 1). In case of observed resistance to 3rd-generation-cephalosporines or meropenem the testing with panel 2 (Table 4) was performed.

Laboratory used for detection for resistance - Cut-off values used in testing

Application of European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (EUCAST) epidemiological cut-off values (ECOFFs) for the interpretation of microbiological resistance (as stated in CID 2013/652/EU).

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place

The control program is in line with the EU Commission and described in the National Action Plan (NAP) published on the homepage of the Federal Ministry of Health

(http://www.bmgfj.gv.at/cms/home/attachments/9/2/1/CH1318/CMS1416214760260/nap_amr.pdf).

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

No measures foreseen in case of resistant isolates.

Notification system in place

No notification foreseen in case of resistant isolates.

Results of the investigation

In 2016, 115 slaughter batches from broilers fattened in Austria were sampled in four slaughter houses. *Salmonella* were isolated from 34 slaughter batches (36 isolates) in three abattoirs. Seven different serovars have been identified, in one slaughterhouse all isolates belonged to one serovar, *S. Infantis* (17-times); all these isolates showed resistance to chinolones, 15 also to tetracyclines and 14 isolates were multiple resistant (resistant to sulfonamides). All other isolates, *S. Montevideo* and *S. Coeln* (seven isolates each), *S. Agona* (two isolates) and *Salmonella* group C1, *S. Senftenberg*, and *S. Typhimurium* (one isolate each) were fully susceptible. Resistances to 3rd generation cephalosporines and colistin were not detected.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

All of the identified serovars play an important role as causative agents for human cases. Especially *S. Senftenberg* and *S. Coeln* emerged in the last years (two and ten human cases in 2012; 37 and 22 cases in 2016). Human cases caused by *S. Infantis* have been stable 40 and 60 cases per year).

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Broiler meat is an important source for infections in humans although the importance cannot be quantified.

Additional information

Publication of the results in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria, 2016 (AURES 2016).

D. Antimicrobial resistance of *Salmonella* spp. from carcasses of turkeys sampled according to Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005 (HACCP and own checks, objective sampling)

Description of sampling designs

All *Salmonella* from fattening turkey slaughterhouses in accordance with point 2.1.4 of Chapter 2 of Annex I to Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005 were sent to the NRC-S for typing and for antimicrobial susceptibility testing according to Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU.

Stratification procedures per animal populations and food categories

Carcasses of fattening turkeys are sampled according to Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005 (HACCP and own checks, objective sampling).

Randomisation procedures per animal populations and food categories

Carcasses of fattening turkeys are sampled according to Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005 (HACCP and own checks, objective sampling).

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Frequency of the sampling

Carcasses of fattening turkeys are sampled according to Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005 (HACCP and own checks, objective sampling).

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Type of specimen taken

Carcasses of fattening turkeys are sampled according to Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005 (HACCP and own checks, objective sampling).

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Carcasses of fattening turkeys are sampled according to Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005 (HACCP and own checks, objective sampling).

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

All *Salmonella* spp. isolated were sent to the NRC-S where the susceptibility testing was performed using the micro-dilution-method (sensititre^R) in accordance with the Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU and the disk diffusion method. According to Food Safety and Consumer Protection Law (Lebensmittelsicherheits- und Verbraucherschutzgesetz – LMSVG), Articles 38 (1) Z 6 (duties of the business operator) und § 74 (duties of the analyzing laboratories) all *Salmonella* isolated must be sent to the NRC-S.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Methods used for collecting data

The slaughterhouses collected the data and provided those to the NRC-S.

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007

Laboratory used for detection for resistance - Antimicrobials included in monitoring

NRC-S: All isolates were subjected to susceptibility testing as described by the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI), which is accepted as an international reference method (ISO standard 20776-1:2006 (ISO, 2006)), as stated in Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU (Annex, Part A, Table 1, panel 1). In case of observed resistance to 3rd-generation-cephalosporines or meropenem the testing with panel 2 (Table 4) was performed.

Laboratory used for detection for resistance - Cut-off values used in testing

Application of European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (EUCAST) epidemiological cut-off values (ECOFFs) for the interpretation of microbiological resistance (as stated in CID 2013/652/EU).

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place

The control program is in line with the EU Commission and described in the National Action Plan (NAP) published on the homepage of the Federal Ministry of Health (http://www.bmgfj.gv.at/cms/home/attachments/9/2/1/CH1318/CMS1416214760260/nap_amr.pdf).

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

No measures foreseen in case of resistant isolates.

Notification system in place

No measures foreseen in case of resistant isolates.

Results of the investigation

In 2016, 103 slaughter batches from turkeys fattened in Austria were sampled in two slaughter houses. *Salmonella* were not detected in course of the process controls.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In the last years, *S. Stanley* transmitted via imported turkey meat caused outbreaks in Austria, although in 2016 the number of human cases decreased (19 cases).

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

In 2016, *Salmonella* were only found in ten turkey flocks but not in turkey slaughter houses; national produced turkey meat seems not important as source for human infections.

Additional information

Publication of the results in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria, 2016 (AURES 2016).

Table 51 Breakpoints for antibiotic resistance of *Salmonella* sp., 2016

antimicrobial	ECOFF	Range tested		zone diameter	
	concentration (µg/ml)			(mm)	
	wild type <=	lowest	highest	resistant <=	
panel 1	aminoglycosids - gentamicin	2	0.5	32	13
	amphenicols - chloramphenicol	16	8	128	16
	carbapenems - meropenem	0.12	0.03	16	15
	cephalosporines - cefotaxime	0.5	0.25	4	16
	cephalosporines - ceftazidime	2	0.5	8	18
	fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	0.06	0.016	8	23
	glycylcyclines - tigecycline	1	0.25	8	14
	macrolides - azithromycin	16	2	64	-
	penicillins - ampicillin	8	1	64	13
	polymyxins - colistin	2	1	16	-
	quinolones - nalidixic acid	16	4	128	13
	sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	256	8	1024	12
	tetracyclines - tetracycline	8	2	64	11
	trimethoprim	2	0.25	32	14
panel 2	carbapenems - ertapenem	0.06	0.016	2	21
	carbapenems - imipenem	1	0.12	16	15
	carbapenems - meropenem	0.12	0.03	16	15
	cephalosporines - cefepim	0.12	0.06	32	20
	cephalosporines - cefotaxime	0.5	0.25	64	16
	cephalosporines - ceftaxitin	8	0.5	64	18
	cephalosporines - ceftazidime	2	0.25	128	18
	clavulanate synergy with cefotaxime	*	0.06	64	***
	clavulanate synergy with ceftazidime	**	0.12	128	****
	penicillins, extended-spectrum - temocillin	32	0.5	128	-

presumptive ESBL: *CTX/CTXCL >= 8 **CAZ/CAZCL >= 8 *** Ø CTXCL at least 5mm > Ø CTX **** Ø CAZCL at least 5mm > Ø CAZ

Number of fully-susceptible and number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 or >4 antimicrobials of different classes, excluding cross-resistance. For *Salmonella* this includes resistance to ampicillin, cefotaxime/ceftazidime, meropenem, ciprofloxacin/nalidixic acid, tetracycline, gentamicin, colistin, trimethoprim, sulfonamides, chloramphenicol, tigecycline.

Table 52 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Salmonella* spp. in humans, meat and poultry flocks, 2016

<i>Salmonella</i> spp.	humans			broiler meat			turkey meat			poultry meat (unspec.)			pork			beef			broiler carcasses			layer flocks			broiler flocks			turkey flocks		
number of isolates	1,480			226			43			157			11			2			36			46			179			11		
antimicrobial	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		micro-biological resistant									
	N	%R		n	N		%R	n		N	%R		n	N		%R	n		N	%R		n	N		%R	n		N	%R	
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	1,480	1.2	18	226	0.0	0	43	0.0	0	157	0.0	0	11	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	36	0.0	0	46	0.0	0	179	0.0	0	11	0.0	0
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	1,480	2.4	35	226	0.4	1	43	0.0	0	157	0.6	1	11	9.1	1	2	0.0	0	36	0.0	0	46	0.0	0	179	0.0	0	11	0.0	0
carbapenems - meropenem	1,480	0.0	0	226	0.0	0	43	0.0	0	157	0.0	0	11	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	36	0.0	0	46	0.0	0	179	0.0	0	11	0.0	0
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	1,480	0.5	8	226	0.0	0	43	0.0	0	157	0.0	0	11	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	36	0.0	0	46	0.0	0	179	0.0	0	11	0.0	0
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	1,480	0.5	7	226	0.0	0	43	0.0	0	157	0.0	0	11	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	36	0.0	0	46	0.0	0	179	0.0	0	11	0.0	0
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	1,480	14.3	212	226	72.1	163	43	44.2	19	157	87.9	138	11	45.5	5	2	100	2	36	47.2	17	46	6.5	3	179	53.6	96	11	36.4	4
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	1,480	0.0	0	226	0.0	0	43	0.0	0	157	0.0	0	11	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	36	0.0	0	46	0.0	0	179	0.0	0	11	0.0	0
macrolides - azithromycin	1,480	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	36	0.0	0	46	0.0	0	179	0.0	0	11	0.0	0
penicillins - ampicillin	1,480	12.6	186	226	4.4	10	43	30.2	13	157	3.8	6	11	54.5	6	2	0.0	0	36	0.0	0	46	0.0	0	179	1.7	3	11	9.1	1
polymyxins - colistin	1,480	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	36	0.0	0	46	0.0	0	179	0.0	0	11	0.0	0
quinolones - nalidixic acid	1,480	13.2	195	226	71.7	162	43	41.9	18	157	87.3	137	11	45.5	5	2	100	2	36	47.2	17	46	6.5	3	179	53.6	96	11	36.4	4
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	1,480	14.8	219	226	68.1	154	43	7.0	3	157	79.6	125	11	54.5	6	2	100	2	36	41.7	15	46	4.3	2	179	53.6	96	11	27.3	3
tetracyclines - tetracycline	1,480	14.9	221	226	69.5	157	43	34.9	15	157	80.9	127	11	36.4	4	2	100	2	36	41.7	15	46	13	6	179	53.6	96	11	27.3	3
trimethoprim	1,480	2.6	39	226	1.3	3	43	0.0	0	157	1.3	2	11	18.2	2	2	0.0	0	36	0.0	0	46	0.0	0	179	0.6	1	11	0.0	0
multiresistant isolates	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n
fully sensitive	1,480	74.7	1,106	226	27.4	62	43	55.8	24	157	11.5	18	11	18.2	2	2	0.0	0	36	52.8	19	46	84.4	39	179	45.3	81	11	54.5	6
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	1,480	9.1	135	226	2.2	5	43	7.0	3	157	6.4	10	11	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	36	5.6	2	46	10.9	5	179	0.6	1	11	18.2	2
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	1,480	1.8	27	226	1.3	3	43	2.3	1	157	0.6	1	11	36.4	4	2	0.0	0	36	0.0	0	46	0	0	179	0.6	1	11	0	0
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	1,480	10.0	148	226	65.9	149	43	34.9	15	157	80.9	127	11	36.4	4	2	100	2	36	41.7	15	46	4.3	2	179	53.1	95	11	27.3	3
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	1,480	2.1	31	226	2.7	6	43	0.0	0	157	0.0	0	11	9.1	1	2	0.0	0	36	0.0	0	46	0	0	179	0.6	1	11	0	0
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	1,480	2.2	33	226	0.4	1	43	0.0	0	157	0.6	1	11	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	36	0.0	0	46	0	0	179	0.0	0	11	0	0

CAVE: Isolates from humans, broiler meat, turkey meat, poultry meat (unspec.), pork and beef were AST using the disk diffusion test applying EUCAST clinical breakpoints, whereas for isolates from broiler carcasses, layer flocks, broiler flocks and turkey flocks the microbilution method applying ECOFFs was used.

Table 53 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Enteritidis* in humans, meat and poultry flocks, 2016

<i>S. Enteritidis</i>	humans			broiler meat			turkey meat			poultry meat (unspec.)			pork			beef			broiler carcasses			layer flocks			broiler flocks			turkey flocks		
number of isolates	725			2			1			2			0			0			0			10			2			3		
antimicrobial	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		micro-biological	resistant	total units tested		micro-biological	resistant	total units tested		micro-biological	resistant
	N	%R		n	N		%R	n		N	%R		n	N		%R	n		N	%R			n	N			%R	n		
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	725	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	1	0.0	0	2	0.0	0							-	-	-	10	0	0	2	0	0	3	0	0
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	725	0.4	3	2	0.0	0	1	0.0	0	2	0.0	0							-	-	-	10	0	0	2	0	0	3	0	0
carbapenems - meropenem	725	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	1	0.0	0	2	0.0	0							-	-	-	10	0	0	2	0	0	3	0	0
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	725	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	1	0.0	0	2	0.0	0							-	-	-	10	0	0	2	0	0	3	0	0
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	725	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	1	0.0	0	2	0.0	0							-	-	-	10	0	0	2	0	0	3	0	0
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	725	10.9	79	2	0.0	0	1	0.0	0	2	50.0	1							-	-	-	10	10	1	2	0	0	3	0	0
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	725	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	1	0.0	0	2	0.0	0							-	-	-	10	0	0	2	0	0	3	0	0
macrolides - azithromycin																			-	-	-	10	0	0	2	0	0	3	0	0
penicillins - ampicillin	725	1.5	11	2	0.0	0	1	0.0	0	2	0.0	0							-	-	-	10	0	0	2	0	0	3	0	0
polymyxins - colistin																			-	-	-	10	0	0	2	0	0	3	0	0
quinolones - nalidixic acid	725	11.0	80	2	0.0	0	1	0.0	0	2	0.0	0							-	-	-	10	10	1	2	0	0	3	0	0
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	725	1.0	7	2	0.0	0	1	0.0	0	2	0.0	0							-	-	-	10	0	0	2	0	0	3	0	0
tetracyclines - tetracycline	725	1.1	8	2	0.0	0	1	0.0	0	2	0.0	0							-	-	-	10	0	0	2	0	0	3	0	0
trimethoprim	725	0.4	3	2	0.0	0	1	0.0	0	2	0.0	0							-	-	-	10	0	0	2	0	0	3	0	0
multiresistant isolates	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n
fully sensitive	725	87.3	633	2	100	2	1	100	1	2	50.0	1							-	-	-	10	90	9	2	100	2	3	100	3
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	725	11.3	82	2	0.0	0	1	0.0	0	2	50.0	1							-	-	-	10	10	1	2	0	0	3	0	0
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	725	0.6	4	2	0.0	0	1	0.0	0	2	0.0	0							-	-	-	10	0	0	2	0	0	3	0	0
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	725	0.4	3	2	0.0	0	1	0.0	0	2	0.0	0							-	-	-	10	0	0	2	0	0	3	0	0
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	725	0.3	2	2	0.0	0	1	0.0	0	2	0.0	0							-	-	-	10	0	0	2	0	0	3	0	0
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	725	0.1	1	2	0.0	0	1	0.0	0	2	0.0	0							-	-	-	10	0	0	2	0	0	3	0	0

CAVE: Isolates from humans, broiler meat, turkey meat, poultry meat (unspec.), pork and beef were AST using the disk diffusion test applying EUCAST clinical breakpoints, whereas for isolates from broiler carcasses, layer flocks, broiler flocks and turkey flocks the microbilution method applying ECOFFs was used.

Table 54 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Typhimurium* in humans, meat and poultry flocks, 2016

<i>S. Typhimurium</i>	humans			broiler meat			turkey meat			poultry meat (unspec.)			pork			beef			broiler carcasses			layer flocks			broiler flocks			turkey flocks		
number of isolates	182			5			13			0			2			0			1			4			5			0		
antimicrobial	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		micro-biological	resistant	total units tested		micro-biological	resistant	total units tested		micro-biological	resistant
	N	%R		n	N		%R	n		N	%R		n	N		%R	n		N	%R			n	N			%R	n		
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	182	1.6	3	5	0.0	0	13	0.0	0				2	0.0	0				1	0	0	4	0	0	5	0	0	-	-	-
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	182	7.7	14	5	0.0	0	13	0.0	0				2	0.0	0				1	0	0	4	0	0	5	0	0	-	-	-
carbapenems - meropenem	182	0.0	0	5	0.0	0	13	0.0	0				2	0.0	0				1	0	0	4	0	0	5	0	0	-	-	-
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	182	2.2	4	5	0.0	0	13	0.0	0				2	0.0	0				1	0	0	4	0	0	5	0	0	-	-	-
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	182	2.2	4	5	0.0	0	13	0.0	0				2	0.0	0				1	0	0	4	0	0	5	0	0	-	-	-
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	182	7.1	13	5	0.0	0	13	0.0	0				2	0.0	0				1	0	0	4	0	0	5	0	0	-	-	-
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	182	0.0	0	5	0.0	0	13	0.0	0				2	0.0	0				1	0	0	4	0	0	5	0	0	-	-	-
macrolides - azithromycin																			1	0	0	4	0	0	5	0	0	-	-	-
penicillins - ampicillin	182	31.9	58	5	20.0	1	13	0.0	0				2	100	2				1	0	0	4	0	0	5	0	0	-	-	-
polymyxins - colistin																			1	0	0	4	0	0	5	0	0	-	-	-
quinolones - nalidixic acid	182	5.5	10	5	0.0	0	13	0.0	0				2	0.0	0				1	0	0	4	0	0	5	0	0	-	-	-
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	182	33.0	60	5	20.0	1	13	0.0	0				2	100	2				1	0	0	4	0	0	5	0	0	-	-	-
tetracyclines - tetracycline	182	32.4	59	5	20.0	1	13	0.0	0				2	100	2				1	0	0	4	0	0	5	0	0	-	-	-
trimethoprim	182	4.4	8	5	0.0	0	13	0.0	0				2	0.0	0				1	0	0	4	0	0	5	0	0	-	-	-
multiresistant isolates	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n
fully sensitive	182	59.3	108	5	80.0	4	13	100	13				2	0.0	0				1	100	1	4	100	4	5	100	5	-	-	-
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	182	7.1	13	5	0.0	0	13	0.0	0				2	0.0	0				1	0	0	4	0	0	5	0	0	-	-	-
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	182	3.3	6	5	0.0	0	13	0.0	0				2	0.0	0				1	0	0	4	0	0	5	0	0	-	-	-
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	182	20.3	37	5	20.0	1	13	0.0	0				2	100	2				1	0	0	4	0	0	5	0	0	-	-	-
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	182	6.0	11	5	0.0	0	13	0.0	0				2	0.0	0				1	0	0	4	0	0	5	0	0	-	-	-
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	182	3.8	7	5	0.0	0	13	0.0	0				2	0.0	0				1	0	0	4	0	0	5	0	0	-	-	-

CAVE: Isolates from humans, broiler meat, turkey meat, poultry meat (unspec.), pork and beef were AST using the disk diffusion test applying EUCAST clinical breakpoints, whereas for isolates from broiler carcasses, layer flocks, broiler flocks and turkey flocks the microbilution method applying ECOFFs was used.

Table 55 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Typhimurium* monophasic strain in humans, meat and poultry flocks, 2016

<i>S. Typhimurium</i> , monophasic	humans			broiler meat			turkey meat			poultry meat (unspec.)			pork			beef			broiler carcasses			layer flocks			broiler flocks			turkey flocks				
number of isolates	61			0			0			0			0			0			0			0			0			0				
antimicrobial	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		micro-biological	resistant	total units tested		micro-biological	resistant	total units tested		micro-biological	resistant		
	N	%R		n	N		%R	n		N	%R		n	N		%R	n		N	%R			n	N			%R	n			N	%R
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	61	3.3	2																													
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	61	4.9	3																													
carbapenems - meropenem	61	0.0	0																													
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	61	0.0	0																													
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	61	0.0	0																													
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	61	8.2	5																													
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	61	0.0	0																													
macrolides - azithromycin																																
penicillins - ampicillin	61	95.1	58																													
polymyxins - colistin																																
quinolones - nalidixic acid	61	4.9	3																													
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	61	90.2	55																													
tetracyclines - tetracycline	61	90.2	55																													
trimethoprim	61	3.3	2																													
multiresistant isolates	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n		
fully sensitive	61	3.3	2																													
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	61	1.6	1																													
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	61	6.6	4																													
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	61	78.7	48																													
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	61	6.6	4																													
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	61	3.3	2																													

CAVE: Isolates from humans, broiler meat, turkey meat, poultry meat (unspec.), pork and beef were AST using the disk diffusion test applying EUCAST clinical breakpoints, whereas for isolates from broiler carcasses, layer flocks, broiler flocks and turkey flocks the microbilution method applying ECOFFs was used.

Table 56 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Infantis* in humans, meat and poultry flocks, 2016

<i>S. Infantis</i>	humans			broiler meat			turkey meat			poultry meat (unspec.)			pork			beef			broiler carcasses			layer flocks			broiler flocks			turkey flocks						
number of isolates	68			160			7			125			2			2			17			3			104			3						
antimicrobial	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		micro-biological	resistant	total units tested		micro-biological	resistant	total units tested		micro-biological	resistant	total units tested		micro-biological	resistant
	N	%R		n	N		%R	n		N	%R		n	N		%R	n		N	%R			n	N			%R	n			N	%R		
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	68	4.4	3	160	0.0	0	7	0.0	0	125	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	17	0	0	3	0	0	104	0	0	3	0	0	3	0	0	
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	68	0.0	0	160	0.6	1	7	0.0	0	125	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	17	0	0	3	0	0	104	0	0	3	0	0	3	0	0	
carbapenems - meropenem	68	0.0	0	160	0.0	0	7	0.0	0	125	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	17	0	0	3	0	0	104	0	0	3	0	0	3	0	0	
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	68	2.9	2	160	0.0	0	7	0.0	0	125	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	17	0	0	3	0	0	104	0	0	3	0	0	3	0	0	
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	68	1.5	1	160	0.0	0	7	0.0	0	125	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	17	0	0	3	0	0	104	0	0	3	0	0	3	0	0	
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	68	73.5	50	160	99.4	159	7	42.9	3	125	100	125	2	100	2	2	100	2	17	100	17	3	66.7	2	104	92.3	96	3	66.7	2				
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	68	0.0	0	160	0.0	0	7	0.0	0	125	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	17	0	0	3	0	0	104	0	0	3	0	0				
macrolides - azithromycin																			17	0	0	3	0	0	104	0	0	3	0	0				
penicillins - ampicillin	68	5.9	4	160	3.1	5	7	0.0	0	125	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	17	0	0	3	0	0	104	1.0	1	3	0	0				
polymyxins - colistin																			17	0	0	3	0	0	104	0	0	3	0	0				
quinolones - nalidixic acid	68	72.1	49	160	99.4	159	7	42.9	3	125	100	125	2	100	2	2	100	2	17	100	17	3	66.7	2	104	92.3	96	3	66.7	2				
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	68	69.1	47	160	95.6	153	7	42.9	3	125	98.4	123	2	100	2	2	100	2	17	88.2	15	3	66.7	2	104	91.3	95	3	66.7	2				
tetracyclines - tetracycline	68	69.1	47	160	96.3	154	7	42.9	3	125	98.4	123	2	100	2	2	100	2	17	88.2	15	3	66.7	2	104	92.3	96	3	66.7	2				
trimethoprim	68	2.9	2	160	1.9	3	7	0.0	0	125	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	17	0	0	3	0	0	104	0	0	3	0	0				
multiresistant isolates	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	
fully sensitive	68	26.5	18	160	0.6	1	7	57.1	4	125	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	17	0	0	3	33.3	1	104	7.7	8	3	33.3	1				
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	68	2.9	2	160	3.1	5	7	0.0	0	125	1.6	2	2	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	17	11.8	2	3	0	0	104	0	0	3	0	0				
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	68	1.5	1	160	0.6	1	7	0.0	0	125	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	17	0.0	0	3	0	0	104	1.0	1	3	0	0				
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	68	61.8	42	160	91.3	146	7	42.9	3	125	98.4	123	2	100	2	2	100	2	17	88.2	15	3	66.7	2	104	90.4	94	3	66.7	2				
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	68	4.4	3	160	3.8	6	7	0.0	0	125	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	17	0	0	3	0	0	104	1.0	1	3	0	0				
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	68	2.9	2	160	0.6	1	7	0.0	0	125	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	17	0	0	3	0	0	104	0	0	3	0	0				

CAVE: Isolates from humans, broiler meat, turkey meat, poultry meat (unspec.), pork and beef were AST using the disk diffusion test applying EUCAST clinical breakpoints, whereas for isolates from broiler carcasses, layer flocks, broiler flocks and turkey flocks the microbilution method applying ECOFFs was used.

Table 57 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Thompson* in humans, meat and poultry flocks, 2016

<i>S. Thompson</i>	humans			broiler meat			turkey meat			poultry meat (unspec.)			pork			beef			broiler carcasses			layer flocks			broiler flocks			turkey flocks					
number of isolates	17			2			0			2			0			0			0			3			31			1					
antimicrobial	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		micro-biological	resistant	total units tested		micro-biological	resistant	total units tested		micro-biological	resistant			
	N	%R		n	N		%R	n		N	%R		n	N		%R	n		N	%R			n	N			%R	n			N	%R	n
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	17	0.0	0	2	0.0	0				2	0.0	0							-	-	-	3	0	0	31	0	0	1	0	0			
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	17	0.0	0	2	0.0	0				2	0.0	0							-	-	-	3	0	0	31	0	0	1	0	0			
carbapenems - meropenem	17	0.0	0	2	0.0	0				2	0.0	0							-	-	-	3	0	0	31	0	0	1	0	0			
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	17	0.0	0	2	0.0	0				2	0.0	0							-	-	-	3	0	0	31	0	0	1	0	0			
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	17	0.0	0	2	0.0	0				2	0.0	0							-	-	-	3	0	0	31	0	0	1	0	0			
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	17	0.0	0	2	0.0	0				2	0.0	0							-	-	-	3	0	0	31	0	0	1	0	0			
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	17	0.0	0	2	0.0	0				2	0.0	0							-	-	-	3	0	0	31	0	0	1	0	0			
macrolides - azithromycin																			-	-	-	3	0	0	31	0	0	1	0	0			
penicillins - ampicillin	17	0.0	0	2	0.0	0				2	0.0	0							-	-	-	3	0	0	31	3.2	1	1	1	0	0		
polymyxins - colistin																			-	-	-	3	0	0	31	0	0	1	0	0			
quinolones - nalidixic acid	17	0.0	0	2	0.0	0				2	0.0	0							-	-	-	3	0	0	31	0	0	1	0	0			
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	17	0.0	0	2	0.0	0				2	0.0	0							-	-	-	3	0	0	31	0	0	1	0	0			
tetracyclines - tetracycline	17	0.0	0	2	0.0	0				2	0.0	0							-	-	-	3	0	0	31	0	0	1	0	0			
trimethoprim	17	0.0	0	2	0.0	0				2	0.0	0							-	-	-	3	0	0	31	0	0	1	0	0			
multiresistant isolates	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n
fully sensitive	17	100	17	2	100	2				2	100	2							-	-	-	3	100	3	31	97	30	1	100	1			
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	17	0.0	0	2	0.0	0				2	0.0	0							-	-	-	3	0	0	31	3.2	1	1	1	0	0		
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	17	0.0	0	2	0.0	0				2	0.0	0							-	-	-	3	0	0	31	0	0	1	0	0			
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	17	0.0	0	2	0.0	0				2	0.0	0							-	-	-	3	0	0	31	0	0	1	0	0			
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	17	0.0	0	2	0.0	0				2	0.0	0							-	-	-	3	0	0	31	0	0	1	0	0			
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	17	0.0	0	2	0.0	0				2	0.0	0							-	-	-	3	0	0	31	0	0	1	0	0			

CAVE: Isolates from humans, broiler meat, turkey meat, poultry meat (unspec.), pork and beef were AST using the disk diffusion test applying EUCAST clinical breakpoints, whereas for isolates from broiler carcasses, layer flocks, broiler flocks and turkey flocks the microbilution method applying ECOFFs was used.

Table 58 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Coeln* in humans, meat and poultry flocks, 2016

<i>S. Coeln</i>	humans			broiler meat			turkey meat			poultry meat (unspec.)			pork			beef			broiler carcasses			layer flocks			broiler flocks			turkey flocks						
number of isolates	23			28			2			13			0			0			7			0			5			1						
antimicrobial	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		micro-biological	resistant	total units tested		micro-biological	resistant	total units tested		micro-biological	resistant	total units tested		micro-biological	resistant
	N	%R		n	N		%R	n		N	%R		n	N		%R	n		N	%R			n	N			%R	n			N	%R		
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	23	0.0	0	28	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	13	0.0	0										7	0	0	-	-	-	5	0	0	1	0	0	
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	23	0.0	0	28	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	13	0.0	0										7	0	0	-	-	-	5	0	0	1	0	0	
carbapenems - meropenem	23	0.0	0	28	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	13	0.0	0										7	0	0	-	-	-	5	0	0	1	0	0	
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	23	0.0	0	28	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	13	0.0	0										7	0	0	-	-	-	5	0	0	1	0	0	
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	23	0.0	0	28	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	13	0.0	0										7	0	0	-	-	-	5	0	0	1	0	0	
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	23	0.0	0	28	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	13	0.0	0										7	0	0	-	-	-	5	0	0	1	0	0	
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	23	0.0	0	28	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	13	0.0	0										7	-	-	-	-	-	5	0	0	1	0	0	
macrolides - azithromycin																						7	0	0	-	-	-	5	0	0	1	0	0	
penicillins - ampicillin	23	0.0	0	28	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	13	0.0	0										7	0	0	-	-	-	5	0	0	1	100	1	
polymyxins - colistin																						7	0	0	-	-	-	5	0	0	1	0	0	
quinolones - nalidixic acid	23	0.0	0	28	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	13	0.0	0										7	0	0	-	-	-	5	0	0	1	0	0	
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	23	0.0	0	28	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	13	0.0	0										7	0	0	-	-	-	5	0	0	1	100	1	
tetracyclines - tetracycline	23	0.0	0	28	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	13	0.0	0										7	0	0	-	-	-	5	0	0	1	100	1	
trimethoprim	23	0.0	0	28	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	13	0.0	0										7	0	0	-	-	-	5	0	0	1	0	0	
multiresistant isolates	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	
fully sensitive	23	100	23	28	100	28	2	100	2	13	100	13										7	100	7	-	-	-	5	100	5	1	0	0	
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	23	0.0	0	28	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	13	0.0	0										7	0	0	-	-	-	5	0	0	1	0	0	
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	23	0.0	0	28	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	13	0.0	0										7	0	0	-	-	-	5	0	0	1	0	0	
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	23	0.0	0	28	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	13	0.0	0										7	0	0	-	-	-	5	0	0	1	100	1	
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	23	0.0	0	28	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	13	0.0	0										7	0	0	-	-	-	5	0	0	1	0	0	
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	23	0.0	0	28	0.0	0	2	0.0	0	13	0.0	0										7	0	0	-	-	-	5	0	0	1	0	0	

CAVE: Isolates from humans, broiler meat, turkey meat, poultry meat (unspec.), pork and beef were AST using the disk diffusion test applying EUCAST clinical breakpoints, whereas for isolates from broiler carcasses, layer flocks, broiler flocks and turkey flocks the microbilution method applying ECOFFs was used.

Table 59 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Senftenberg* in humans, meat and poultry flocks, 2016

<i>S. Senftenberg</i>	humans			broiler meat			turkey meat			poultry meat (unspec.)			pork			beef			broiler carcasses			layer flocks			broiler flocks			turkey flocks						
number of isolates	43			5			0			0			0			0			1			1			6			0						
antimicrobial	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		micro-biological	resistant	total units tested		micro-biological	resistant	total units tested		micro-biological	resistant	total units tested		micro-biological	resistant
	N	%R		n	N		%R	n		N	%R		n	N		%R	n		N	%R			n	N			%R	n			N	%R		
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	43	0.0	0	5	0.0	0														1	0	0	1	0	0	6	0	0	-	-	-			
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	43	0.0	0	5	0.0	0														1	0	0	1	0	0	6	0	0	-	-	-			
carbapenems - meropenem	43	0.0	0	5	0.0	0														1	0	0	1	0	0	6	0	0	-	-	-			
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	43	0.0	0	5	0.0	0														1	0	0	1	0	0	6	0	0	-	-	-			
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	43	0.0	0	5	0.0	0														1	0	0	1	0	0	6	0	0	-	-	-			
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	43	2.3	1	5	0.0	0														1	0	0	1	0	0	6	0	0	-	-	-			
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	43	0.0	0	5	0.0	0														1	-	-	1	0	0	6	0	0	-	-	-			
macrolides - azithromycin																				1	0	0	1	0	0	6	0	0	-	-	-			
penicillins - ampicillin	43	0.0	0	5	0.0	0														1	0	0	1	0	0	6	0	0	-	-	-			
polymyxins - colistin																				1	0	0	1	0	0	6	0	0	-	-	-			
quinolones - nalidixic acid	43	2.3	1	5	0.0	0														1	0	0	1	0	0	6	0	0	-	-	-			
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	43	2.3	1	5	0.0	0														1	0	0	1	0	0	6	0	0	-	-	-			
tetracyclines - tetracycline	43	2.3	1	5	0.0	0														1	0	0	1	0	0	6	0	0	-	-	-			
trimethoprim	43	2.3	1	5	0.0	0														1	0	0	1	0	0	6	0	0	-	-	-			
multiresistant isolates	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	
fully sensitive	43	97.7	42	5	100	5														1	100	1	1	100	1	6	100	6	-	-	-			
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	43	0.0	0	5	0.0	0														1	0	0	1	0	0	6	0	0	-	-	-			
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	43	0.0	0	5	0.0	0														1	0	0	1	0	0	6	0	0	-	-	-			
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	43	0.0	0	5	0.0	0														1	0	0	1	0	0	6	0	0	-	-	-			
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	43	2.3	1	5	0.0	0														1	0	0	1	0	0	6	0	0	-	-	-			
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	43	0.0	0	5	0.0	0														1	0	0	1	0	0	6	0	0	-	-	-			

CAVE: Isolates from humans, broiler meat, turkey meat, poultry meat (unspec.), pork and beef were AST using the disk diffusion test applying EUCAST clinical breakpoints, whereas for isolates from broiler carcasses, layer flocks, broiler flocks and turkey flocks the microbilution method applying ECOFFs was used.

Table 60 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Montevideo* in humans, meat and poultry flocks, 2016

<i>S. Montevideo</i>	humans			broiler meat			turkey meat			poultry meat (unspec.)			pork			beef			broiler carcasses			layer flocks			broiler flocks			turkey flocks						
number of isolates	2			3			2			0			0			0			7			2			10			0						
antimicrobial	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		micro-biological	resistant	total units tested		micro-biological	resistant	total units tested		micro-biological	resistant	total units tested		micro-biological	resistant
	N	%R		n	N		%R	n		N	%R		n	N		%R	n		N	%R			n	N			%R	n			N	%R		
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	2	0.0	0	3	0.0	0	2	0.0	0													7	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	-	-	-	
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	2	0.0	0	3	0.0	0	2	0.0	0													7	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	-	-	-	
carbapenems - meropenem	2	0.0	0	3	0.0	0	2	0.0	0													7	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	-	-	-	
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	2	0.0	0	3	0.0	0	2	0.0	0													7	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	-	-	-	
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	2	0.0	0	3	0.0	0	2	0.0	0													7	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	-	-	-	
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	2	0.0	0	3	0.0	0	2	0.0	0													7	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	-	-	-	
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	2	0.0	0	3	0.0	0	2	0.0	0													7	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	-	-	-	
macrolides - azithromycin																						7	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	-	-	-	
penicillins - ampicillin	2	0.0	0	3	0.0	0	2	0.0	0													7	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	-	-	-	
polymyxins - colistin																						7	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	-	-	-	
quinolones - nalidixic acid	2	0.0	0	3	0.0	0	2	0.0	0													7	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	-	-	-	
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	2	0.0	0	3	0.0	0	2	0.0	0													7	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	-	-	-	
tetracyclines - tetracycline	2	0.0	0	3	0.0	0	2	0.0	0													7	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	-	-	-	
trimethoprim	2	0.0	0	3	0.0	0	2	0.0	0													7	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	-	-	-	
multiresistant isolates	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	
fully sensitive	2	100	2	3	100	3	2	100	2													7	100	7	2	100	2	10	100	10	-	-	-	
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	2	0.0	0	3	0.0	0	2	0.0	0													7	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	-	-	-	
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	2	0.0	0	3	0.0	0	2	0.0	0													7	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	-	-	-	
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	2	0.0	0	3	0.0	0	2	0.0	0													7	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	-	-	-	
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	2	0.0	0	3	0.0	0	2	0.0	0													7	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	-	-	-	
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	2	0.0	0	3	0.0	0	2	0.0	0													7	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	-	-	-	

CAVE: Isolates from humans, broiler meat, turkey meat, poultry meat (unspec.), pork and beef were AST using the disk diffusion test applying EUCAST clinical breakpoints, whereas for isolates from broiler carcasses, layer flocks, broiler flocks and turkey flocks the microbilution method applying ECOFFs was used.

Table 61 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of other serotypes than mentioned before in humans, meat and poultry flocks, 2016

<i>Salmonella</i> other serotypes	humans			broiler meat			turkey meat			poultry meat (unspec.)			pork			beef			broiler carcasses			layer flocks			broiler flocks			turkey flocks			
number of isolates	359			21			18			15			7			0			3			23			16			3			
antimicrobial	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		resistant	total units tested		micro-biological	resistant	total units tested		micro-biological	resistant	total units tested		micro-biological	resistant	
	N	%R		n	N		%R	n		N	%R		n	N		%R	n		N	%R			n	N			%R	n			N
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	359	2.8	10	21	0.0	0	18	0.0	0	15	0.0	0	7	0.0	0					3	0	0	23	0	0	16	0	0	3	0	0
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	359	4.2	15	21	0.0	0	18	0.0	0	15	6.7	1	7	14.3	1					3	0	0	23	0	0	16	0	0	3	0	0
carbapenems - meropenem	359	0.0	0	21	0.0	0	18	0.0	0	15	0.0	0	7	0.0	0					3	0	0	23	0	0	16	0	0	3	0	0
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	359	0.6	2	21	0.0	0	18	0.0	0	15	0.0	0	7	0.0	0					3	0	0	23	0	0	16	0	0	3	0	0
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	359	0.6	2	21	0.0	0	18	0.0	0	15	0.0	0	7	0.0	0					3	0	0	23	0	0	16	0	0	3	0	0
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	359	17.8	64	21	19.0	4	18	88.9	16	15	80.0	12	7	42.9	3					3	0	0	23	0	0	16	0	0	3	66.7	2
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	359	0.0	0	21	0.0	0	18	0.0	0	15	0.0	0	7	0.0	0					3	0	0	23	0	0	16	0	0	3	0	0
macrolides - azithromycin																				3	0	0	23	0	0	16	0	0	3	0	0
penicillins - ampicillin	359	15.3	55	21	19.0	4	18	72.2	13	15	40.0	6	7	57.1	4					3	0	0	23	0	0	16	6.3	1	3	0	0
polymyxins - colistin																				3	0	0	23	0	0	16	0	0	3	0	0
quinolones - nalidixic acid	359	14.5	52	21	14.3	3	18	83.3	15	15	73.3	11	7	42.9	3					3	0	0	23	0	0	16	0	0	3	66.7	2
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	359	13.6	49	21	0.0	0	18	0.0	0	15	13.3	2	7	28.6	2					3	0	0	23	0	0	16	6.3	1	3	0	0
tetracyclines - tetracycline	359	14.2	51	21	9.5	2	18	66.7	12	15	26.7	4	7	0.0	0					3	0	0	23	17.4	4	16	0	0	3	0	0
trimethoprim	359	6.4	23	21	0.0	0	18	0.0	0	15	13.3	2	7	28.6	2					3	0	0	23	0	0	16	6.3	1	3	0	0
multiresistant isolates	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	
fully sensitive	359	72.7	261	21	81.0	17	18	11.1	2	15	13.3	2	7	28.6	2					3	100	3	23	83	19	16	94	15	3	33	1
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	359	10.3	37	21	0.0	0	18	16.7	3	15	46.7	7	7	0.0	0					3	0	0	23	17.4	4	16	0	0	3	66.7	2
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	359	3.3	12	21	9.5	2	18	5.6	1	15	6.7	1	7	57.1	4					3	0	0	23	0.0	0	16	0	0	3	0	0
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	359	5.0	18	21	9.5	2	18	66.7	12	15	26.7	4	7	0.0	0					3	0	0	23	0	0	16	6	1	3	0	0
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	359	2.8	10	21	0.0	0	18	0.0	0	15	0.0	0	7	14.3	1					3	0	0	23	0	0	16	0	0	3	0	0
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	359	5.8	21	21	0.0	0	18	0.0	0	15	6.7	1	7	0.0	0					3	0	0	23	0	0	16	0	0	3	0	0

CAVE: Isolates from humans, broiler meat, turkey meat, poultry meat (unspec.), pork and beef were AST using the disk diffusion test applying EUCAST clinical breakpoints, whereas for isolates from broiler carcasses, layer flocks, broiler flocks and turkey flocks the microbilution method applying ECOFFs was used.

Table 63 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Infantis* in broiler carcasses - quantitative data, 2016

zoonotic agent	<i>S. Infantis</i>		
matrix	broiler carcasses		
sampling context	AMR monitoring		
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	17	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:	

antimicrobial	total units tested		micro-biological resistant	n	=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
	N	%R																							
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	17	0.0	0	0							17	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	17	0.0	0	0											15	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
carbapenems - meropenem	17	0.0	0	0			17	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	17	0.0	0	0						16	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	17	0.0	0	0						16	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	17	100.0	17	17		-	-	-	-	2	14	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	17	-	-	-						2	9	6	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
macrolides - azithromycin	17	0.0	0	0									-	4	10	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
penicillins - ampicillin	17	0.0	0	0							2	13	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
polymyxins - colistin	17	0.0	0	0							17	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
quinolones - nalidixic acid	17	100.0	17	17										-	-	-	-	-	1	16	-	-	-	-	-
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	17	88.2	15	15												-	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	14
tetracyclines - tetracycline	17	88.2	15	15									2	-	-	-	2	9	4	-	-	-	-	-	-
trimethoprim	17	0.0	0	0						12	1	3	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Table 64 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Coeln* in broiler carcasses - quantitative data, 2016

zoonotic agent	<i>S. Coeln</i>	
matrix	broiler carcasses	
sampling context	AMR monitoring	
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	7	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:

antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant		=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
		N	%R																				
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	7	0.0	0							7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	7	0.0	0											7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
carbapenems - meropenem	7	0.0	0			7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	7	0.0	0						7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	7	0.0	0						7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	7	0.0	0	3	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
glycyclines - tigecycline	7	-	-						7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
macrolides - azithromycin	7	0.0	0									1	5	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
penicillins - ampicillin	7	0.0	0								5	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
polymyxins - colistin	7	0.0	0								6	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
quinolones - nalidixic acid	7	0.0	0										7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	7	0.0	0												-	7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
tetracyclines - tetracycline	7	0.0	0									7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
trimethoprim	7	0.0	0						7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Table 65 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Montevideo* in broiler carcasses - quantitative data, 2016

zoonotic agent	<i>S. Montevideo</i>	
matrix	broiler carcasses	
sampling context	AMR monitoring	
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	7	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:

antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	N	%R	n	= < 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
						n																				
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	7	0.0	0									6	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	7	0.0	0													7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
carbapenems - meropenem	7	0.0	0				7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	7	0.0	0							7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	7	0.0	0							7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	7	0.0	0			7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
glycylycylines - tigecycline	7	-	-							7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
macrolides - azithromycin	7	0.0	0											-	2	5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
penicillins - ampicillin	7	0.0	0										7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
polymyxins - colistin	7	0.0	0										7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
quinolones - nalidixic acid	7	0.0	0												7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	7	0.0	0													-	2	5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
tetracyclines - tetracycline	7	0.0	0											7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
trimethoprim	7	0.0	0							7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Table 66 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Salmonella* other serotypes (than mentioned before) in broiler carcasses - quantitative data, 2016

zoonotic agent	<i>Salmonella</i> other serotypes (than mentioned before)	
matrix	broiler carcasses	
sampling context	AMR monitoring	
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	5	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:

antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	N	%R	n	= < 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
						n																				
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	5	0.0	0									5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	5	0.0	0													5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
carbapenems - meropenem	5	0.0	0				5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	5	0.0	0							5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	5	0.0	0								5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	5	0.0	0			3	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
glycylyclines - tigecycline	5	-	-							5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
macrolides - azithromycin	5	0.0	0											-	3	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
penicillins - ampicillin	5	0.0	0									4	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
polymyxins - colistin	5	0.0	0									4	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
quinolones - nalidixic acid	5	0.0	0												5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	5	0.0	0													-	2	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
tetracyclines - tetracycline	5	0.0	0											5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
trimethoprim	5	0.0	0							5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Table 67 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Salmonella* sp. in layer flocks - quantitative data, 2016

zoonotic agent	<i>Salmonella</i> spp.		
matrix	layer flocks		
sampling context	AMR monitoring		
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	46	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:	

antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant		= < 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
		%R	n																				
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	46	0.0	0							46	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	46	0.0	0											45	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
carbapenems - meropenem	46	0.0	0			45	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	46	0.0	0						45	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	46	0.0	0						45	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	46	6.5	3	33	10	-	-	1	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	46	-	-						38	6	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
macrolides - azithromycin	46	0.0	0									-	17	27	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
penicillins - ampicillin	46	0.0	0							27	17	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
polymyxins - colistin	46	0.0	0							38	8	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
quinolones - nalidixic acid	46	6.5	3										43	-	-	-	-	-	3	-	-	-	
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	46	4.3	2											2	6	29	7	-	-	-	-	2	
tetracyclines - tetracycline	46	13.0	6									40	-	-	-	-	2	4	-	-	-	-	
trimethoprim	46	0.0	0						39	7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	

Table 68 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Enteritidis* in layer flocks - quantitative data, 2016

zoonotic agent	<i>S. Enteritidis</i>		
matrix	layer flocks		
sampling context	AMR monitoring		
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	10	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:	

antimicrobial	total units tested		micro-biological resistant	n	= < 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
	N	%R																						
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	10	0.0	0	0							10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	10	0.0	0	0											10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
carbapenems - meropenem	10	0.0	0	0			9	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	10	0.0	0	0						10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	10	0.0	0	0						10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	10	10.0	1	1	5	4	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	10	0.0	0	0						8	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
macrolides - azithromycin	10	0.0	0	0									-	7	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
penicillins - ampicillin	10	0.0	0	0								2	7	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
polymyxins - colistin	10	0.0	0	0								2	8	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
quinolones - nalidixic acid	10	10.0	1	1										9	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	10	0.0	0	0												2	7	1	-	-	-	-	-	-
tetracyclines - tetracycline	10	0.0	0	0									10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
trimethoprim	10	0.0	0	0						8	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Table 69 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Typhimurium* in layer flocks - quantitative data, 2016

zoonotic agent	<i>S. Typhimurium</i>		
matrix	layer flocks		
sampling context	AMR monitoring		
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	4	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:	

antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
			= < 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
	N	%R	n																			
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	4	0.0	0						4	-	-	-	-	-	-							
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	4	0.0	0											4	-	-	-					
carbapenems - meropenem	4	0.0	0		4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-								
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	4	0.0	0					4	-	-	-	-	-									
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	4	0.0	0					4	-	-	-	-	-									
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	4	0.0	0	1	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-									
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	4	0.0	0					4	-	-	-	-	-									
macrolides - azithromycin	4	0.0	0									4	-	-	-							
penicillins - ampicillin	4	0.0	0						2	2	-	-	-	-	-							
polymyxins - colistin	4	0.0	0					4	-	-	-	-	-									
quinolones - nalidixic acid	4	0.0	0								4	-	-	-	-							
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	4	0.0	0										1	3	-	-	-	-	-			
tetracyclines - tetracycline	4	0.0	0							4	-	-	-	-	-							
trimethoprim	4	0.0	0					1	3	-	-	-	-	-								

Table 70 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Infantis* in layer flocks - quantitative data, 2016

zoonotic agent	<i>S. Infantis</i>	
matrix	layer flocks	
sampling context	AMR monitoring	
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	3	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:

antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant		=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
		%R	n																				
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	3	0.0	0						3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	3	0.0	0											2	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
carbapenems - meropenem	3	0.0	0			3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	3	0.0	0						2	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	3	0.0	0						3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	3	66.7	2	1	-	-	-	1	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	3	-	-						1	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
macrolides - azithromycin	3	0.0	0											2	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
penicillins - ampicillin	3	0.0	0							1	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
polymyxins - colistin	3	0.0	0							3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
quinolones - nalidixic acid	3	66.7	2										1	-	-	-	-	-	2	-	-	-	-
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	3	66.7	2													1	-	-	-	-	-	2	-
tetracyclines - tetracycline	3	66.7	2									1	-	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	-	-
trimethoprim	3	0.0	0						3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Table 71 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Salmonella* other serotypes (than mentioned before) in layer flocks - quantitative data, 2016

zoonotic agent	<i>Salmonella</i> other serotypes (than mentioned before)		
matrix	layer flocks		
sampling context	AMR monitoring		
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	29	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:	

antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant		= < 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
		%R	n																				
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	29	0.0	0						29	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	29	0.0	0											29	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
carbapenems - meropenem	29	0.0	0			29	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	29	0.0	0						29	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	29	0.0	0						28	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	29	0.0	0	26	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	29	-	-						25	3	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
macrolides - azithromycin	29	0.0	0									-	10	18	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
penicillins - ampicillin	29	0.0	0							22	6	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
polymyxins - colistin	29	0.0	0							29	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
quinolones - nalidixic acid	29	0.0	0										29	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	29	0.0	0											2	3	18	6	-	-	-	-	-	-
tetracyclines - tetracycline	29	13.8	4									25	-	-	-	-	1	3	-	-	-	-	-
trimethoprim	29	0.0	0						27	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Table 72 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Salmonella* sp. in broiler flocks - quantitative data, 2016

zoonotic agent	<i>Salmonella</i> spp.		
matrix	broiler flocks		
sampling context	AMR monitoring		
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	179	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:	

antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant		= < 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
		%R	n																				
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	179	0.0	0						174	5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	179	0.0	0											159	20	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
carbapenems - meropenem	179	0.0	0		179	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	179	0.0	0						167	12	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	179	0.0	0						157	22	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	179	53.6	96	64	19	-	-	-	19	61	16	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	179	-	-						92	56	31	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
macrolides - azithromycin	179	0.0	0									-	43	113	23	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
penicillins - ampicillin	179	1.7	3							70	85	21	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	
polymyxins - colistin	179	0.0	0							174	5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
quinolones - nalidixic acid	179	53.6	96										82	1	-	-	1	1	94	-	-	-	-
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	179	53.6	96							1				1	41	39	1	-	-	2	2	92	
tetracyclines - tetracycline	179	53.6	96									82	1	-	-	4	45	47	-	-	-	-	
trimethoprim	179	0.6	1						137	38	1	2	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	

Table 73 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Enteritidis* in broiler flocks - quantitative data, 2016

zoonotic agent	<i>S. Enteritidis</i>	
matrix	broiler flocks	
sampling context	AMR monitoring	
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	2	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:

antimicrobial	total units tested		micro-biological resistant																					
	N	%R	n	= < 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	2	0.0	0						2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	2	0.0	0											2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
carbapenems - meropenem	2	0.0	0			2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	2	0.0	0						2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	2	0.0	0						2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	2	0.0	0	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
glycylyclines - tigecycline	2	0.0	0						2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
macrolides - azithromycin	2	0.0	0									-	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
penicillins - ampicillin	2	0.0	0								1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
polymyxins - colistin	2	0.0	0								1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
quinolones - nalidixic acid	2	0.0	0										2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	2	0.0	0												1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
tetracyclines - tetracycline	2	0.0	0									2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
trimethoprim	2	0.0	0						1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Table 74 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Typhimurium* in broiler flocks - quantitative data, 2016

zoonotic agent	<i>S. Typhimurium</i>	
matrix	broiler flocks	
sampling context	AMR monitoring	
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	5	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:

antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	= < 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
				n																			
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	5	0.0	0						5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-							
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	5	0.0	0											5	-	-	-						
carbapenems - meropenem	5	0.0	0		5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-							
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	5	0.0	0					5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-							
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	5	0.0	0						5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-							
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	5	0.0	0	5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-							
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	5	0.0	0					5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-							
macrolides - azithromycin	5	0.0	0									-	2	3	-	-	-						
penicillins - ampicillin	5	0.0	0							3	2	-	-	-	-	-	-						
polymyxins - colistin	5	0.0	0							4	1	-	-	-	-	-							
quinolones - nalidixic acid	5	0.0	0										5	-	-	-	-	-					
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	5	0.0	0												3	2	-	-	-	-	-		
tetracyclines - tetracycline	5	0.0	0									5	-	-	-	-	-						
trimethoprim	5	0.0	0					4	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-							

Table 75 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Infantis* in broiler flocks - quantitative data, 2016

zoonotic agent	<i>S. Infantis</i>		
matrix	broiler flocks		
sampling context	AMR monitoring		
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	104	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:	

antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant		= < 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
		%R	n																				
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	104	0.0	0							103	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	104	0.0	0											84	20	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
carbapenems - meropenem	104	0.0	0			104	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	104	0.0	0						92	12	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	104	0.0	0						82	22	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	104	92.3	96	3	5	-	-	19	61	16	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	104	-	-						21	52	31	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
macrolides - azithromycin	104	0.0	0									-	17	64	23	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
penicillins - ampicillin	104	1.0	1								17	65	21	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	
polymyxins - colistin	104	0.0	0								104	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
quinolones - nalidixic acid	104	92.3	96										8	-	-	-	1	1	94	-	-	-	
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	104	91.3	95												3	6	-	-	-	2	2	91	
tetracyclines - tetracycline	104	92.3	96									8	-	-	-	4	45	47	-	-	-	-	
trimethoprim	104	0.0	0						70	31	1	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	

Table 76 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Thompson* in broiler flocks - quantitative data, 2016

zoonotic agent	<i>S. Thompson</i>	
matrix	broiler flocks	
sampling context	AMR monitoring	
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	31	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:

antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant		= < 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
		%R	n																				
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	31	0.0	0						29	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	31	0.0	0											31	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
carbapenems - meropenem	31	0.0	0		31	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	31	0.0	0						31	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	31	0.0	0						31	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	31	0.0	0	29	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	31	-	-						31	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
macrolides - azithromycin	31	0.0	0									-	4	27	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
penicillins - ampicillin	31	3.2	1								21	9	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-
polymyxins - colistin	31	0.0	0								29	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
quinolones - nalidixic acid	31	0.0	0										31	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	31	0.0	0							1				1	21	8	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
tetracyclines - tetracycline	31	0.0	0									30	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
trimethoprim	31	0.0	0						28	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Table 77 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Montevideo* in broiler flocks - quantitative data, 2016

zoonotic agent	<i>S. Montevideo</i>		
matrix	broiler flocks		
sampling context	AMR monitoring		
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	10	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:	

antimicrobial	total units tested		micro-biological resistant																					
	N	%R	n	= < 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	10	0.0	0							9	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	10	0.0	0											10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
carbapenems - meropenem	10	0.0	0			10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	10	0.0	0						10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	10	0.0	0							10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	10	0.0	0		8	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	10	-	-						8	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
macrolides - azithromycin	10	0.0	0									-	1	9	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
penicillins - ampicillin	10	0.0	0							6	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
polymyxins - colistin	10	0.0	0							9	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
quinolones - nalidixic acid	10	0.0	0										10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	10	0.0	0												2	8	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
tetracyclines - tetracycline	10	0.0	0								10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
trimethoprim	10	0.0	0						10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	

Table 78 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Salmonella* other serotypes (than mentioned before) in broiler flocks - quantitative data, 2016

zoonotic agent	<i>Salmonella</i> other serotypes (than mentioned before)	
matrix	broiler flocks	
sampling context	AMR monitoring	
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	27	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:

antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant		= < 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
		%R	n																				
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	27	0.0	0							26	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	27	0.0	0																				
carbapenems - meropenem	27	0.0	0			27	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	27	0.0	0						27	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	27	0.0	0							27	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	27	0.0	0	17	10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	27	-	-						25	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
macrolides - azithromycin	27	0.0	0											18	9	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
penicillins - ampicillin	27	3.7	1								22	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-
polymyxins - colistin	27	0.0	0								27	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
quinolones - nalidixic acid	27	0.0	0											26	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	27	3.7	1												11	14	1	-	-	-	-	1	-
tetracyclines - tetracycline	27	0.0	0									27	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
trimethoprim	27	3.7	1						24	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-

Table 79 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Salmonella* sp. in turkey flocks - quantitative data, 2016

zoonotic agent	<i>Salmonella</i> spp.		
matrix	turkey flocks		
sampling context	AMR monitoring		
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	11	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:	

antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant		= < 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
		%R	n																				
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	11	0.0	0						11	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	11	0.0	0											11	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
carbapenems - meropenem	11	0.0	0			11	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	11	0.0	0						11	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	11	0.0	0						11	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	11	36.4	4		2	5	-	-	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
glycylycylines - tigecycline	11	-	-						8	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
macrolides - azithromycin	11	0.0	0										-	5	6	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
penicillins - ampicillin	11	9.1	1								7	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-
polymyxins - colistin	11	0.0	0							11	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
quinolones - nalidixic acid	11	36.4	4										7	-	-	-	-	-	1	3	-	-	-
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	11	27.3	3												-	2	4	2	-	-	-	-	3
tetracyclines - tetracycline	11	27.3	3									8	-	-	-	-	2	1	-	-	-	-	-
trimethoprim	11	0.0	0						9	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Table 81 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Infantis* in turkey flocks - quantitative data, 2016

zoonotic agent	<i>S. Infantis</i>		
matrix	turkey flocks		
sampling context	AMR monitoring		
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	3	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:	

antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant		= < 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
		%R	n																				
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	3	0.0	0						3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	3	0.0	0											3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
carbapenems - meropenem	3	0.0	0			3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	3	0.0	0						3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	3	0.0	0						3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	3	66.7	2		-	1	-	-	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	3	-	-						1	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
macrolides - azithromycin	3	0.0	0											3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
penicillins - ampicillin	3	0.0	0							2	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
polymyxins - colistin	3	0.0	0							3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
quinolones - nalidixic acid	3	66.7	2										1	-	-	-	-	-	2	-	-	-	-
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	3	66.7	2													1	-	-	-	-	-	-	2
tetracyclines - tetracycline	3	66.7	2									1	-	-	-	-	2	-	-	-	-	-	-
trimethoprim	3	0.0	0						3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Table 82 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Salmonella* other serotypes (than mentioned before) in turkey flocks - quantitative data, 2016

zoonotic agent	<i>Salmonella</i> other serotypes (than mentioned before)		
matrix	turkey flocks		
sampling context	AMR monitoring		
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	5	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:	

antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant		=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
		%R	n																					
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	5	0.0	0						5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	5	0.0	0											5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
carbapenems - meropenem	5	0.0	0			5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	5	0.0	0						5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	5	0.0	0						5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	5	40.0	2		-	3	-	-	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	5	-	-						4	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
macrolides - azithromycin	5	0.0	0										-	3	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
penicillins - ampicillin	5	20.0	1							3	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	
polymyxins - colistin	5	0.0	0							5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
quinolones - nalidixic acid	5	40.0	2										3	-	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	-	
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	5	20.0	1													2	2	-	-	-	-	1	-	
tetracyclines - tetracycline	5	20.0	1									4	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	
trimethoprim	5	0.0	0						4	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	

5.2. *Campylobacter*

5.2.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Resistance monitoring of thermotolerant *Campylobacter*- isolates from broiler flocks has been started in Austria in 2004, although using different antimicrobial, different measure ranges and breakpoints. The microdilution method has stayed the same therefore it is possible to analyse the former data using the actual ECOFFs applied to the 5 antimicrobial classes (fluoro(chinolones), macrolides, gentamicin, streptomycin and tetracyclines) that have to be reported according to CID 2013/652/EU. In 2004, 50% of *C. jejuni* tested were susceptible to the five antimicrobial classes. The percentage of fully susceptible isolates decreased until 2012 to 18%. Since then we can see a slight recovery of susceptible isolates, increasing to 26% in 2013, 20% in 2014 and 20% in 2016.

Isolates from turkeys have been analysed for the first time in 2014, showing 34% fully susceptible *C. jejuni*-isolates, but only 11% in 2016.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Humans: 411 isolates have been tested in course of the national sentinel program. Extremely high resistance rates were found to ciprofloxacin (72.5%), high rates to tetracycline (42.1%), and low rates to streptomycin (3.6%). Very low resistance was detected to erythromycin (0.2%) and gentamicin (0.2%).

Broiler flocks: 174 isolates have been tested, 35 isolates (20.1%) were fully susceptible. Extremely high resistance rates were found to ciprofloxacin (77.6%), high rates to tetracycline (50.0%), and low rates to streptomycin (6.3%). No resistance was detected to macrolides and gentamicin. Eight isolates (4.6%) showed multiple resistances.

Turkeys: 55 isolates could be obtained from turkey flocks, of which 6 isolates (10.9%) were fully susceptible. Extremely high resistance rates were found to ciprofloxacin (74.5%), very high rates to tetracycline (54.5%), and low rates to streptomycin (7.3%). No resistance was detected to macrolides and gentamicin. Three isolates (5.5%) showed multiple resistances.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Due to the fact that human isolates show similar percentages of resistance rates to ciprofloxacin as the poultry isolates poultry meat seems to be the most important vehicle for human infections.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

The National Action Plan to control antimicrobial resistance, published on the homepage of the Federal Ministry of Health and Women Affairs

(http://www.bmgfj.gv.at/cms/home/attachments/9/2/1/CH1318/CMS1416214760260/nap_amr.pdf).

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil.

Additional information

Publication of the results in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria, 2016 (AURES 2016).

5.2.2. Antimicrobial resistance in *Campylobacter jejuni* and *C. coli* isolates in humans

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

A sentinel surveillance program for *Campylobacter* isolates from human infections was installed in October 2006. On a monthly basis, the first 10 isolates collected at each of four designated diagnostic laboratories serving different provinces in Austria are sent to the National Reference Centre for

Campylobacter for speciation analysis and antimicrobial susceptibility testing by broth microdilution method.

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

Stool specimens were plated on *Campylobacter* blood-free selective agar at 37°C or 42°C for 48 hours under microaerobic conditions, and organisms were identified as *Campylobacter* spp. by oxidase testing and cell morphology. Isolates were speciated by biochemical methods and/or molecular methods as well as matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization time-of-flight mass spectrometry (MALDI-TOF). Broth microdilution susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter* spp. isolates was done using customised Sensititre® susceptibility microtitre plates (TREK Diagnostic Systems Ltd., East Grinstead, West Sussex, UK).

Briefly, *Campylobacter* spp. strains were subcultivated on Columbia blood agar and incubated for 48 hours at 37 °C in a microaerobic atmosphere. Inocula from fresh cultures were prepared by suspension in physiological saline to obtain a turbidity equivalent to that of a McFarland standard 0.5. The suspension was added to Mueller Hinton bouillon for a final concentration of approximately 500,000 cfu/ml and incubated for 48 hours at 37 °C in a microaerobic atmosphere. *Campylobacter jejuni* ATCC 33560 was used as control.

The number of isolates that are fully sensitive and the number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 and > 4 antimicrobials for *Campylobacter* includes only resistance to tetracycline, erythromycin, ciprofloxacin/nalidixic acid, gentamicin, and streptomycin!

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2016, out of the sentinel program, 454 isolates of *Campylobacter* (411 *C. jejuni*, 43 *C. coli*) were tested for their antimicrobial susceptibility using broth microdilution method. Compared to 2015, in *C. jejuni* resistance rates to chinolones equaled to rates in 2016 (73% to 74%), although to ampicillin resistance rates dropped from 40% to 33% but to tetracycline rose from 40% to 42%; resistance to erythromycin was very low (0.2% in *C. jejuni*, 2,3% in *C. coli*). In *C. coli*, resistance rates were generally higher than in *C. jejuni*.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

The quinolone and tetracycline resistance rates of *C. jejuni* isolates from humans correspond with the resistance rates found in isolates from broiler meat.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Additional information

The sentinel surveillance system will be continued. Results are published annually in the Report of the National Reference Centre for *Campylobacter* and in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria (AURES).

5.2.3. Antimicrobial resistance in *Campylobacter jejuni* isolates from animals and food

A. Antimicrobial resistance in *Campylobacter jejuni* and *coli* in poultry meat

No isolates from food tested in 2016.

B. Antimicrobial resistance in *Campylobacter jejuni* in broiler flocks

Description of sampling designs

See chapter: *C. jejuni* isolates from caecal samples gathered at slaughter from broilers

Stratification procedures per animal populations and food categories

See chapter: *C. jejuni* isolates from caecal samples gathered at slaughter from broilers

Randomisation procedures per animal populations and food categories

See chapter: *C. jejuni* isolates from caecal samples gathered at slaughter from broilers

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Frequency of the sampling

See chapter: *C. jejuni* isolates from caecal samples gathered at slaughter from broilers

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Type of specimen taken

See chapter: *C. jejuni* isolates from caecal samples gathered at slaughter from broilers

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

See chapter: *C. jejuni* isolates from caecal samples gathered at slaughter from broilers

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

In 2016, 175 *C. jejuni*-isolates were obtained from broilers. At NRL-AR 174 isolates were susceptibility tested, one isolate could not be reisolated.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Methods used for collecting data

Each sample taken was accompanied by an electronical order form from the Poultry Heath Data (PHD).

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

C. jejuni isolates from caecal samples gathered at slaughter from broilers.

Laboratory used for detection for resistance - Antimicrobials included in monitoring

NRL-AR: All isolates were subjected to susceptibility testing as described by the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI), which is accepted as an international reference method (ISO standard 20776-1:2006 (ISO, 2006)), as stated in Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU (Annex, Part A, Table 1). Following antimicrobial substances tested: Chinolones (ciprofloxacin and nalidixic acid), aminoglycosides (gentamicin und streptomycin), tetracycline, and macrolides (erythromycin).

Laboratory used for detection for resistance - Cut-off values used in testing

Application of European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (EUCAST) epidemiological cut-off values (ECOFFs) for the interpretation of microbiological resistance (as stated in CID 2013/652/EU).

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place

The control program is in line with the EU Commission and described in the National Action Plan (NAP) published on the homepage of the Federal Ministry of Health

(http://www.bmgfj.gv.at/cms/home/attachments/9/2/1/CH1318/CMS1416214760260/nap_amr.pdf).

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

No measures foreseen in case of resistant isolates.

Notification system in place

No notification foreseen in case of resistant isolates.

Results of the investigation

Out of 174 isolates tested, 20.1% were susceptible to all tested antimicrobial substances. Resistance rates were extremely high towards ciprofloxacin (77.6%), and high towards tetracycline (50.0%). Low

resistance rates were detected towards streptomycin. Towards gentamicin and erythromycin no resistance was found. Eight isolates (4.6%) showed multiple resistances.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The proportion of isolates sensitive to the six antimicrobials (ciprofloxacin, nalidixic acid, gentamicin, streptomycin, tetracycline, and erythromycin) shows a decreasing tendency since 2004 (50.1% to 23.6%); although since 2012 the proportion of fully sensitive isolates increased from 17.6% to 23.6%.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Isolates from humans show similar rates of resistance towards ciprofloxacin (2014: 71.0%) as isolates from broilers. The actual source of infection in human cases is unknown, chicken meat may account for approx. 40% or even more of human infections.

Additional information

Publication of the results in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria 2016 (AURES 2016).

C. Antimicrobial resistance in *Campylobacter jejuni* in turkey flocks

Description of sampling designs

See chapter: *C. jejuni* isolates from caecal samples gathered at slaughter from fattening turkeys.

Stratification procedures per animal populations and food categories

See chapter: *C. jejuni* isolates from caecal samples gathered at slaughter from fattening turkeys.

Randomisation procedures per animal populations and food categories

See chapter: *C. jejuni* isolates from caecal samples gathered at slaughter from fattening turkeys.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Frequency of the sampling

See chapter: *C. jejuni* isolates from caecal samples gathered at slaughter from fattening turkeys.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Type of specimen taken

See chapter: *C. jejuni* isolates from caecal samples gathered at slaughter from fattening turkeys.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

See chapter: *C. jejuni* isolates from caecal samples gathered at slaughter from fattening turkeys.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

In 2016, 55 *C. jejuni*-isolates were obtained from fattening turkeys. All isolates were susceptibility tested in the NRL-AR.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Methods used for collecting data

Each sample taken was accompanied by an electronical order form from the Poultry Health Data (PHD).

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

C. jejuni isolates from caecal samples gathered at slaughter from fattening turkeys.

Laboratory used for detection for resistance - Antimicrobials included in monitoring

NRL-AR: All isolates were subjected to susceptibility testing as described by the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI), which is accepted as an international reference method (ISO standard 20776-1:2006 (ISO, 2006)), as stated in Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU (Annex, Part A, Table 1). Following antimicrobial substances tested: Chinolones (ciprofloxacin and nalidixic acid), aminoglycosides (gentamicin und streptomycin), tetracycline, and macrolides (erythromycin).

Laboratory used for detection for resistance - Cut-off values used in testing

Application of European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (EUCAST) epidemiological cut-off values (ECOFFs) for the interpretation of microbiological resistance (as stated in CID 2013/652/EU).

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place

The control program is in line with the EU Commission and described in the National Action Plan (NAP) published on the homepage of the Federal Ministry of Health (http://www.bmgfj.gv.at/cms/home/attachments/9/2/1/CH1318/CMS1416214760260/nap_amr.pdf).

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

No measures foreseen in case of resistant isolates.

Notification system in place

No notification foreseen in case of resistant isolates.

Results of the investigation

Out of 55 isolates tested, 10.9% were susceptible to all tested antimicrobial substances. Resistance rates were extremely high towards ciprofloxacin (74.5%), and very high towards tetracycline (54.5%). Low resistance rates were detected towards streptomycin. Towards gentamicin and erythromycin no resistance was found. Three isolates (5.5%) showed multiple resistances.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The proportion of isolates sensitive to the six antimicrobials (ciprofloxacin, nalidixic acid, gentamicin, streptomycin, tetracycline, and erythromycin) strongly decreased compared to 2014, from 34.4% to 10.9%.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Isolates from humans show similar rates of resistance towards ciprofloxacin (2014: 71.0%) as isolates from turkeys. The actual source of infection in human cases is unknown, chicken meat may account for approx. 40% or even more of human infections, turkey meat could also play an important role.

Additional information

Publication of the results in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria 2016 (AURES 2016).

Table 83 Breakpoints used for antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter jejuni* and *C. coli*, 2016

Antimicrobial	<i>C. jejuni</i>			<i>C. coli</i>		
	ECOFF	Range tested concentration (µg/ml)		ECOFF	Range tested concentration (µg/ml)	
	wild type <=	lowest	highest	wild type <=	lowest	highest
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	2	0.12	16	2	0.12	16
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	4	0.5	32	4	0.5	32
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	16	2	64	16	2	64
Carbapenems - Imipenem	8	0.06	16	8	0.06	16
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	0.5	0.06	32	0.5	0.06	32
Macrolides - Erythromycin	4	0.25	128	8	0.25	128
Penicillins – Ampicillin	8	1	64	8	1	64
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	16	2	256	16	2	256
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	1	0.12	64	2	0.12	64

Number of fully-susceptible and number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 or >4 antimicrobials of different classes, excluding cross-resistance. For *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* this includes resistance to ciprofloxacin/nalidixic acid, tetracycline, gentamicin, streptomycin, erythromycin.

Table 84 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter jejuni*, qualitative data, 2016

antimicrobial	humans			broiler flocks			turkey flocks		
	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n
	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	411	0.2	1	174	0.0	0	55	0.0	0
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	411	3.6	15	174	6.3	11	55	7.3	4
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	411	0.2	1	-	-	-	-	-	-
Carbapenems - Imipenem	411	0.5	2	-	-	-	-	-	-
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	411	72.5	298	174	77.6	135	55	74.5	41
Macrolides - Erythromycin	411	0.2	1	174	0.0	0	55	0.0	0
Penicillins - Ampicillin	411	32.8	135	-	-	-	-	-	-
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	411	71.8	295	174	73.0	127	55	63.6	35
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	411	42.1	173	174	50.0	87	55	54.5	30
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n
fully sensitive	411	23.8	98	174	20.1	35	55	10.9	6
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	411	37.2	153	174	30.5	53	55	47.3	26
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	411	35.5	146	174	44.8	78	55	36.4	20
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	411	3.2	13	174	4.6	8	55	5.5	3
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	411	0.2	1	174	0.0	0	55	0.0	0
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	411	0.0	0	174	0.0	0	55	0.0	0

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 85 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter jejuni* in humans, quantitative data, 2016

		zoonotic agent	<i>C. jejuni</i>																					
		matrix	humans																					
		sampling context	cases																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		411	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																					
antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant																						
	N	%R	n	= < 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	411	0.2	1	n																				
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	411	3.6	15				294	112	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	1								
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	411	0.2	1									270	89	50	1	1	-							
Carbapenems - Imipenem	411	0.5	2			383	25	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	2									
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	411	72.5	298		53	51	6	3	-	1	18	210	32	33	4									
Macrolides - Erythromycin	411	0.2	1				26	188	165	28	3	-	-	-	-	-	1							
Penicillins - Ampicillin	411	32.8	135						5	62	135	74	9	20	54	52								
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	411	71.8	295								52	50	9	5	-	2	59	222	12					
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	411	42.1	173			89	93	34	22	3	3	1	3	9	22	132								

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 86 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter jejuni* in broiler flocks, quantitative data, 2016

zoonotic agent	<i>C. jejuni</i>
matrix	broiler flocks
sampling context	cases

Number of isolates available in the laboratory 174 Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:

antimicrobial	total units tested		micro-biological resistant																					
	N	%R	n	= < 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	174	0.0	0					101	66	7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	174	6.3	11						29	52	72	9	1	3	6	2								
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	174	77.6	135			2	32	5	-	-	-	2	103	17	13									
Macrolides - Erythromycin	174	0.0	0						-	4	158	12	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	174	73.0	127									20	21	6	-	-	5	111	10	1				
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	174	50.0	87				1	2	77	7	1	4	-	-	7	11	64							

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 87 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter jejuni* in turkey flocks, quantitative data, 2016

zoonotic agent	<i>C. jejuni</i>
matrix	turkey flocks
sampling context	cases

Number of isolates available in the laboratory 55 Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:

antimicrobial	total units tested		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																					
	N	%R	n	= < 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	55	0.0	0					34	19	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	55	7.3	4						10	16	20	4	1	-	2	2								
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	55	74.5	41			-	10	4	-	-	-	-	1	27	8	5								
Macrolides - Erythromycin	55	0.0	0						2	1	43	8	1	-	-	-	-	-	-					
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	55	63.6	35								1	5	7	7	-	-	-	31	4					
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	55	54.5	30					2	-	22	1	4	3	-	2	3	1	17						

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 88 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter coli*, qualitative data, 2016

humans			
antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	
	N	%R	n
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	43	2.3	1
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	43	25.6	11
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	43	0.0	0
Carbapenems - Imipenem	43	0.0	0
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	43	81.4	35
Macrolides - Erythromycin	43	2.3	1
Penicillins - Ampicillin	43	51.2	22
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	43	81.4	35
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	43	65.1	28
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%R	n
fully sensitive	43	14.0	6
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	43	20.9	9
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	43	44.2	19
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	43	18.6	8
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	43	0.0	0
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	43	2.3	1

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 89 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter coli* in humans, quantitative data, 2016

zoonotic agent	<i>C. coli</i>
matrix	humans
sampling context	cases

Number of isolates available in the laboratory 43 Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:

antimicrobial	total units tested		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																					
	N	%R	n	= < 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	43	2.3	1					8	31	3	-	-	-	-	-	1								
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	43	25.6	11						3	27	2	-	-	-	6	4	1							
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	43	0.0	0								2	29	10	2	-	-								
Carbapenems - Imipenem	43	0.0	0					-	14	29	-	-	-	-	-									
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	43	81.4	35			3	4	1	-	-	-	8	15	8	2	2								
Macrolides - Erythromycin	43	2.3	1					2	14	9	14	2	1	-	-	-	-	1						
Penicillins - Ampicillin	43	51.2	22							-	-	7	14	10	2	-	10							
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	43	81.4	35								1	5	1	1	-	-	25	10						
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	43	65.1	28					-	8	5	2	-	-	-	-	-	2	26						

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

5.3. *E. coli* Indicators

5.3.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Resistance monitoring of faeces isolates from different slaughtered animals was started in Austria in 2004. The microdilution method applying ECOFFs was used for antimicrobial susceptibility testing (AST) of poultry-isolates. In 2014, the new legislation (CID 2013/652/EU) was implemented in Austria.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2004, the percentage of indicator *E. coli* susceptible to all antimicrobials tested was similar for isolates from broilers and fattening pigs (27% and 28%) but much higher for bovine isolates (91%). In the following years, the percentage of fully susceptible isolates from broilers varied, reaching the lowest rate in 2010 (10.5%); since then, the percentage of fully susceptible isolates has increased, reaching 21% in 2014 and 33.5% in 2016. Until 2013, the percentage of fully susceptible isolates from pigs more or less stayed the same, but in 2015 the highest rate was reached, with 48%. In isolates from bovines, no significant variations have been observed. Indicator *E. coli* from turkeys were examined for the first time in 2014. Compared to 2014, an increase of fully susceptible isolates could be observed from 33.6% to 42.2% in 2016.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Not available because indicator *E. coli* are not examined in humans.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

The National Action Plan to control antimicrobial resistance, published on the homepage of the Federal Ministry of Health and Women Affairs

(http://www.bmgfj.gv.at/cms/home/attachments/9/2/1/CH1318/CMS1416214760260/nap_amr.pdf).

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil.

Additional information

Publication of the results in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria, 2016 (AURES 2016).

5.3.2. Antimicrobial resistance of indicator *Escherichia coli* isolates from animals

A. Antimicrobial resistance of indicator *E. coli* from broiler flocks

Description of sampling designs

In 2016, the monitoring for indicator *E. coli* was performed according to CID 2013/652/EU. A sampling plan was calculated to obtain a representative sample of 170 *E. coli* isolates from broiler flocks all over Austria during the whole year. Out of 433 sampled broiler slaughter batches that were taken to isolate *C. jejuni*, 180 were randomly designated to *E. coli*-isolation.

Stratification procedures per animal populations and food categories

Sampling was performed in the 4 broiler abattoirs, where >80% of all Austrian broiler flocks are slaughtered. According to their throughput of slaughtered flocks, 76 (abattoir A), 52 (B), 5 (C), and 47 (D) samples had to be taken in the abattoirs. The sampling plan also determined the number of slaughter batches that had to be sampled every month.

Randomisation procedures per animal populations and food categories

The sampling was performed after evisceration by officially and designated veterinarians carrying out the post-mortem inspection.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Frequency of the sampling

See above at: Stratification procedures per animal populations and food categories

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Type of specimen taken

Intestines of 10 animals per slaughter batch.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

The sampling was performed by officially and designated veterinarians carrying out the post-mortem inspection. At time of evisceration the whole intestines of 10 animals per slaughter batch were taken, wrapped in a sterile plastic bag and cooled down to 4°C. Using a polystyrene box with freezer bags the samples were sent to the AGES Institute of Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, Department for Veterinary Microbiology (VEMI) in Graz. In the laboratory the temperature of the content was measured, caecums of each intestinal convolute were identified and some content of each caecum pooled and cultured by direct plating onto selective medium and incubated.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

Out of 182 samples 179 indicator *E. coli* were isolated and 170 randomly selected isolates susceptibility tested.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Methods used for collecting data

Each sample taken was accompanied by an electronic order form from the Poultry Health Data (PHD).

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

The intestinal contents are streaked onto MacConkey-agar plates (Merck Nr. 1.05465) and incubated for 24 hrs at 37±1 °C. Suspect *E. coli* colonies are streaked onto a blood-agar (Oxoid Nr. CM0055, 5% Sheep blood) and incubated for 24 hrs at 37±1 °C. The confirmation of the identification of *E. coli* is done with an oxidase- (Merck Nr. 1.13300.0001) and spot indol test (Remel, Nr. R8309002).

Laboratory used for detection for resistance - Antimicrobials included in monitoring

NRL-AR: All isolates were subjected to susceptibility testing as described by the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI), which is accepted as an international reference method (ISO standard 20776-1:2006 (ISO, 2006)), as stated in Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU (Annex, Part A, Table 1; panel 1).

Laboratory used for detection for resistance - Cut-off values used in testing

Application of European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (EUCAST) epidemiological cut-off values (ECOFFs) for the interpretation of microbiological resistance (as stated in CID 2013/652/EU).

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place

The control program is in line with the EU Commission and described in the National Action Plan (NAP) published on the homepage of the Federal Ministry of Health

(http://www.bmgfj.gv.at/cms/home/attachments/9/2/1/CH1318/CMS1416214760260/nap_amr.pdf).

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

No measures foreseen in case of resistant isolates.

Notification system in place

No notification foreseen in case of resistant isolates.

Results of the investigation

Out of 170 indicator *E. coli*, 33.5% were susceptible to all tested antimicrobials. High resistance rates were observed towards chinolones (47.6%), sulfonamides (37.1%) ampicillin (32.9%), trimethoprim (29.4%) and tetracycline (22.3%). Resistance to colistin was not detected. Fifty-six isolates (32.9%) showed multiple resistances.

One isolate was resistant to 3rd generation cephaosporines; this isolate was tested in panel 2 and was identified as AmpC-producing *E. coli* (synergy test with clavulanic acid negative, resistant towards cefoxitin).

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Compared to 2014, a strong increase of fully susceptible isolates could be observed from 21.0% to 33.5% in 2016. Since 2010 (10.5%) a significant increase in fully susceptible isolates can be found.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Not available because indicator *E. coli* are not examined in humans.

Additional information

Publication of the results in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria 2016 (AURES 2016).

B. Antimicrobial resistance of indicator *E. coli* from turkey flocks

Description of sampling designs

See also chapter: *C. jejuni* isolates from caecal samples gathered at slaughter from fattening turkeys. In 2016 the monitoring for indicator *E. coli* was performed according to CID 2013/652/EU. In two national slaughter houses > 80% of all Austrian turkey flocks are slaughtered. Based on the sampling plan for *C. jejuni*, it was exactly calculated which of these samples also should have been analysed for indicator *E. coli* to obtain 85 isolates (92 samples). During the DG (Sante)-audit 2016-8918 – MR in April 2016 the audit team did not approve Austria's decision of 85 isolates. Therefore the sampling plan was adjusted and all Austrian turkey flocks slaughtered in Austria should be sampled to obtain as many as possible indicator *E. coli*-isolates.

Stratification procedures per animal populations and food categories

See chapter: *C. jejuni* isolates from caecal samples gathered at slaughter from fattening turkeys.

Randomisation procedures per animal populations and food categories

See chapter: *C. jejuni* isolates from caecal samples gathered at slaughter from fattening turkeys.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Frequency of the sampling

See chapter: *C. jejuni* isolates from caecal samples gathered at slaughter from fattening turkeys.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Type of specimen taken

Intestines of 10 animals per slaughter batch.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

The sampling was performed by officially and designated veterinarians carrying out the post-mortem inspection. At time of evisceration caeca of 10 animals per slaughter batch were taken, wrapped in a sterile plastic bag and cooled down to 4°C. Using a polystyrene box with freezer bags the samples were sent to the AGES Institute of Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, Department for Veterinary Microbiology (VEMI) in Graz. In the laboratory the temperature of the content was measured, caeca were identified and some content of each caecum pooled and cultured by direct plating onto selective medium and incubated.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

One hundred and fifty-five samples were analyzed for *E. coli* and 154 indicator *E. coli* were identified. All these isolates were susceptibility tested.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Methods used for collecting data

Each sample taken was accompanied by an electronic order form from the Poultry Health Data (PHD).

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

The intestinal contents are streaked onto MacConkey-agar plates (Merck Nr. 1.05465) and incubated for 24 hrs at 37±1 °C. Suspect *E. coli* colonies are streaked onto a blood-agar (Oxoid Nr. CM0055, 5% Sheep blood) and incubated for 24 hrs at 37±1 °C. The confirmation of the identification of *E. coli* is done with an oxidase- (Merck Nr. 1.13300.0001) and spot indol test (Remel, Nr. R8309002).

Laboratory used for detection for resistance - Antimicrobials included in monitoring

NRL-AR: All isolates were subjected to susceptibility testing as described by the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI), which is accepted as an international reference method (ISO standard 20776-1:2006 (ISO, 2006)), as stated in Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU (Annex, Part A, Table 1; panel 1).

Laboratory used for detection for resistance - Cut-off values used in testing

Application of European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (EUCAST) epidemiological cut-off values (ECOFFs) for the interpretation of microbiological resistance (as stated in CID 2013/652/EU).

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place

The control program is in line with the EU Commission and described in the National Action Plan (NAP) published on the homepage of the Federal Ministry of Health

(http://www.bmgfj.gv.at/cms/home/attachments/9/2/1/CH1318/CMS1416214760260/nap_amr.pdf).

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

No measures foreseen in case of resistant isolates.

Notification system in place

No notification foreseen in case of resistant isolates.

Results of the investigation

Out of 154 indicator *E. coli*, 42.2% were susceptible to all tested antimicrobials. High resistance rates were observed towards tetracycline (40.9%), ampicillin (31.8%), and chinolones (22.7%). Resistance to colistin was not detected. Thirty-five isolates (22.7%) showed multiple resistances.

One isolate was resistant to 3rd generation cephalosporines; this isolate was tested in panel 2 and identified as ESBL-producing *E. coli* (synergy test with clavulanic acid positive, susceptible towards cefoxitin).

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Compared to 2014, an increase of fully susceptible isolates could be observed from 33.6% to 42.2% in 2016.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Not available because indicator *E. coli* are not examined in humans.

Additional information

Publication of the results in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria 2016 (AURES 2016).

5.4. β -lactamase- and carbapenemase-producing *E. coli*

5.4.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Specific Monitoring of Beta-Lactamase producing *E. coli* in samples from animals and food has been started in 2015 in accordance with CID 2013/652/EU). Previously, single projects were carried out, eg. in 2012 and in 2013 the AGES conducted projects with food samples collected in one Austrian province. In 2012, 50 samples of fresh broiler meat from conventional and 50 from organic production, as well as 54 samples of fresh turkey meat from conventional and 44 samples from organic production were selective tested for carbapenemase-producing-, ESBL-producing -, and ciprofloxacin resistant *Enterobacteriaceae*. Carbapenemase-producing *Enterobacteriaceae* were not be detected in any food sample. ESBL-producing *Enterobacteriaceae* were found in 30 (60%) of conventional and in 46 (92%) organic broiler meat samples, in 9 (17%) of conventional and 3 (7%) of organic turkey meat samples. Ciprofloxacin resistant *Enterobacteriaceae* were isolated from 48 (96%) of both each, conventional and organic broiler meat samples, and from 51 (94%) of conventional and 43 (98%) of organic turkey meat samples. These isolates showed high co-resistances to ampicillin, tetracyclines and sulfonamides.

In 2013, 100 samples of each pork, beef, and eggs (50 samples each of conventional and organic production) were selective tested for tested for carbapenemase-producing-, ESBL-producing -, ciprofloxacin resistant *Enterobacteriaceae*, and MRSA.

Carbapenemase-producing *Enterobacteriaceae* could not be detected in any food sample. ESBL-producing *Enterobacteriaceae* were found in 6% of conventional and 18% of organic pork meat samples, in 18% of conventional and 6% of organic beef samples, but in none of the tested eggs. Ciprofloxacin resistant *Enterobacteriaceae* were isolated from 22% of conventional and 14% of organic pork meat samples, from 30% of conventional and 4% of organic beef samples, but in none of the examined eggs. MRSA was detected in five conventional and one organic pork meat samples, in seven conventional and four organic beef samples, but was not detected in any eggs sampled.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Broiler meat samples: Three-hundred fresh broiler meat samples were tested, 191 presumptive ESBL-/AmpC-producing *E. coli* (63.7%) were detected and confirmed. Out of 191 isolates tested, 29 (15.2%) did not show resistances to other antimicrobials than to 3rd generation cephalosporines and ampicillin. Very high resistance rates could be observed to sulfonamides (61.8%), and high resistance rates to quinolones (47.6%), to tetracycline (37.7 %), and to trimethoprim (35.1%). Resistance to colistin was detected in one isolate; the mobile plasmid mediated *mcr-1*-gene was confirmed. Multiple resistances were found in 84.8% of the tested isolates. Carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* was not detected.

Broiler caecal samples: Of 306 samples tested, 160 presumptive ESBL-/AmpC-producing *E. coli* (52.3%) were confirmed as enzyme-producing *E. coli*. Twenty-eight isolates (17.5%) did not show resistances to other antimicrobials than to 3rd generation cephalosporines and ampicillin. Very high resistance rates could be observed to sulfonamides (60.0%), to quinolones (58.1%), and to tetracycline (53.1 %). Resistance to colistin was detected in one isolate; the mobile plasmid mediated *mcr-1*-gene was confirmed. Multiple resistances were found in 82.5% of the tested isolates. Carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* was not detected.

Turkey caecal samples: One-hundred and eighty-three samplers were tested, 81 presumptive ESBL-/AmpC-producing *E. coli* were detected and 80 (43.7%) of these confirmed as ESBL-/AmpC-producing *E. coli*. Eleven isolates (13.8%) did not show resistances to other antimicrobials than to 3rd generation cephalosporines and ampicillin. Extremely high resistance rates could be observed to sulfonamides (77.5%), to tetracycline (76.3 %), and very high rates to quinolones (56.3%).

Resistance to colistin was not detected. Multiple resistances were found in 85.2% of the tested isolates. Carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* was not detected.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Although there is a high prevalence of beta-lactamase producing *E. coli* in animal and food samples, their relevance for humans is not clear. Most molecular types of beta-lactamase producing *E. coli* isolated from humans differ from those types found in non-human samples.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

The National Action Plan to control antimicrobial resistance, published on the homepage of the Federal Ministry of Health and Women Affairs

(http://www.bmgfj.gv.at/cms/home/attachments/9/2/1/CH1318/CMS1416214760260/nap_amr.pdf).

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil.

Additional information

Publication of the results in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria, 2016 (AURES 2016).

5.4.2. Antimicrobial resistance of ESBL-/AmpC- /carbapenemase-producing *Escherichia coli* isolates from food

A. Antimicrobial resistance of ESBL-/AmpC-producing *E. coli* from chicken meat, fresh, at retail

Description of sampling designs

In accordance with the harmonized sampling strategy of the CID the sample number for ESBL-/AmpC-producing *E. coli* in fresh broiler meat at retail was 300. The sampling plan was comprised from two different plans, one from the permanent routine sampling and the other from additional sampling.

Routine samples: This is the so-called advanced test-planning within the annual collection of routine samples by the Austrian Food Inspection on the basis of a report from the AGES sampling plan.

Approx. 120 samples are collected at retail all over Austria according to the revision- and sampling plan given in the ordinance Revisions- und Probenplan für das Jahr 2016 acc. to article 31 Lebensmittelsicherheitsgesetz (LMSVG).

Additional samples: For those samples a separate plan for purchasing at retail was created. The purchase of fresh broiler meat samples was carried out by AGES employees in Vienna, Linz, Salzburg, Graz and Innsbruck. The sampling was stratified proportional to the population (including tourist nights) of the Austrian provinces in 2014 (source: Statistics Austria) and distributed evenly over the year.

During the year the analysis of the number of samples revealed that less routine samples than expected arrived in the lab. Therefore the sampling plan had to be adjusted two times: The first time, from April to June the lacking samples were additionally taken; the second adjustment took place in the second semester, when 145 samples were taken instead of the previously planned 88 samples.

All samples were collected as objective samples.

Stratification procedures per animal populations and food categories

See "Description of sampling designs"

Randomisation procedures per animal populations and food categories

See "Description of sampling designs"

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Frequency of the sampling

Sampling was distributed evenly throughout the 12 months of the year.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Type of specimen taken

Fresh broiler meat

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Samples were packed in a sterile bag. The sample was transported in a refrigerator to one of the AGES Official Food Control Laboratories or one of the Regional Food Laboratories. From there the samples were forwarded to the NRL-AR in Graz.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

All samples were checked for conformity and invalid samples were excluded from analysis. Out of 300 samples 191 presumptive ESBL-/AmpC-producing *E. coli* (63.7%) were isolated. All these isolates were directed to susceptibility testing.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Methods used for collecting data

In the laboratory all information was entered into the data base (LISA), also the lab results. The whole file with all data could be downloaded and analyzed using MS Excel®.

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

The methodology was performed as described in the EURL-protocoll: "LABORATORY PROTOCOL: Isolation of ESBL-, AmpC- and carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* from caecal samples. Versions 3"

Laboratory used for detection for resistance - Antimicrobials included in monitoring

NRL-AR: All isolates were subjected to susceptibility testing as described by the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI), which is accepted as an international reference method (ISO standard 20776-1:2006 (ISO, 2006)), as stated in Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU (Annex, Part A, Table 1; panel 1 and 2).

Laboratory used for detection for resistance - Cut-off values used in testing

Application of European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (EUCAST) epidemiological cut-off values (ECOFFs) for the interpretation of microbiological resistance (as stated in CID 2013/652/EU).

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place

The control program is in line with the EU Commission and described in the National Action Plan (NAP) published on the homepage of the Federal Ministry of Health (http://www.bmgfi.gv.at/cms/home/attachments/9/2/1/CH1318/CMS1416214760260/nap_amr.pdf).

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

No measures foreseen in case of resistant isolates.

Notification system in place

No notification foreseen in case of resistant isolates.

Results of the investigation

Three-hundred fresh broiler meat samples were tested, 191 presumptive ESBL-/AmpC-producing *E. coli* (63.7%) were detected and confirmed. Out of 191 isolates tested, 29 (15.2%) did not show resistances to other antimicrobials than to 3rd generation cephalosporines and ampicillin. Very high resistance rates could be observed to sulfonamides (61.8%), and high resistance rates to quinolones (47.6%), to tetracycline (37.7%), and to trimethoprim (35.1%). Resistance to colistin was detected in one isolate; the mobile plasmid mediated *mcr-1*-gene was confirmed. Multiple resistances were found in 84.8% of the tested isolates.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

This monitoring in fresh broiler meat from broilers was performed for the first time, therefore the significance is difficult to assess. Compared to 52.3% of ESBL-/AmpC-producing *E. coli* in caecal samples from broilers and 43.7% from turkeys, broiler meat samples are even higher contaminated; in 2015, fresh pork (8.5%) and fresh beef samples (3.0%) showed much lower contamination rates with ESBL-/AmpC-producing *E. coli* than fresh broiler meat in 2016.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

The relevance has to be analyzed by comparing the strains from humans and from broilers.

Additional information

Publication of the results in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria 2016 (AURES 2016).

B. Antimicrobial resistance of carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* from chicken meat, fresh. at retail

Description of sampling designs

See chapter “ESBL-/AmpC-producing *E. coli* in fresh broiler meat at retail”

Stratification procedures per animal populations and food categories

See chapter “ESBL-/AmpC-producing *E. coli* in fresh broiler meat at retail”

Randomisation procedures per animal populations and food categories

See chapter “ESBL-/AmpC-producing *E. coli* in fresh broiler meat at retail”

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Frequency of the sampling

See chapter “ESBL-/AmpC-producing *E. coli* in fresh broiler meat at retail”

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Type of specimen taken

See chapter “ESBL-/AmpC-producing *E. coli* in fresh broiler meat at retail”

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

See chapter “ESBL-/AmpC-producing *E. coli* in fresh broiler meat at retail”

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

See chapter “ESBL-/AmpC-producing *E. coli* in fresh broiler meat at retail”

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Methods used for collecting data

See chapter “ESBL-/AmpC-producing *E. coli* in fresh broiler meat at retail”

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

See chapter “ESBL-/AmpC-producing *E. coli* in fresh broiler meat at retail”

Laboratory used for detection for resistance - Antimicrobials included in monitoring

See chapter “ESBL-/AmpC-producing *E. coli* in fresh broiler meat at retail”

Laboratory used for detection for resistance - Cut-off values used in testing

See chapter “ESBL-/AmpC-producing *E. coli* in fresh broiler meat at retail”

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place

See chapter “ESBL-/AmpC-producing *E. coli* in fresh broiler meat at retail”

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

See chapter “ESBL-/AmpC-producing *E. coli* in fresh broiler meat at retail”

Notification system in place

See chapter “ESBL-/AmpC-producing *E. coli* in fresh broiler meat at retail”

Results of the investigation

295 samples of fresh beef were analyzed on selective media for carbapenemase-producing *E. coli*. Carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* was not detected in any fresh beef sample.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* was not detected in any fresh broiler meat sample tested.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* was not detected in any fresh broiler meat sample tested.

Additional information

Publication of the results in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria 2016 (AURES 2016).

5.4.3. Antimicrobial resistance of ESBL-/AmpC- /carbapenemase-producing *Escherichia coli* isolates from animals

A. Antimicrobial resistance of ESBL-/AmpC-producing *E. coli* from broiler flocks

Description of sampling designs

In 2016, the monitoring for ESBL-/AmpC-producing *E. coli* was performed according to CID 2013/652/EU. Out of 433 flocks that had to be sampled for isolation of *C. jejuni*, designated 300 samples had to be tested for the presence ESBL-/AmpC-producing *E. coli*. For more details see chapter “*Campylobacter* in animals”.

Stratification procedures per animal populations and food categories

Sampling was performed in the 4 broiler abattoirs, where >80% of all Austrian broiler flocks are slaughtered. For stratification procedures the number of slaughtered batches per abattoir 2013 and 2014 were collected (data source: Poultry Health Data, PHD). The samples were stratified proportionally by slaughterhouses in accordance with their annual throughputs. The number of samples per slaughterhouse was evenly distributed throughout the year, given as number of samples per month. According to their throughput of slaughtered flocks, 126 (abattoir A), 87 (B), 9 (C), and 78 (D) samples had to be taken in the abattoirs. The sampling plan also determined the number of slaughter batches that had to be sampled every month.

Randomisation procedures per animal populations and food categories

The sampling was performed after evisceration by officially and designated veterinarians carrying out the post-mortem inspection.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Frequency of the sampling

See above at: Stratification procedures per animal populations and food categories

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Type of specimen taken

Intestines of 10 animals per slaughter batch.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

The sampling was performed by officially and designated veterinarians carrying out the post-mortem inspection. At time of evisceration the whole intestines of 10 animals per slaughter batch were taken, wrapped in a sterile plastic bag and cooled down to 4°C. Using a polystyrene box with freezer bags the samples were sent to the AGES Institute of Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, Department for Veterinary Microbiology (VEMI) in Graz. In the laboratory the temperature of the content was measured, caecums of each intestinal convolute were identified and some content of each caecum pooled and cultured by direct plating onto selective medium and incubated.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

Out of 306 samples 160 presumptive ESBL-/AmpC-producing *E. coli* (52.3%) were isolated. All these isolates were directed to susceptibility testing.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Methods used for collecting data

Each sample taken was accompanied by an electronic order form from the Poultry Health Data (PHD).

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

The methodology was performed as described in the EURL-protocoll: "LABORATORY PROTOCOL: Isolation of ESBL-, AmpC- and carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* from caecal samples. Versions 3"

Laboratory used for detection for resistance - Antimicrobials included in monitoring

NRL-AR: All isolates were subjected to susceptibility testing as described by the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI), which is accepted as an international reference method (ISO standard 20776-1:2006 (ISO, 2006)), as stated in Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU (Annex, Part A, Table 1; panel 1 and 2).

Laboratory used for detection for resistance - Cut-off values used in testing

Application of European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (EUCAST) epidemiological cut-off values (ECOFFs) for the interpretation of microbiological resistance (as stated in CID 2013/652/EU).

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place

The control program is in line with the EU Commission and described in the National Action Plan (NAP) published on the homepage of the Federal Ministry of Health

(http://www.bmgfj.gv.at/cms/home/attachments/9/2/1/CH1318/CMS1416214760260/nap_amr.pdf).

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

No measures foreseen in case of resistant isolates.

Notification system in place

No notification foreseen in case of resistant isolates.

Results of the investigation

All 160 presumptive ESBL-/AmpC-producing *E. coli* (52.3%) were confirmed as enzyme-producing *E. coli*. Twenty-eight isolates (17.5%) did not show resistances to other antimicrobials than to 3rd generation cephalosporines and ampicillin. Very high resistance rates could be observed to sulfonamides (60.0%), to quinolones (58.1%), and to tetracycline (53.1 %). Resistance to colistin was detected in one isolate; the mobile plasmid mediated *mcr-1*-gene was confirmed. Multiple resistances were found in 82.5% of the tested isolates.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

This monitoring in caeca from broilers was performed for the first time therefore the significance is difficult to assess. Compared to 52.1% of ESBL-/AmpC-producing *E. coli* in caecal samples from pigs in 2015 and 43.7% in turkeys in 2016, the proportion of positive samples was the same in broilers.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

The relevance has to be analyzed by comparing the strains from humans and from broilers.

Additional information

Publication of the results in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria 2016 (AURES 2016).

B. Antimicrobial resistance of Carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* from broiler flocks

Description of sampling designs

In 2016, the monitoring for carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* was performed according to CID 2013/652/EU. Out of 433 flocks that had to be sampled for isolation of *C. jejuni*, designated 300 samples had to be tested for the presence ESBL-/AmpC-producing *E. coli*. For more details see chapter “*Campylobacter* in animals”.

Stratification procedures per animal populations and food categories

Sampling was performed in the 4 broiler abattoirs, where >80% of all Austrian broiler flocks are slaughtered. For stratification procedures the number of slaughtered batches per abattoir 2013 and 2014 were collected (data source: Poultry Health Data, PHD). The samples were stratified proportionally by slaughterhouses in accordance with their annual throughputs. The number of samples per slaughterhouse was evenly distributed throughout the year, given as number of samples per month. According to their throughput of slaughtered flocks, 126 (abattoir A), 87 (B), 9 (C), and 78 (D) samples had to be taken in the abattoirs. The sampling plan also determined the number of slaughter batches that had to be sampled every month.

Randomisation procedures per animal populations and food categories

The sampling was performed after evisceration by officially and designated veterinarians carrying out the post-mortem inspection.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Frequency of the sampling

See above at: Stratification procedures per animal populations and food categories

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Type of specimen taken

Intestines of 10 animals per slaughter batch.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

The sampling was performed by officially and designated veterinarians carrying out the post-mortem inspection. At time of evisceration the whole intestines of 10 animals per slaughter batch were taken, wrapped in a sterile plastic bag and cooled down to 4°C. Using a polystyrene box with freezer bags the samples were sent to the AGES Institute of Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, Department for Veterinary Microbiology (VEMI) in Graz. In the laboratory the temperature of the content was measured, caecums of each intestinal convolute were identified and some content of each caecum pooled and cultured by direct plating onto selective medium and incubated.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

In 306 samples no carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* was detected.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Methods used for collecting data

Each sample taken was accompanied by an electronic order form from the Poultry Health Data (PHD).

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

The methodology was performed as described in the EURL-protocoll: “LABORATORY PROTOCOL: Isolation of ESBL-, AmpC- and carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* from caecal samples. Versions 3”

Laboratory used for detection for resistance - Antimicrobials included in monitoring

No carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* was obtained in the course of the monitoring

Laboratory used for detection for resistance - Cut-off values used in testing

No carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* was obtained in the course of the monitoring

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place

No carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* was obtained in the course of the monitoring

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

No carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* was obtained in the course of the monitoring

Notification system in place

No carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* was obtained in the course of the monitoring

Results of the investigation

No carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* was obtained in the course of the monitoring

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

No carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* was obtained in the course of the monitoring

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

No carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* was obtained in the course of the monitoring

Additional information

Publication of the results in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria 2016 (AURES 2016).

C. Antimicrobial resistance of ESBL-/AmpC-producing *E. coli* from turkey flocks

Description of sampling designs

In 2016, the monitoring for ESBL-/AmpC-producing *E. coli* was performed according to CID 2013/652/EU. Out of 221 flocks that had to be sampled for isolation of *C. jejuni*, designated 150 samples had to be tested for the presence ESBL-/AmpC-producing *E. coli*. During the DG(Sante)-audit 2016-8918 – MR in April 2016 the audit team did not approve Austria's decision of 150 samples for ESBL-/AmpC-producing *E. coli*. Therefore the sampling plan was adjusted and all Austrian turkey flocks slaughtered in Austria should be sampled to obtain as many as possible indicator *E. coli*-isolates. For more details see chapter "*Campylobacter* in animals".

Stratification procedures per animal populations and food categories

See chapter: *C. jejuni* isolates from caecal samples gathered at slaughter from fattening turkeys.

Randomisation procedures per animal populations and food categories

See chapter: *C. jejuni* isolates from caecal samples gathered at slaughter from fattening turkeys.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Frequency of the sampling

See chapter: *C. jejuni* isolates from caecal samples gathered at slaughter from fattening turkeys.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Type of specimen taken

Intestines of 10 animals per slaughter batch.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

The sampling was performed by officially and designated veterinarians carrying out the post-mortem inspection. At time of evisceration caeca of 10 animals per slaughter batch were taken, wrapped in a sterile plastic bag and cooled down to 4°C. Using a polystyrene box with freezer bags the samples were sent to the AGES Institute of Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, Department for Veterinary Microbiology (VEMI) in Graz. In the laboratory the temperature of the content was measured, caeca were identified and some content of each caecum pooled and cultured by direct plating onto selective medium and incubated.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

One hundred and eighty-three samples were tested; presumptive of ESBL-/AmpC-producing *E. coli* isolates were detected in 81 samples (44.3%). All these isolates were antimicrobial susceptibility tested.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Methods used for collecting data

Each sample taken was accompanied by an electronic order form from the Poultry Health Data (PHD).

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

The methodology was performed as described in the EURL-protocol: "LABORATORY PROTOCOL: Isolation of ESBL-, AmpC- and carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* from caecal samples. Versions 3"

Laboratory used for detection for resistance - Antimicrobials included in monitoring

NRL-AR: All isolates were subjected to susceptibility testing as described by the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI), which is accepted as an international reference method (ISO standard 20776-1:2006 (ISO, 2006)), as stated in Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU (Annex, Part A, Table 1; panel 1 and 2).

Laboratory used for detection for resistance - Cut-off values used in testing

Application of European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (EUCAST) epidemiological cut-off values (ECOFFs) for the interpretation of microbiological resistance (as stated in CID 2013/652/EU).

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place

The control program is in line with the EU Commission and described in the National Action Plan (NAP) published on the homepage of the Federal Ministry of Health (http://www.bmgfi.gv.at/cms/home/attachments/9/2/1/CH1318/CMS1416214760260/nap_amr.pdf).

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

No measures foreseen in case of resistant isolates.

Notification system in place

No notification foreseen in case of resistant isolates.

Results of the investigation

One-hundred and eighty-three samplers were tested, 81 presumptive ESBL-/AmpC-producing *E. coli* were detected and 80 (43.7%) of these confirmed as ESBL-/AmpC-producing *E. coli*. Eleven isolates (13.8%) did not show resistances to other antimicrobials than to 3rd generation cephalosporines and ampicillin. Extremely high resistance rates could be observed to sulfonamides (77.5%), to tetracycline (76.3 %), and very high rates to quinolones (56.3%). Resistance to colistin was not detected. Multiple resistances were found in 85.2% of the tested isolates.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

This monitoring in caeca from turkeys was performed for the first time therefore the significance is difficult to assess. Compared to the prevalence of ESBL-/AmpC-producing *E. coli* in caecal samples from broilers (52.3% and from pigs in 2015 (52.1%), the proportion of positive samples in turkeys was slightly lower.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

The relevance has to be analyzed by comparing the strains from humans and from broilers.

Additional information

Publication of the results in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria 2016 (AURES 2016).

D. Antimicrobial resistance of carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* from turkey flocks

Description of sampling designs

In 2016, the monitoring for ESBL-/AmpC-producing *E. coli* was performed according to CID 2013/652/EU. Out of 221 flocks that had to be sampled for isolation of *C. jejuni*, designated 150 samples had to be tested for the presence carbapenemase-producing *E. coli*. During the DG(Sante)-

audit 2016-8918 – MR in April 2016 the audit team did not approve Austria’s decision of 150 samples for ESBL-/AmpC-producing *E. coli*. Therefor the sampling plan was adjusted and all Austrian turkey flocks slaughtered in Austria should be sampled to obtain as many as possible indicator *E. coli*-isolates. For more details see chapter “*Campylobacter* in animals”.

Stratification procedures per animal populations and food categories

See chapter: *C. jejuni* isolates from caecal samples gathered at slaughter from fattening turkeys.

Randomisation procedures per animal populations and food categories

See chapter: *C. jejuni* isolates from caecal samples gathered at slaughter from fattening turkeys.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Frequency of the sampling

See chapter: *C. jejuni* isolates from caecal samples gathered at slaughter from fattening turkeys.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Type of specimen taken

Intestines of 10 animals per slaughter batch.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

The sampling was performed by officially and designated veterinarians carrying out the post-mortem inspection. At time of evisceration caeca of 10 animals per slaughter batch were taken, wrapped in a sterile plastic bag and cooled down to 4°C. Using a polystyrene box with freezer bags the samples were sent to the AGES Institute of Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, Department for Veterinary Microbiology (VEMH) in Graz. In the laboratory the temperature of the content was measured, caeca were identified and some content of each caecum pooled and cultured by direct plating onto selective medium and incubated.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

One hundred and eighty-three samples were tested and no carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* was detected.

Sampling strategy used in monitoring - Methods used for collecting data

Each sample taken was accompanied by an electronic order form from the Poultry Health Data (PHD).

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

The methodology was performed as described in the EURL-protocol: “LABORATORY PROTOCOL: Isolation of ESBL-, AmpC- and carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* from caecal samples. Versions 3”.

Laboratory used for detection for resistance - Antimicrobials included in monitoring

No carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* was obtained in the course of the monitoring.

Laboratory used for detection for resistance - Cut-off values used in testing

No carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* was obtained in the course of the monitoring.

Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place

No carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* was obtained in the course of the monitoring.

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

No carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* was obtained in the course of the monitoring.

Notification system in place

No carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* was obtained in the course of the monitoring.

Results of the investigation

No carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* was obtained in the course of the monitoring.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

No carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* was obtained in the course of the monitoring.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

No carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* was obtained in the course of the monitoring.

Additional information

Publication of the results in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria 2016 (AURES 2016).

Table 90 Breakpoints used for antibiotic resistance testing of *E. coli* from food and animals, 2016

antimicrobial	ECOFF	Range tested		
	concentration (µg/ml)			
	wild type < =	lowest	highest	
panel 1	aminoglycosids - gentamicin	2	0.5	32
	amphenicols - chloramphenicol	16	8	128
	carbapenems - meropenem	0.125	0.03	16
	cephalosporines - cefotaxime	0.25	0.25	4
	cephalosporines - ceftazidime	0.5	0.5	8
	fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	0.064	0.016	8
	glycylcyclines - tigecycline	0.5	0.25	8
	macrolides - azithromycin	16	2	64
	penicillins - ampicillin	8	1	64
	polymyxins - colistin	2	1	16
	quinolones - nalidixic acid	16	4	128
	sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	64	8	1024
	tetracyclines - tetracycline	8	2	64
	trimethoprim	2	0.25	32
panel 2	carbapenems - ertapenem	0.06	0.016	2
	carbapenems - imipenem	0.5	0.12	16
	carbapenems - meropenem	0.125	0.03	16
	cephalosporines - cefepim	0.125	0.06	32
	cephalosporines - cefotaxime	0.25	0.25	64
	cephalosporines - cefoxitin	8	0.5	64
	cephalosporines - ceftazidime	0.5	0.25	128
	clavulanate synergy with cefotaxime	NA	0.06	64
	clavulanate synergy with ceftazidime	NA	0.12	128
	penicillins, extended-spectrum - temocillin	32	0.5	128

Number of fully-susceptible and number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 or >4 antimicrobials of different classes, excluding cross-resistance. For *E. coli* this includes resistance to ampicillin, cefotaxime/ceftazidime, meropenem, ciprofloxacin/nalidixic acid, tetracycline, gentamicin, colistin, trimethoprim, sulfonamides, chloramphenicol, tigecycline.

Table 91 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of indicator *E. coli* in animals (qualitative tables), 2016

<i>E. coli</i>	broiler flocks			turkey flocks		
	total units tested	micro-biological resistant		total units tested	micro-biological resistant	
	N	%R	n	N	%R	n
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	170	3.5	6	154	4.5	7
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	170	4.7	8	154	8.4	13
carbapenems - meropenem	170	0.0	0	154	0.0	0
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	170	0.6	1	154	0.6	1
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	170	0.6	1	154	0.6	1
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	170	47.1	80	154	22.7	35
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	170	0.6	1	154	0.0	0
macrolides - azithromycin	170	1.8	3	154	0.0	0
penicillins - ampicillin	170	32.9	56	154	31.8	49
polymyxins - colistin	170	0.0	0	154	0.0	0
quinolones - nalidixic acid	170	45.3	77	154	16.9	26
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	170	37.1	63	154	18.2	28
tetracyclines - tetracycline	170	22.4	38	154	40.9	63
trimethoprim	170	29.4	50	154	11.0	17
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%R	n	N	%R	n
fully sensitive	170	33.5	57	154	42.2	65
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	170	22.4	38	154	18.8	29
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	170	11.2	19	154	16.2	25
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	170	11.8	20	154	10.4	16
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	170	10.0	17	154	6.5	10
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	170	11.2	19	154	5.8	9

antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant		total units tested	micro-biological resistant	
	N	%R	n	N	%R	n
	carbapenems - ertapenem	1	0	0	1	0
carbapenems - imipenem	1	0	0	1	0	0
carbapenems - meropenem	1	0	0	1	0	0
cephalosporines - cefepim	1	100	1	1	100	1
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	1	100	1	1	100	1
cephalosporines - ceftoxitin	1	100	1	1	0	0
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	1	100	1	1	100	1
clavulanate synergy with cefotaxime	1	100	1	1	100	1
clavulanate synergy with ceftazidime	1	100	1	1	100	1
penicillins, extended-spectrum - temocillin	1	0	0	1	0	0

N = number of isolates tested, n = number of resistant isolates, %R = % isolates resistant

Table 92 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of indicator *E. coli* in broiler flocks - quantitative data, 2016

zoonotic agent	<i>E. coli</i>
matrix	broiler flocks
sampling context	AMR monitoring

Panel 1

Number of isolates available in the laboratory 170 Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:

antimicrobial	total units tested		micro-biological resistant	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																					
	N	%R		n	= < 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	170	3.5	6							131	32	1	-	4	-	-	2								
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	170	4.7	8												150	12	2	-	3	3					
carbapenems - meropenem	170	0.0	0		169	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	170	0.6	1					169	-	-	-	-	-	1											
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	170	0.6	1					169	-	-	-	-	-	1											
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	170	47.1	80		83	6	1	5	38	19	8	-	-	6	4										
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	170	0.6	1					161	8	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
macrolides - azithromycin	170	1.8	3								4	55	75	33	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
penicillins - ampicillin	170	32.9	56								3	39	69	3	-	-	-	56							
polymyxins - colistin	170	0.0	0							170	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
quinolones - nalidixic acid	170	45.3	77											89	3	1	3	15	29	30					
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	170	37.1	63												27	55	20	5	1	-	-	-	-	62	
tetracyclines - tetracycline	170	22.4	38										104	27	1	-	-	15	23						
trimethoprim	170	29.4	50						49	52	18	1	-	-	-	-	50								

N = number of isolates tested, n = number of resistant isolates, %R = % isolates resistant

Table 92, cont.

Number of isolates available in the laboratory		1		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant		= < 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
	N	%R	n	n																			
Panel 2	carbapenems - ertapenem	1	0.0	0	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	carbapenems - imipenem	1	0.0	0	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	carbapenems - meropenem	1	0.0	0	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	cephalosporines - cefepim	1	100.0	1	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	cephalosporines - cefotaxime	1	100.0	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	cephalosporines - ceftoxitin	1	100.0	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-
	cephalosporines - ceftazidime	1	100.0	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	clavulanate synergy with cefotaxime	1	100.0	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	clavulanate synergy with ceftazidime	1	100.0	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	penicillins, extended-spectrum - temocillin	1	0.0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

N = number of isolates tested, n = number of resistant isolates, %R = % isolates resistant

Table 93, cont.

Number of isolates available in the laboratory		1		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant		= < 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
		%R	n																				
Panel 2	N	%R	n																				
carbapenems - ertapenem	1	0.0	0	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
carbapenems - imipenem	1	0.0	0	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
carbapenems - meropenem	1	0.0	0	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
cephalosporines - cefepim	1	100.0	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	1	100.0	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-
cephalosporines - ceftaxitin	1	0.0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	1	100.0	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
clavulanate synergy with cefotaxime	1	100.0	1	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
clavulanate synergy with ceftazidime	1	100.0	1	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
penicillins, extended-spectrum - temocillin	1	0.0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

N = number of isolates tested, n = number of resistant isolates, %R = % isolates resistant

Table 94 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of ESBL/AmpC producing *E. coli* from animals and food (qualitative tables), 2016

ESBL		broiler meat			broiler flocks			turkey flocks		
antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant		total units tested	micro-biological resistant		total units tested	micro-biological resistant		
	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	191	11.5	22	160	15.6	25	81	3.7	3	
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	191	9.9	19	160	14.4	23	81	4.9	4	
carbapenems - meropenem	191	0.0	0	160	0.0	0	81	0.0	0	
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	191	100	191	160	100	160	81	100	81	
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	191	95.8	183	160	97.5	156	81	97.5	79	
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	191	47.6	91	160	58.1	93	81	55.6	45	
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	191	0.5	1	160	3.8	6	81	1.2	1	
macrolides - azithromycin	191	1.0	2	160	1.3	2	81	1.2	1	
penicillins - ampicillin	191	100	191	160	100	160	81	100	81	
polymyxins - colistin	191	0.5	1	160	0.6	1	81	0.0	0	
quinolones - nalidixic acid	191	43.5	83	160	46.3	74	81	46.9	38	
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	191	61.8	118	160	60.0	96	81	76.5	62	
tetracyclines - tetracycline	191	37.7	72	160	53.1	85	81	75.3	61	
trimethoprim	191	35.1	67	160	23.1	37	81	48.1	39	
Number of multiresistant isolates										
fully sensitive	191	0.0	0	160	0.0	0	81	0.0	0	
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	191	0.0	0	160	0.0	0	81	0.0	0	
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	191	15.2	29	160	17.5	28	81	14.8	12	
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	191	23.6	45	160	20.0	32	81	9.9	8	
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	191	23.6	45	160	10.6	17	81	18.5	15	
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	191	37.7	72	160	51.9	83	81	56.8	46	

antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant		total units tested	micro-biological resistant		total units tested	micro-biological resistant	
	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n
carbapenems - ertapenem	191	1.0	2	160	0.6	1	81	0	0
carbapenems - imipenem	191	0	0	160	0	0	81	0	0
carbapenems - meropenem	191	0	0	160	0	0	81	0	0
cephalosporines - cefepim	191	83.8	160	160	88.1	141	81	86.4	70
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	191	100	191	160	100	160	81	100	81
cephalosporines - ceftaxitin	191	50.8	97	160	56.3	90	81	25.9	21
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	191	94.8	181	160	97.5	156	81	98.8	80
clavulanate synergy with cefotaxime	191	100	191	160	100	160	81	100	81
clavulanate synergy with ceftazidime	191	100	191	160	100	160	81	100	81
penicillins, extended-spectrum - temocillin	191	0	0	160	0	0	81	0	0

Table 95 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. coli* in broiler meat - quantitative data, 2016

zoonotic agent	<i>ESBL</i>
matrix	broiler meat
sampling context	ESBL monitoring

Panel 1

Number of isolates available in the laboratory		191		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant		=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
		%R	n																				
	N	%R	n																				
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	191	11.5	22							148	20	1	-	-	12	6	4						
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	191	9.9	19											170	2	4	7	4	4				
carbapenems - meropenem	191	0.0	0	191	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	191	100.0	191					-	1	5	13	20	152										
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	191	95.8	183						8	41	25	13	68	36									
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	191	47.6	91	91	6	3	7	42	15	6	4	2	6	9									
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	191	0.5	1					176	14	1	-	-	-										
macrolides - azithromycin	191	1.0	2								42	109	36	2	1	-	1						
penicillins - ampicillin	191	100.0	191														4	187					
polymyxins - colistin	191	0.5	1							190	-	1	-	-									
quinolones - nalidixic acid	191	43.5	83									99	6	3	10	11	31	31					
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	191	61.8	118										10	35	23	5	-	-	-	-	118		
tetracyclines - tetracycline	191	37.7	72								116	3	-	1	-	28	43						
trimethoprim	191	35.1	67					63	50	10	1	-	-	-	-	67							

N = number of isolates tested, n = number of resistant isolates, %R = % isolates resistant

Table 95, cont.

Number of isolates available in the laboratory		191		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant		= < 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
				N	%R	n																		
carbapenems - ertapenem	191	1.0	2	112	71	6	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
carbapenems - imipenem	191	0.0	0	-	-	-	152	37	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
carbapenems - meropenem	191	0.0	0	191	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
cephalosporines - cefepim	191	83.8	160	-	3	28	69	13	2	8	34	26	7	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	191	100.0	191	-	-	-	-	1	6	7	19	78	21	27	25	7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
cephalosporines - ceftoxitin	191	50.8	97	-	-	-	-	-	2	63	29	7	6	71	13	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	191	94.8	181	-	-	-	10	42	19	12	51	48	9	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
clavulanate synergy with cefotaxime	191	100.0	191	-	92	6	-	1	4	5	62	20	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
clavulanate synergy with ceftazidime	191	100.0	191	-	-	77	20	1	-	10	39	41	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
penicillins, extended-spectrum - temocillin	191	0.0	0	-	-	-	-	-	1	11	88	88	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

N = number of isolates tested, n = number of resistant isolates, %R = % isolates resistant

Table 96 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. coli* in broiler flocks - quantitative data, 2016

zoonotic agent	ESBL
matrix	broiler flocks
sampling context	AMR monitoring

Panel 1

Number of isolates available in the laboratory		160		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant																						
	N	%R	n	< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
				n																				
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	160	15.6	25						113	22	-	-	1	6	16	2								
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	160	14.4	23											129	8	5	12	5	1					
carbapenems - meropenem	160	0.0	0	160	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	160	100.0	160					-	-	2	17	25	116											
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	160	97.5	156					4	21	12	11	52	60											
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	160	58.1	93	64	3	-	6	29	27	3	1	-	2	25										
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	160	3.8	6					131	23	6	-	-	-											
macrolides - azithromycin	160	1.3	2								25	81	51	1	2	-								
penicillins - ampicillin	160	100.0	160							-	-	-	-	-	-	2	158							
polymyxins - colistin	160	0.6	1							159	-	1	-	-										
quinolones - nalidixic acid	160	46.3	74										71	6	9	2	12	20	40					
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	160	60.0	96											10	25	25	4	-	-	-	-	96		
tetracyclines - tetracycline	160	53.1	85									70	5	-	-	1	18	66						
trimethoprim	160	23.1	37					56	42	21	4	-	-	-	-	37								

N = number of isolates tested, n = number of resistant isolates, %R = % isolates resistant

Table 96, cont.

Number of isolates available in the laboratory		160		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant		= < 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
	N	%R	n	n																				
Panel 2	carbapenems - ertapenem	160	0.6	1	90	62	7	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	carbapenems - imipenem	160	0.0	0	-	-	-	122	38	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	carbapenems - meropenem	160	0.0	0	-	158	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	cephalosporines - cefepim	160	88.1	141	-	-	2	17	61	18	6	2	22	25	6	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	cephalosporines - cefotaxime	160	100.0	160	-	-	-	-	-	2	10	24	64	13	14	18	15	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	cephalosporines - ceftoxitin	160	56.3	90	-	-	-	-	-	-	5	37	28	19	4	50	17	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	cephalosporines - ceftazidime	160	97.5	156	-	-	-	-	4	18	16	11	42	53	15	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	clavulanate synergy with cefotaxime	160	100.0	160	-	79	8	-	-	4	1	42	24	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	clavulanate synergy with ceftazidime	160	100.0	160	-	-	-	65	21	1	-	8	21	42	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	penicillins, extended-spectrum - temocillin	160	0.0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	5	62	80	13	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

N = number of isolates tested, n = number of resistant isolates, %R = % isolates resistant

Table 97 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. coli* in turkey flocks - quantitative data, 2016

zoonotic agent	ESBL
matrix	turkey flocks
sampling context	AMR monitoring

Panel 1

Number of isolates available in the laboratory		81		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																						
antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	N	%R	n	= < 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
						aminoglycosids - gentamicin	81	3.7	3								66	12	-	-	-	-	1	1	1	
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	81	4.9	4													76	1	1	1	1						
carbapenems - meropenem	81	0.0	0			80	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	81	100.0	81							-	-	1	6	3	71											
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	81	97.5	79							2	17	34	13	10	5											
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	81	55.6	45			35	1	-	1	30	3	-	-	-	7	4										
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	81	1.2	1							71	9	1	-	-	-											
macrolides - azithromycin	81	1.2	1										10	53	16	1	-	-	1							
penicillins - ampicillin	81	100.0	81										-	-	-	-	-	-	1	80						
polymyxins - colistin	81	0.0	0								81	-	-	-	-											
quinolones - nalidixic acid	81	46.9	38											37	3	3	-	9	15	14						
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	81	76.5	62												3	8	6	2	-	-	-	-	-	62		
tetracyclines - tetracycline	81	75.3	61										18	2	-	-	-	10	51							
trimethoprim	81	48.1	39							13	25	4	-	-	-	-	-	39								

N = number of isolates tested, n = number of resistant isolates, %R = % isolates resistant

Table 97, cont.

Number of isolates available in the laboratory		81		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant		= < 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
		N	%R	n	n																			
carbapenems - ertapenem	81	0.0	0	44	32	5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
carbapenems - imipenem	81	0.0	0	-	-	-	61	20	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
carbapenems - meropenem	81	0.0	0	80	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
cephalosporines - cefepim	81	86.4	70	-	-	2	9	10	2	-	-	23	21	12	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	81	100.0	81	-	-	-	-	-	1	4	5	7	11	20	19	14	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
cephalosporines - ceftoxitin	81	25.9	21	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	23	38	1	2	8	9	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	81	98.8	80	-	-	-	1	1	16	34	11	10	7	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
clavulanate synergy with cefotaxime	81	100.0	81	-	-	41	21	-	-	3	2	7	7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
clavulanate synergy with ceftazidime	81	100.0	81	-	-	-	31	30	1	-	5	8	6	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
penicillins, extended-spectrum - temocillin	81	0.0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	25	53	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

N = number of isolates tested, n = number of resistant isolates, %R = % isolates resistant

5.5. *Enterococcus* Indicators

5.5.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Resistance monitoring of faeces isolates from slaughtered animals was started in Austria from 2004 to 2012 but that program was suspended in 2013.

6. Information on specific microbiological agents

6.1. Staphylococcal Enterotoxins

6.1.1. Staphylococcal enterotoxins general evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Staphylococcal food intoxication is not a major health problem in Austria. Nevertheless there are two staphylococcal food poisoning outbreaks documented in the last 10 years.

September 2006: Outbreak of an acute gastroenteritis in an Austrian boarding school caused by *Staphylococcus aureus* producing Enterotoxins A and D in rice. Afflicted were 113 persons/101 hospitalised because of vomiting and circulatory collapse. The rice had been contaminated by a kitchenstaff.

June 2007: Outbreak of staphylococcal food intoxication after consumption of pasteurized milk products. 166 children had fallen ill with abdominal cramps and vomiting caused by school milk products containing staphylococcal Enterotoxins A and D. The source of the contamination was three milk producing cows with subclinical mastitis.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The analysis of food samples consists of two steps, a prescreening to identify samples harbouring > 100,000 coagulase-positive staphylococci CFU per gram; in that case, a second screening step is applied directly in all types of food matrices according to the European screening method given by the EURL for coagulase positive staphylococci to detect staphylococcal enterotoxins (SE) types A to E. The direct testing for staphylococcal enterotoxins is done in case of outbreaks or when food was pasteurised or heated before the screening for coagulasepositive staphylococci.

Because it is not known how many and which samples were tested for coagulase-positive staphylococci the results cannot be reported.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Hygiene is of utmost importance in food producing process and in the kitchen to prevent contamination with coagulasepositive staphylococci. Additionally precautions must be taken to ensure and control the effective maintaining of the refrigeration chain.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Not available

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Continue the efforts already started to improve harmonization of the detection of staphylococcal enterotoxins types A to E in food matrices.

Additional information

Not available

6.1.2. Staphylococcal enterotoxins in foodstuff

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

In 2016, foodstuffs were sampled all over Austria according to the national control plan given in the ordinance „Nationaler Kontrollplan für das Jahr 2015 gem. § 31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2016“ (BMG-75500/0168-II/B/13/2015) from the Federal Ministry of Health. This “Nationaler Kontrollplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2016-2018) according to the Art. 41ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004 and consists of several separated parts: The revision plan (“Revisionsplan”) determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be visited and inspected. Every food business has to be inspected regularly. The inspection comprises sampling, hygienic investigations of the establishment and the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc. The sampling plan is comprised of scheduled (“Planproben”) and suspect samples (“Verdachtsproben”). In 2016, the sampling plan intended approximately 20,000 scheduled samples and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). This yearly sampling plan determines the number of samples for each stage (retail, processing plants, primary production) and for each food category that has to be investigated randomly. If specific suspicions (e.g. colour deviation, temperature, etc.) initiate the sampling by officials, these samples are categorised as suspect samples. Moreover any follow up sampling (e.g. due to RASFF, monitoring, positive samples, further information, etc.) is defined as suspect sample as well as food samples from private persons or sampling due to outbreak situations. In addition there are monitoring plans, so called campaigns, for specific food items (about 55-60 individual campaigns per year). In the course of those campaigns food items of special interest are investigated for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents. In order to gain in-depth information the sampling takes place during a specified time frame. In 2016, 4 different food campaigns were conducted throughout Austria dealing with zoonotic agents. Each campaign is described in detail and results are depicted in the respective chapters per pathogen.

Definition of positive finding

Detection of staphylococcal enterotoxins A to E in food .

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Prescreening: Several food (e. g. ice-cream, meat, cheese, etc.) is tested for coagulase-positive staphylococci. If the number of detected staphylococci exceeds 100,000 CFU/g, the food matrices are further tested for staphylococcal enterotoxins A to E following the European screening method of the EU-RL for coagulasepositive staphylococci, including *Staphylococcus aureus* using commercially available ELISAs. A positive screening result leads to an identification of the toxin group by another ELISA or a RPLA (Reverse passive latex agglutination). Positive isolates are sent to the National Reference Laboratory in Graz, where the Enterotoxins A, B, C1, C2, C3, D, E are identified via an ELFA (enzyme linked fluorescent assay). RPLA and ELISAs for further investigations on the enterotoxins may complete the analysis.

Results of the investigation

As it is not exactly known how many and which samples were tested for coagulase-positive staphylococci the results cannot be reported.

6.2. *Cronobacter sakazakii*

6.2.1. *Cronobacter sakazakii* in foodstuff

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Not available

Frequency of the sampling

Sampling distributed evenly throughout the year

Type of specimen taken

Infant formula

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Bacteriological method ISO 22964:2006

Control program/mechanisms

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Not available

Results of the investigation

See table

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Not available

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Not available

Additional information

Not available

Table 98 *Cronobacter sakazakii* in food, 2016

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Cronobacter sakazakii</i>
Infant formula	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	
		AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	3	0	
	Retail	XX	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	

6.3. Histamine

6.3.1. Histamine general evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Not available

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Not available

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Not available

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Not available

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Not available

Additional information

Not available

6.3.2. Histamine in foodstuff

Monitoring system**Sampling strategy**

Not available

Frequency of the sampling

Not available

Type of specimen taken

Fish, fishery products, cheese

Definition of positive finding

>200 mg histamine per kg fish - fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine - not enzyme matured

>400 mg histamine per kg fish - fishery products which have undergone enzyme maturation treatment in brine

>400 mg histamine per kg cheese

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

High performance liquid chromatography with UV detection; (HPLC-UV)

Control program/mechanisms**Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases**

Not available

Results of the investigation

See table

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infections

Not available

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Not available

Additional information

Not available

Table 99 Histamine in food, 2016

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units in non-conformity	< = 100	>100 to < = 200	>200 to < = 400	>400
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - hard - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Fish - Fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine - not enzyme matured	Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	1	0	0	0	0	1
		EU	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Retail	XE	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0
Fish - Fishery products which have undergone enzyme maturation treatment in brine	Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0
		XE	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Wholesale	XE	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0
Fish - raw	Retail	XE	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Fish - unspecified - frozen	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	30	2	0	0	2	0	0
Fishery products, unspecified	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
		EU	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Retail	XE	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0
		XX	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Fishery products, unspecified - cooked	Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
		XE	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Fishery products, unspecified - raw - chilled	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Molluscan shellfish - shelled, shucked and cooked - chilled	Catering	XX	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0

7. Food-borne outbreaks

Food-borne outbreaks are defined as two or more human cases of the same disease or infection where the cases are linked or are probably linked to the same food source. A situation in which the observed human cases exceed the expected number of cases and where a same food source is suspected, is also indicative of a food-borne outbreak.

A. Food-borne outbreaks

System in place for identification, epidemiological investigations and reporting of food-borne outbreaks

Presently, every district (n = 95) is responsible for outbreak investigation. However, the investigation of food-borne outbreaks affecting more than one district or even more than one province (Austria = 9 provinces) are regulated by the Federal Zoonoses Act (Zoonosengesetz, BGBl. I, 128/2005 entered into force on 1. January 2006). The Federal Zoonoses Commission was founded to advise the Federal Minister to survey and combat the zoonoses in Austria. One target of the Zoonoses Act is to ensure that food-borne outbreaks receive proper epidemiological investigation. It regulates, in case of food-borne outbreaks affecting more than one province, that the governors of the affected provinces provide operative units to investigate possible or confirmed food-borne outbreaks. Data concerning epidemiological criteria, potential implicated food items and the source of an outbreak must be collected and adequate epidemiological and microbiological examinations must be conducted. Short reports summarize each outbreak and must be communicated to the Federal Commission for Zoonoses and to AGES.

Description of the types of outbreaks covered by the reporting:

The large majority of food-borne outbreaks (77.5%) have been classified as household outbreaks because in most cases it has not been possible to merge different household outbreaks by identifying unique foodstuffs that human cases from different households consumed. Better coordinated investigation of outbreaks affecting more than one province - unhampered by district limits - could decrease the total number of outbreaks.

National evaluation of the reported outbreaks in the country: - Trends in numbers of outbreaks and numbers of human cases involved

In 2016, 80 food-borne outbreaks affecting 436 persons were reported. 68 persons were hospitalized and no lethal cases occurred. The total number of food-borne outbreaks increased by 3 % compared to 2015. The average number of cases affected by an outbreak was 5.5 persons, ranging from two to 102 persons per outbreak. 14 % (18 % in 2015, 13.5 % in 2014, 16 % in 2013, and 14 % in 2012) of the reported outbreaks were acquired abroad. 52 % of all food-borne outbreaks acquired in Austria were caused by *Campylobacter* spp. (n = 36), 44 % by *Salmonella* spp. (n = 30) and 60 % thereof by serotype Enteritidis (n = 18) compared to 69 % in 2015.

National evaluation of the reported outbreaks in the country: - Relevance of the different causative agents, food categories and the agent/food category combinations

Campylobacter and *Salmonella* pose the most important agents causing 95 % of all food borne outbreaks in Austria (85 % in 2015, 91 % in 2014, 77 % in 2013, and 93 % in 2012). Nine outbreaks (12.5%) were reported as outbreaks with strong evidence. The following food items have been associated with strong evidence to outbreaks: eggs and egg products (3 outbreaks) and one outbreak each by broiler meat and products thereof, cheese, turkey meat and products thereof, beef and products thereof, sheep meat and products thereof and a self-made cake. For the majority of outbreaks (weak evidence outbreaks), the data quality does not allow conclusions on the relevance of different food categories.

National evaluation of the reported outbreaks in the country: - Relevance of the different type of places of food production and preparation in outbreaks

At the present, the data quality does not allow conclusions on the relevance of the different type of places of food production and preparation in outbreaks.

National evaluation of the reported outbreaks in the country: - Evaluation of the severity and clinical picture of the human cases

In 2016, 15.6 % (25.8 % in 2015, 15.3 % in 2014; 19 % in 2013; 17.3 % in 2012) of patients affected by these food-borne outbreaks are reported as hospitalized; no one died in association with an outbreak.

National evaluation of the reported outbreaks in the country: - Descriptions of single outbreaks of special interest

National evaluation of the reported outbreaks in the country: - Control measures or other actions taken to improve the situation

Improvement due to the implementation of the Federal Zoonoses Act e.g. the chain of command in terms of investigation of food-borne outbreaks affecting more than one province was implemented.

National evaluation of the reported outbreaks in the country: - Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Additional information

The situation of food-borne outbreaks is published in the National Zoonoses Brochure.

Table 100 Food-borne outbreaks with food vehicle identified and strong evidence (EMS), 2016

FBO Code	Causative Agent	Number of Outbreaks	Number of Cases	Number of Hospitalised	Number of Deaths	Food Vehicle	Nature of Evidence linking the Outbreak with Food	Type of Outbreak	Setting	Place of Origin of Problem	Origin of Food Vehicle	Contributory Factors
1234	Norovirus	1	26	1	0	Sweets and chocolate	Analytical epidemiological evidence	General	Others	Household	XX	Unknown
1235	<i>S. Enteritidis</i> PT4	1	20	11	0	Eggs and egg products	Descriptive epidemiological evidence, Detection of causative agent in food vehicle or its component - Detection of indistinguishable causative agent in humans	General	Household	Farm	AT	Unprocessed contaminated ingredient
1236	<i>S. Enteritidis</i> PT8	1	8	0	0	Eggs and egg products	Descriptive epidemiological evidence, Detection of causative agent in food vehicle or its component - Detection of indistinguishable causative agent in humans	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Farm	AT	Unprocessed contaminated ingredient
4041	<i>S. Enteritidis</i> PT8	1	10	1	0	Eggs and egg products	Descriptive epidemiological evidence	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Household	XX	Unknown
4044	<i>S. Enteritidis</i> PT13a	1	9	2	0	Sheep meat and products thereof	Descriptive epidemiological evidence	General	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	Travel abroad, Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	XX	Cross-contamination
4267	<i>S. Enteritidis</i> PT8	1	2	0	0	Bovine meat and products thereof	Descriptive epidemiological evidence	General	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	Travel abroad	XX	Unknown
4327	<i>S. Enteritidis</i> PT2	1	2	2	0	Turkey meat and products thereof	Descriptive epidemiological evidence, Detection of causative agent in food vehicle or its component - Symptoms and onset of illness pathognomonic to causative agent	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Retail	XX	
Meta 36	<i>S. Senftenberg</i>	1	34	5	0	Broiler meat (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) and products thereof	Analytical epidemiological evidence, Detection of causative agent in food vehicle or its component - Detection of indistinguishable causative agent in humans	General	Household	Farm	AT	Unprocessed contaminated ingredient
Meta 39	<i>S. Enteritidis</i> PT6c	1	33	18	0	Cheese	Descriptive epidemiological evidence, Detection of causative agent in food vehicle or its component - Detection of indistinguishable causative agent in humans	General	Farm	Farm	AT	Other contributory factor

Data source: EMS as of March 17, 2017

Table 101 Food-borne outbreaks with no food vehicle identified or weak evidence, 2016

FBO Code	Causative Agent	Number of Outbreaks	Number of Cases	Number of Hospitalised	Number of Deaths	Food Vehicle	Nature of Evidence linking the Outbreak with Food	Type of Outbreak	Setting	Place of Origin of Problem	Origin of Food Vehicle	Contributory Factors
1237	<i>C. jejuni</i>	1	35	0	0	Tap water, including well water	Unknown	General	Household	Water source	AT	Untreated drinking water
1238	Norovirus	1	10	2	0	Unknown	Unknown	General	School or kindergarten	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3946	<i>C. jejuni</i>	1	3	0	0	Broiler meat (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) and products thereof	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	Take-away or fast-food outlet	XX	Unknown
3947	<i>C. jejuni</i>	1	2	2	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Travel abroad	XX	Unknown
3955	<i>S. Enteritidis</i> PT21	1	2	0	0	Broiler meat (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) and products thereof	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	Travel abroad, Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	XX	Unknown
3965	<i>C. jejuni</i>	1	3	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Travel abroad, Household	XX	Unknown
3968	<i>C. jejuni</i>	1	2	0	0	Fish and fish products	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen		Retail, Household	EU	Unknown
3983	<i>C. jejuni</i>	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3994	<i>C. jejuni</i>	1	2	1	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
4010	<i>Campylobacter</i> , unspecified	1	3	3	0	Unknown	Unknown	General	Others	Others	EU	Unknown
4012	<i>S. Enteritidis</i> PT4b	1	4	2	0	Other, mixed or unspecified poultry meat and products thereof	Unknown	General	Others	Others	EU	Unknown
4013	<i>C. jejuni</i>	1	2	1	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
4014	<i>C. jejuni</i>	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
4018	<i>S. Enteritidis</i> PT13a	1	2	1	0	Eggs and egg products	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Retail, Household	XX	Unknown
4032	<i>S. Typhimurium</i>	1	2	1	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household /	Household		XX	

Food-borne outbreaks

FBO Code	Causative Agent	Number of Outbreaks	Number of Cases	Number of Hospitalised	Number of Deaths	Food Vehicle	Nature of Evidence linking the Outbreak with Food	Type of Outbreak	Setting	Place of Origin of Problem	Origin of Food Vehicle	Contributory Factors
	U 277							domestic kitchen				
4035	<i>S. Enteritidis</i> PT6c	1	3	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	General	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	XX	Unknown
4037	<i>C. jejuni</i>	1	2	0	0	Turkey meat and products thereof	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Take-away or fast-food outlet	Take-away or fast-food outlet	XX	Unknown
4047	<i>C. coli</i>	1	2	0	0	Broiler meat (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) and products thereof	Unknown	General	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
4050	<i>C. jejuni</i>	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Household		XX	Unknown
4061	<i>C. jejuni</i>	1	2	0	0	Broiler meat (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) and products thereof	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Household	XX	Inadequate heat treatment
4066	<i>C. jejuni</i>	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	Travel abroad	XX	
4068	<i>C. jejuni</i>	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
4069	<i>S. Enteritidis</i> PT4	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Unknown	XX	Unknown
4073	<i>C. jejuni</i>	1	3	0	0	Mixed food	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Others	Others	XX	Storage time/temperature abuse, Inadequate chilling, Inadequate heat treatment
4078	<i>S. Enteritidis</i> PT13a	1	3	1	0	Buffet meals	Unknown	General	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service		XX	
4079	<i>C. jejuni</i>	1	2	0	0	Other, mixed or unspecified poultry meat and products thereof	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Household	AT	Unknown
4085	<i>C. jejuni</i>	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	

Food-borne outbreaks

FBO Code	Causative Agent	Number of Outbreaks	Number of Cases	Number of Hospitalised	Number of Deaths	Food Vehicle	Nature of Evidence linking the Outbreak with Food	Type of Outbreak	Setting	Place of Origin of Problem	Origin of Food Vehicle	Contributory Factors
4090	<i>S. Typhimurium</i> RDNC	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
4091	<i>C. jejuni</i>	1	3	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Household	XX	
4097	<i>C. jejuni</i>	1	2	0	0	Broiler meat (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) and products thereof	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Household	XX	Unknown
4115	<i>C. jejuni</i>	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	
4122	<i>S. Enteritidis</i> PT8	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
4139	<i>S. Typhimurium</i> , monophasic - DT193	1	2	1	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Household	XX	Unknown
4144	<i>S. Enteritidis</i> Not typable	1	3	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Household	XX	
4146	<i>C. jejuni</i>	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
4149	<i>C. jejuni</i>	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Household	XX	Unknown
4151	<i>C. jejuni</i>	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	General	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
4162	<i>S. Coeln</i>	1	2	1	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Others	Unknown	XX	Unknown
4165	<i>S. Enteritidis</i> PT8	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	
4167	<i>S. Enteritidis</i> PT8	1	3	1	0	Other foods	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	Travel abroad	XX	Unknown
4173	<i>C. jejuni</i>	1	2	0	0	Buffet meals	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	XX	Unknown
4176	<i>C. jejuni</i>	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Unknown	XX	Unknown
4177	<i>C. jejuni</i>	1	2	1	0	Unknown	Unknown	General	Unknown	Others	XX	Unknown
4179	<i>C. jejuni</i>	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Unknown	XX	Unknown

Food-borne outbreaks

FBO Code	Causative Agent	Number of Outbreaks	Number of Cases	Number of Hospitalised	Number of Deaths	Food Vehicle	Nature of Evidence linking the Outbreak with Food	Type of Outbreak	Setting	Place of Origin of Problem	Origin of Food Vehicle	Contributory Factors
4180	<i>S. Enteritidis</i> PT4	1	2	1	0	Broiler meat (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) and products thereof	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Household	AT	Unknown
4184	<i>C. jejuni</i>	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
4192	<i>C. jejuni</i>	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
4200	<i>S. Enteritidis</i> PT8	1	2	0	0	Eggs and egg products	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	Travel abroad, Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	XX	Unprocessed contaminated ingredient, Inadequate heat treatment
4206	<i>Campylobacter</i> , unspecified	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Household	XX	Unknown
4208	<i>S. Enteritidis</i> PT4	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Other contributory factor
4211	<i>S. Enteritidis</i> PT21	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Travel abroad	XX	Unknown
4212	<i>C. jejuni</i>	1	2	1	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
4213	<i>S. Typhimurium</i> RDNC	1	3	0	0	Fish and fish products	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	Unknown	AT	Unknown
4223	<i>S. Typhimurium</i> DT1	1	3	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Household	XX	
4235	<i>S. Typhimurium</i> , monophasic - DT193	1	2	1	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
4236	<i>S. Braenderup</i>	1	2	1	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
4242	<i>C. jejuni</i>	1	2	0	0	Broiler meat (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) and products thereof	Unknown	General	Unknown	Travel abroad, Unknown	EU	Unknown
4251	VTEC O157	1	3	0	0	Pig meat and products thereof	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Household	XX	Unknown

Food-borne outbreaks

FBO Code	Causative Agent	Number of Outbreaks	Number of Cases	Number of Hospitalised	Number of Deaths	Food Vehicle	Nature of Evidence linking the Outbreak with Food	Type of Outbreak	Setting	Place of Origin of Problem	Origin of Food Vehicle	Contributory Factors
4253	<i>S. Enteritidis</i> PT53	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	General	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	Travel abroad, Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	XX	Unknown
4258	<i>S. Enteritidis</i> PT21	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	General	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
4274	<i>C. jejuni</i>	1	3	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
4277	<i>S. Typhimurium</i> U 311	1	2	1	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Household	XX	Unknown
4278	<i>C. jejuni</i>	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
4286	<i>C. jejuni</i>	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
4290	<i>S. Enteritidis</i> PT21	1	3	3	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Household	XX	Unknown
4294	<i>C. jejuni</i>	1	2	0	0	Other foods	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	XE	Unknown
4322	<i>C. jejuni</i>	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
4330	<i>S. Enteritidis</i> PT20a	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
4338	<i>S. Infantis</i>	1	2	1	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
4340	<i>S. Typhimurium</i> DT193	1	3	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
4359	<i>C. jejuni</i>	1	2	1	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown

Data source: EMS as of March 17, 2017

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